

Egyptian Journal of Plant Protection Research Institute

Volume 5: No. (1), March , 2022

President of the Journal: Prof. Dr. Ahmed Abd El Mageed

Editor –in-Chief : Prof. Dr. Shaaban Abd-Rabou

Secretary of the Journal

Prof. Dr. Shaaban Abd-Rabou

Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Noha H. Ahmed

Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Editorial Board Abroad

Dr. Alvin M. Simmons, FRES

Research Entomologist
USDA, ARS, U.S. Vegetable Laboratory
2700 Savannah Highway
Charleston, SC 29414
USA

Prof. Dr. Dong Chu

College of Plant Health and Medicine
Qingdao Agricultural University
No. 700, Changcheng Road
Chengyang, Qingdao, Shandong 266109
CHINA

Dr. Doo-Sang Park,

Korean Collection for Type Cultures (KCTC),
Microbiological Resource Center,
Korea Research Institute of Bioscience & Biotechnology (KRIBB), 125 Gwahangno,
Yuseong, Daejeon 305-806,
SOUTH KOREA

Dr. Gregory A. Evans

USDA/ APHIS/ PPQ c/o Systematic Entomology Laboratory
Bldg 005, Room 137,
BARC-WEST 10300 Baltimore Ave.
Beltsville, MD 20705
USA

Prof. Dr. Hassan Ghahari
Department of Entomology
Science & Research Campus
Islamic Azad University
Poonak – Hesarak
Tehran
IRAN

Dr. HDR. Hélène Delatte
UMR "Peuplements Végétaux et Bio-agresseurs en Milieu Tropical"
CIRAD-3P 7, Chemin de l'IRAT
Ligne Paradis
97410 Saint Pierre
La Réunion
FRANCE

Egyptian Editorial Board

Prof. Dr. Mohamed Ibrahim Abdel Mageed
University of Ain Shames
Faculty of Agriculture,
Cairo,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Mohamed Gomaa Abbass
Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Aly Soliman
Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Aly H. El-Sherbiny
Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Eman Radwan
Central Agricultural Pesticides Laboratory,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Magdy Welson
Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Mahmoud El-Naggar
Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Mohammad Hendi
Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Egyptian Journal of Plant Protection Research Institute *is* an official journal of the Plant Protection Research Institute, *Agricultural* Research Center. It includes original research papers on basic and applied research in all aspects of plant protection. In addition to original research papers, also published reviews and scientific notes or short communications on critical issues relevant to plant protection. Subject areas include, but are not restricted to the following fields: Field pests, vegetable, aromatic, medicinal and ornamental plant pests, orchard pests, locust and grasshopper, beekeeping sericulture, spray technology, alternatives methods of control pests, survey and classification of agriculture pests and new biocontrol technology pests

Abbreviation of the Journal: Egypt. J. of Plant Prot. Res. Inst. `

Egyptian Journal of Plant Protection Research Institute
Volume 5: No. (1), March , 2022

Contents

- 1- **Abd Allah, Y. N. M. ; Refaei, B.M. ; Metwally, S. A. G. ; Ibrahim, S.A. and El Sawaf, B.M. (2022):** Interaction between certain weather factors and plant age of cantaloupe on *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) infestation over different sowing dates. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst. (2022), 5 (1): 1–18. **1–18**
- 2- **Abd Allah, Y. N. M. ; Metwally, S. A. G. ; Refaei, B.M. ; Ibrahim, S.A. and El Sawaf, B.M. (2022):** *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) infestation and yield cantaloupe production in relation to inorganic fertilization. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst. (2022), 5 (1): 19–28. **19–28**
- 3- **Salman, A.M.A.; Attia, S.A.; Foad, H.A. and Assakar, H.H.I. (2022):** Ecological aspects on California red scale *Aonidiella aurantii* (Hemiptera: Diaspididae) on mandarin trees in Sohag Governorate, Egypt. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst. (2022), 5 (1): 29–39. **29-39**
- 4- **Ibrahim, F. Khafagy ; Heba, S. Abd El-Aty and Ghada, M. Ramadan (2022):** Impact of aromatic plants intercropped with sugar beet on infestation by cotton leafworm, sugar beet fly and associated predators. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst. (2022), 5 (1): 40–46. **40–46**
- 5- **Raafat, Badr Abo Arab and Nariman, M. El-Tawelah (2022):** Impacting of some selected plant and cattle dung powders as protectants against *Tribolium castaneum* (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) and *Sitophilus oryzae* (Coleoptera Curculionidae) adults. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst. (2022), 5 (1): 47–62. **47–62**
- 6- **Shaaban, Abd-Rabou¹; El-Amir, S. M.¹ and Xiao-Wei, Wang² (2022):** Efficacy of different natural compounds on cotton and tomato whitefly *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) and its parasitoid *Eretmocerus mundus* (Hymenoptera: Aphelinidae) on vegetable crops. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst. (2022), 5 (1): 63–77. **63–77**
- 7- **Abd Allah, Y. N. M. ; Metwally, S. A. G. ; Refaei, B.M. and El Sawaf, B.M. (2022):** Leaf morphological characters can be a factor for intra-varietal preference of whitefly *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) among certain cantaloupe cultivars. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst. (2022), 5 (1): 78–425. **78–93**
- 8- **Abd Allah, Y. N. M. ; Metwally, S. A. G. ; Ibrahim, S.A. ; Refaei, B.M. and El Sawaf, B.M. (2022):** Interaction effect of cantaloupe cultivars and sowing date on *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) infestation and yield parameters. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst. (2022), 5 (1): 94–101. **94–101**
- 9- **Mervat, A. Kandil; Omnia, Sh. G. Sheba and Hussein, A.M. good (2022):** Diflubenzuron and lufenuron exposed to magnetic flux for *Earias insulana* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) suppression. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst. (2022), 5 (1): 102–109. **102–109**

Continued

- 10- Ismail, G.H.; Abou-Hashem, A. A. M. and Fatma, K. Khider (2022):** Effect of methomyl on certain land snails under field conditions. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst. (2022), 5 (1): 110–115. **110–115**
- 11- Amany, Saad M. Abou-Lila ; Taksira, D.M.; Hebat Allah, S. Elsayh, and Sawires, S.G. (2022):** Morphological forms of varroa mites (Acari and Varroidae) in Egypt and Lebanon by means of scanning electron microscope. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst. (2022), 5 (1): 116–122. **116–122**

Egyptian Journal of Plant
Protection Research Institute

www.ejppri.eg.net

Interaction between certain weather factors and plant age of cantaloupe on *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) infestation over different sowing dates

Abd Allah, Y. N. M. ¹; Refaei, B.M. ²; Metwally, S. A. G. ¹; Ibrahim, S.A. ¹
and El Sawaf, B.M. ²

¹Plant Protection Research Institute, Agriculture Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

²Entomology Department, Faculty of Science, Ain Shams University, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 2 /1/2022

Accepted: 18/ 3 /2022

Keywords

Weather factors, plant age, *Bemisia tabaci*, *Cucumis melo* L., sowing dates, and cantaloupe.

Abstract:

To study the effect of certain weather factors and plant age over three sowing dates on the whitefly; *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) infesting cantaloupe plants, field experiments were carried out over summer plantation three successive growing seasons; 2015, 2016, and 2017 in Qaha, Qalyubiya Governorate. The results revealed that *B. tabaci* eggs and nymphs have differed significantly among the three tested sowing dates (Mar.16, Apr. 2, and Apr. 16) over the tested growing seasons. Statistical analysis revealed that *B. tabaci* oviposition was significantly affected by plant age. The polynomial regression model explained 90.13, 84.97, and 61.5% of the variability of *B. tabaci* oviposition over Mar.16, Apr. 2, and Apr. 16, respectively in 2015. In 2016, the polynomial regression model explained 95.6% of *B. tabaci* laying eggs on Mar. 16, however, the insignificant role was clear on Apr. 2 and Apr. 16. In 2017, the plant age was significant on Apr.2 only (81.74%). The nymph activity was significantly affected by plant age in the three tested sowing dates as 87.8, 92.7, and 95.1 %, respectively over 2015; 90.66, 82.2, and 91.6%, respectively, over 2016 and 90.5,3, 82.4 and 80.72%, respectively, over 2017. Concerning the changes that occurred in *B. tabaci* oviposition the changes in the environmental variables altogether were insignificant over 2015 and 2016. However, in 2017, the role of the three weather factors altogether had a significant response only in on Mar.16 (70.9%). Effect on nymphal activity in 2015, the combined role of the climatic factors had a significant influence on Mar.16 (77.8 %), however, it had an insignificant effect on Apr. 2 and Apr. 16. In 2016 and 2017, the combined role of the three weather factors was insignificant in the nymphal infestation. The combined effect of meteorological parameters and plant age altogether confirmed that the plant age on different sowing dates plays a significant role in the *B. tabaci* build up on cantaloupe more than weather variables and thus represented by their contribution with higher percentages than the studied weather factors with *B. tabaci* oviposition and nymphal infestation. In other words, plant age reflected different morphological and leaf compositions in different growth stages which may affect egg laying (Morphological traits) and the insect life as a source of its feeding (Biochemical elements).

Introduction

To escape, *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) infestation on cantaloupe plants in the field, there was a great demand to study certain ecological parameters affecting *B. tabaci* in the field. The first step of this approach is to study the effect of climatic factors (Including prevailing weather conditions i.e., the maximum temperature, the minimum temperature, and the mean relative humidity) and plant age as well as infestation levels of the insect. This pattern enables us to predict *B. tabaci* infestation by temperature and humidity. Besides, studying the interaction between plant age and physical factor/pest dynamics in the sowing dates is necessary. This information may enable good planning to prevent the pest from reaching a heavy infestation or economic threshold and consequently save the loss in yield.

Devi and Ram (2018) found that the delay of the planting date has significantly increased the infestation of *B. tabaci*. The activity and incidence of pest infestation are influenced to a large extent by climatic conditions. Consequently, parasitoids and predators were affected (Chaudhuri *et al.*, 1999 and Arif *et al.*, 2006). Information with respect to pest population dynamics in relation to meteorological parameters such as temperatures, humidity, rainfall, and sunshine hours is used in planning a weather based pest forewarning model (Selvaraj and Ramesh, 2012).

The aim of the present work is to study the effect of certain weather factors and plant age over three sowing dates on the whitefly *B. tabaci* infesting cantaloupe plants.

Materials and methods

An area of about 1,400 m² represented the experimental area in 2015, 2016, and 2017. This field study was carried out in the Experimental

Farm of Plant Protection Research Institute in Qaha region, southwest of Qalyubiya Governorate (30°17'00 "N, 31° 12'00 "E of 133 meters (436 ft) below sea level) in Egypt over the summer plantation. Cantaloupe seeds were sown directly in successive single rows on the southern edges. Each plot (Replicate) measured 11.9 m². Rows are designed as 7 plants per row spaced 0.30 m apart. The four tested cultivars; Arava, Majus, Darvina, and Royal 481 were planted on the three tested fortnight dates (Mar. 16, Apr. 2, and 16.) under a complete randomized block design (CRBD) over the three years of study.

The tested meteorological parameters were maximum temperature (Mix. T.), minimum temperature (Min. T.), and daily mean relative humidity (RH.). The relationship between the tested ecological factors and *B. tabaci* activity is well studied. Means of *B. tabaci* eggs and nymphs were tabulated against the corresponding weather data. The simple correlation coefficient values, linear regression, and multiple regression between the mean counts of *B. tabaci* eggs and nymphs in weeks plotted to weekly tested weather factors. The percentages of explained variance (E.V. %) as the combined effect of the weather factors were considered. Plant age in weeks (Representing the continuous nutritional values over the growing season) and the percentages of explained variance (E.V. %) as the combined effect of plant age and the percentages of explained variance (E.V.%) of three weather factors and the three plant ages altogether were successfully calculated.

1. Whitefly sampling procedures:

During the three vegetative growing seasons (2015, 2016, and 2017) assessments were conducted 30 days following cultivation and continued weekly. Cantaloupe leaves

(360) were randomly picked up as possible representing all plant levels from the three tested sowing dates (10 leaves * 3 plots * 4 cultivars * 3 sowing dates). Leaves samples were kept separately in polyethylene bags to be transferred to the laboratory. The presence of whitefly *B. tabaci* eggs and nymphs was examined with the aid of a binocular stereomicroscope. The number of eggs and nymphs was assessed on the abaxial leaf surface. Then, the number of eggs and nymphs per the three replicates in each experiment was estimated.

2. Meteorological data:

The data of different meteorological data, such as maximum and minimum temperatures and relative humidity over 2015, 2016, and 2017 were acquired from www.wunderground.com.

3. Data analysis:

All the obtained data during the trials over the three growing seasons were subjected to analysis by using SAS (SAS Institute, 1988) program. Simple correlation and linear regression were calculated according to the relation:

$$Y = a + bX$$

The effect of a single weather factor was considered linear regression. The partial regression was used to obtain the amount of variability in the pest activity which could be attributed to the percentages of explained variance (E.V.%) as the combined effect of the climatic factors. In the multiple regression of interaction between weather factors and plant age on three sowing dates, the combined effect of weather factors was considered as multiple linear regression as $Y = a \pm b_1 \text{ Max. T.} \pm b_2 \text{ Min.T.} \pm b_3 \text{ RH. Plant age in weeks}$ (Presenting the continuous nutritional values over the growing season) was considered as the third

degree of polynomial ($Y = a \pm b_1 \text{ Age} \pm b_2 \text{ Age}^2 \pm b_3 \text{ Age}^3$).

The combined effect of weather factors and plant age was considered as multiple regression, presented as $Y = a \pm b_1 \text{ Max. T.} \pm b_2 \text{ Min.T.} \pm b_3 \text{ RH.} \pm b_4 \text{ Age} \pm b_5 \text{ Age}^2 \pm b_6 \text{ Age}^3$.

Results and discussion

The obtained results presented in Tables (1-9) showed the interaction between Max.T., Min.T., mean RH. %, and cantaloupe plant age (As the third degree of polynomial) on means of deposit *B. tabaci* eggs and nymphal activity over three summer plantation sowing dates of three consecutive growing seasons.

1. Effect of weather factors and plant age on deposited *Bemisia tabaci* eggs on different sowing dates:

In 2015, data are shown in Table (2) indicated Max.T., Min. T. and RH. % had an insignificant negative correlation with eggs on the first sowing date (r values were -0.43, -0.7, and -0.2, respectively). Partial regression indicated that the effect of minimum temperature (In the presence of the other two weather factors was negative and significant while the two other factors were insignificant.

On the second sowing date (Apr. 2) maximum and minimum temperatures had an insignificant positive relation to the numbers of laid eggs (r= 0.4 and 0.3, respectively). The insignificant negative relation of RH. was detected (r= -0.3). The observations on Apr.16 indicated an insignificant and negative association of Max. T., Min. T. and RH. with deposited eggs on cantaloupe. Where this relation was weak in the case of Max. T. (Table 2).

Concerning the changes that occurred in *B. tabaci* eggs due to the changes in the environmental variables altogether in the first sowing date, the multiple regression model explained

68.6%. Besides, this effect decreased by delaying the sowing date by 15 days (Apr. 2) as E.V. = 20.15 % and increased again by delaying the date of sowing month (Apr. 16) E.V. = 49.58%.

The effect of plant age on the three sowing dates revealed that egg oviposition was significantly affected by plant age during the three sowing dates. The polynomial regression model explained 90.13, 84.97, and 61.5% in the variability of *B. tabaci* egg oviposition over first, second, and third sowing dates, respectively.

In other words, the combined effect of three tested climatic factors and plant age altogether in the first sowing date indicated that the activity of *B. tabaci* adults in laying eggs was affected by plant age than by meteorological parameters where the multiple regression model explained 91.7% as the plant age contributed with 90.13%. Likewise, the combined effect in the second and third dates were 96.6 and 64.4 %, respectively, and the contribution of plant age with high percentages in these values. As a result, the plant age was an effective factor in *B. tabaci* laying eggs and influenced oviposition preference by a big magnitude over this season.

The obtained results in Table (4) over 2016 clearly indicated that, the relation of Max. T. with *B. tabaci* eggs number in the three sowing dates was explained by a linear regression model which indicated by insignificant negative r values = -0.2, -0.056, and -0.3, respectively. Besides, a negative relation was detected between Min. T. and egg numbers in the three tested sowing dates (r= -0.5, -0.1, and -0.5, respectively). However, RH. had insignificant positive relation on the first date and an insignificant negative on the second and third dates (r= 0.3, -0.5, and -0.3, respectively).

At the same in the previous year, the role of the three climatic

factors in laying eggs on cantaloupe plants was insignificant. Moreover, it decreased by delaying the sowing date and the multiple regression model explained 53.04 and 47.1, 29.5 % the in the variability of *B. tabaci* laying eggs on first, second and third sowing dates, respectively. With respect to the effect of plant age, the combined role indicated that the role of plant age was highly significant on egg laying on cantaloupe plants. In particular, the third degree polynomial regression model explained 95.6 % of the variability of *B. tabaci* laying eggs on Mar. 16. However, the insignificant role of plant age was clear on Apr. 2 and Apr. 16 as polynomial regression model explained 57.9 and 68.8%, respectively. On Mar. 16, the combined effect of weather factors and plant age altogether, cleared that the egg laying in this season also, was highly influenced by plant age than the tested weather factors as the multiple regression model explained 99.9 % as the plant age contributed with 95.6 % from this percentage. By delaying the sowing date 15 days (Apr. 2) or a month (Apr. 16) it was found that, the combined role of tested factors expressed an insignificant effect on laying eggs and the multiple regression model explained 82.72 % and significant effect as 94.4 %, respectively. The same trend was observed at the plant age had a great influence on laying *B. tabaci* eggs than the other tested meteorological factors.

The obtained data in Table (6) indicated that the results in 2017 came to confirm the test in previous years. The correlation coefficient values of the meteorological factors with *B. tabaci* eggs indicated that insignificant negative relation was found between Mix. T. on Mar. 16 and Apr. 16 (r= -0.3 and -0.1, respectively). Likewise, Min. T. had an insignificant negative relation with eggs number on the same

dates as -0.3 and -0.1, respectively. Whereas, on Apr. 2 the correlation of Mix. T. and Min. T. were best explained by the linear regression model as indicated by significant r values = -0.7 and -0.8, respectively ($P < 0.05$).

In the case of RH., there was an insignificant and negative response on *B. tabaci* eggs on Mar. 16 and Apr. 2 as correlation coefficient values $r = -0.5$ and -0.3 . However, this relation was significant on Apr. 16 as $r = -0.8$, however, regression value $b = 0.6$ i.e. as the RH. (45.8%) increase the laying of *B. tabaci* eggs decreased by 0.6 eggs/leaf in Qaha. The role of the three weather factors altogether had a significant response in the first sowing date as the multiple regression model explained 70.9% of the variability in *B. tabaci* laying eggs. This response was insignificant and decreased by delaying the date 15 days (67.33%) or a month (60.81%).

Concerning the changes that occurred in deposited eggs by *B. tabaci* in cantaloupe plants due to growing up in cantaloupe plants. The plant age played an important and significant role in laying eggs over the second date, Apr. 2 as a multiple regression model explained 81.74% variability in *B. tabaci* laying eggs. However, this relation was insignificant in the first and third sowing dates 60.97 and 61.4%, respectively. The multiple regression model of the tested climatic factors and plant age altogether in the first, second, and third dates explained 77.3, 98.02, and 99.2 %, respectively. In other words, the role of all climatic factors in the variability in whitefly laying eggs was higher on the first date than the role of the plant age and significantly affected whitefly laying eggs this year. Whereas in the delayed (Apr. 16) sowing dates, plant age contributed with a high percentage in the combined effect of weather factors and plant age altogether (Table 6).

2. Effect of weather factors and plant age on nymphal activity in different sowing dates:

In 2015 the population varied in the three sowing dates in relation to weather factors and cantaloupe plant age (Tables 1 and 7). In this sense, on the first sowing date (Mar. 16), Mix.T. and Min. T. had a strong positive response on population ($r = 0.7$ and 0.9 , respectively) In other words, as the Mix.T. increased one unit pest population may increase by 1.5 nymphs/ leaf. Moreover, increasing Min.T. one unit also resulted in a significant increase in population by 2.6 nymphs/leaf in Qaha region during 2015. This means the average mean of Mix. T. and Min. T. (30.93 and 22.43 °C, respectively) was favorable for nymphal activity. However, the very weak association between RH. and the nymph population was detected as $r = 0.002$. On the subsequent dates; Apr. 2 and Apr. 16 the Mix. T. had an insignificant positive effect on nymphs ($r = 0.6$ and 0.1 , respectively). The strong positive correlation and significant effect of Min. T. was detected on the second sowing date (Apr. 2) ($r = 0.83$) and insignificant negative on the third sowing date as r values = -0.2 . On the contrary, a very weak association was detected between RH. and nymphal infestation on the first date, however, an insignificant positive relation was detected in the second sowing date as $r = 0.2$. While, the significant role of RH. was cleared in the third sowing date as it was negatively correlated with *B. tabaci* nymph population, and whitefly increased by decreasing RH. by 1.2 nymph /leaf. The combined role of the climatic factors had a significant influence on the first sowing date as multiple regression model explained 77.8 %, however, it had insignificant effect in the second and third ones as E.V.% = 71.96 and 55.1, respectively.

The nymph survival and activity was significantly affected by plant age in the three tested sowing dates and this was clear from the combined effect of plant age as it influenced nymph survival by 87.8, 92.7 and 95.1 % ($P < 0.01$) in the first, second and third sowing dates, respectively. Regarding the interaction between climatic factors and plant age the explained variance had great influence on nymphs activity with great percent as E.V.% = 93.6, 96.97, and 96.6 %, respectively. In other word, plant age as source of food influence the activity of *B. tabaci* nymphs than the climatic factors.

In 2016, the influence of certain of weather factors, plant age and the combined role of them altogether on *B. tabaci* nymph build up in the three tested sowing dates shown in Table (8). In the first sowing date (Mar. 16), the Mix. T. had insignificant positive influence on *B. tabaci* nymph activity as r value = 0.5. Moreover, Mix. T. had weak association with nymphs population in the second and third sowing dates. On the other hand, the

On the other hand, the third degree of polynomial regression model of cantaloupe age explained 90.66, 82.2 and 91.6% in the variability of *B. tabaci* build up on Mar.16, Apr.2 and Apr.16 dates, respectively and it had a highly significant response on the occurrence of nymph population on cantaloupe leaves especially in the first and third sowing dates ($P < 0.01$). The multiple regression model of weather factors and cantaloupe age altogether on *B. tabaci* buildup explained 99.4, 96.2 and 98.4% in variability of pests in the first, second and third dates, respectively. These values reflected the role of the combined effect of the three weather factors on *B. tabaci* development was lower than the role of the plant age in the three tested sowing dates. As a result, the population buildup was significantly affected by biotic

positive correlation of Min. T. was best explained by linear regression as indicated by significant values of $r = 0.8$ and ($P < 0.05$) in the first sowing date. Min. T. had insignificant positive and negative response on nymphal activity in the second and third dates as r values = 0.4 and - 0.2, respectively. The mean of relative humidity had insignificant negative influence on the insect activity the first and third sowing dates ($r = -0.6$ and -0.6 , respectively). Besides, RH had weak negative association with nymphs in the second sowing date.

Regarding change occurred in *B. tabaci* nymph development due to the changes in the weather factors in three tested sowing dates, the multiple regression model explained 75.9% in variability of *B. tabaci* activity $P < 0.05$. However, the combined role of the three weather factors was insignificant and decreased by delaying sowing which was 51.03 % in second sowing date and 34.97 % in the third sowing date.

(Represented plant age) to large extent, especially in the first and third sowing dates followed by abiotic factors (represented the environmental variables) in this season .

In 2017, with regard to the weather factors on the three sowing dates the correlation of Mix. T. and Min. T. were best explained by the linear regression model as indicated r values = 0.3 and 0.3 on Mar. 16, $r = 0.4$ and 0.5 on Apr. 2 and 0.1 and 0.2 on Apr. 16. On the other hand, RH had insignificant negative association with nymph population in the first sowing date ($r = -0.3$). Whereas, weak associations with nymphs were detected in the second and third dates. The effect of three weather factors altogether on the occurrence of *B. tabaci* was insignificant and didn't affected by the three tested sowing dates (14. 37, 49.1

and 37.8 %, respectively). The polynomial regression model of plant age explained 90.53, 82.4 and 80.35% in the activity and occurrence of nymphs and these values were significant and affected by delaying sowing date. The multiple regression model explained 94.83, 82.4 and 80.72% in first, second and third sowing dates, respectively. Subsequently, the combined effect of meteorological parameters and plant age altogether confirmed that, the plant age was more effective and play principal role in *B. tabaci* infestation and thus represented by their contribution with higher percentages than the studied weather factors in the three tested sowing dates. Besides, the overall combined effect decreased by delaying sowing date (Table 9).

The effect of Mix. T., Min. T. and RH. on *B. tabaci* egg deposition and nymphal activity in the three tested sowing dates under investigation over summer plantation seasons of 2015, 2016 and 2017. Revealed that, the tested weather factors had a non significant negative effect on *B. tabaci* egg laying in three tested sowing dates except on the first sowing date of 2017. The plant age had a significant effect on egg laying on cantaloupe leaves over the three tested sowing. Moreover, the combined effect of weather factors and plant age had a non significant effect on laying egg in most cases. On the other hand, the temperature (Mix. T. and Min. T.) had a positive effect on nymphal activity. The relative humidity had a negative impact in most instances. The combined role of the three tested weather factors was significant in the first sowing date over 2015 and 2017. The plant age played a primary and significant role on *B. tabaci* nymphal infestation. The combined role of weather factors and plant age altogether had significant effect in most instances on *B. tabaci* nymphal activity. The

current investigation revealed that, the plant age in different sowing dates played a significant role in the *B. tabaci* build up on cantaloupe more than weather variables in most instances. In other words, plant age reflected different morphological and leaf compositions in different growth stages which may affect egg laying (Morphological traits) and the insect life as a source of its feeding (biochemical elements). The weather factors also affect the insect survival but it came next to plant age in most instances in this work.

Our results were compatible to the results of Hanafy (2007) who demonstrated in a field study on sweet pea plants that the plant age and climatic factors affect thrips during the four planting dates. The plant age affects thrips populations more than weather factors in most dates. Smith (2005) reported that factors intrinsic to insects, plants, and the environment can substantially alter the expression of resistance-related genes in plants. Khan *et al.* (1999) revealed that aphids population increased with increasing the plant age. Leite *et al.* (2006) suggested that *B. tabaci* was affected by plant aging. Maximum temperature expressed positive correlation with *B. tabaci* population (Soni and Dhakad, 2017). Selvaraj and Ramesh (2012) indicated that maximum and minimum temperatures had positive and significant responses and the evening relative humidity had negative and significant responses on the development of *B. tabaci*. Abdel-Rahman *et al.* (2018) indicated in a study in Egypt that, the maximum and minimum temperatures had non-significant positive responses on *B. tabaci* infesting cotton, however, relative humidity had a highly negative and significant correlation.

Our findings revealed that maximum and minimum temperatures

had a positive response to *B. tabaci* nymphal activity in most instances over the three sowing dates. However, relative humidity had a negative impact on *B. tabaci* population. Plant age affects *B. tabaci* laying eggs and nymphs activity more than the weather factors in the three sowing dates. The information on this topic can lead to

better predictive capabilities in *B. tabaci* management. The prediction of the highest colonization according to obtained results from population corresponding to weather factors and plant age may provide IPM system about the appropriate time to take control option before the highest population builds up.

Table (1): Mean values of temperatures and relative humidity registered in the weeks of sampling of *Bemisia tabaci* eggs or nymphs on cantaloupe in the three sowing dates over the 2015 summer plantation season in Qaha, Qalyubiya Governorate.

Sampling date	Temp. (°C)		RH. (%) Mean	Mean of <i>Bemisia tabaci</i> eggs/ leaf			Mean of <i>Bemisia tabaci</i> nymphs/ leaf		
	Max.	Min.		Mar. 16	Apr. 2	Apr. 16	Mar. 16	Apr. 2	Apr. 16
Apr. 16	20.57	12.14	51.86	10.03	-	-	1.03	-	-
23	26.86	15.14	40.57	21.13	5.77	-	2.53	0.15	-
30	29.86	15.57	40.14	15.4	12.4	-	12.14	2.4	-
May 7	28.57	16.14	53.86	16.82	11.22	1.02	11.4	4.21	2.49
13	30.16	18.83	45.83	12.02	14.74	16.94	12.41	10.52	9.85
20	32.3	18.3	47.57	8.91	14.4	25.67	15.03	35.03	17.22
27	36.14	21.43	35.43	6.2	16.2	9.99	20.7	28.74	26.80
Jun. 3	29.43	19.57	47.43	4.03	16.22	5.98	30.11	38.46	21.63
10	32.14	20.71	45.87	2.85	14.34	3.14	21.93	37.57	18.31
17	32.28	21.14	53.57	1.66	4.4	1.44	23.75	32.73	15.77
24	32.6	22.43	48.3	-	-	0.53	-	-	9.195
Jul. 1	32.28	22.14	48	-	-	0.08	-	-	3.45
8	32.43	22.14	55	-	-	0.08	-	-	2.35
15	33.3	22.86	56	-	-	0.09	-	-	1.175
22	35	23	49.3	-	-	0.07	-	-	0.20
Mean	30.93	19.44	47.9	9.89	12.2	5.42	15.10	21.1	10.70

Table (2): Multiple regression of abiotic factors and plant age on *Bemisia tabaci* egg numbers in different sowing dates over 2015.

Sowing date	Factor	Level	Simple corr. and reg.			Multiple reg.			E.V.%	F	P
			R	B	P	b	P				
Mar. 16	Weather factors	Max. T.	-0.43	-0.7	0.2	1.2	0.2	68.6	4.37	0.059	
		Min. T.	-0.7	-1.5	0.02	-3.02	0.04				
		RH.	-0.2	-0.21	0.6	-0.1	0.7				
	Plant age ¹ - age ³ Combined effect		-	-	-	-	-	90.13	18.3	0.002	
			-	-	-	-	-	91.7	5.53	0.1	
Apr. 2	Weather factors	Max. T.	0.4	0.6	0.3	0.3	0.8	20.15	0.42	0.7	
		Min. T.	0.3	0.5	0.5	0.2	0.9				
		RH.	-0.3	-0.2	0.4	-0.2	0.6				
	Plant age ¹ - age ³ Combined effect		-	-	-	-	-	84.97	9.42	0.02	
			-	-	-	-	-	96.6	9.36	0.1	
Apr. 16	Weather factors	Max. T.	-0.1	-0.3	0.8	1.6	0.4	49.58	2.62	0.1	
		Min. T.	-0.5	-1.9	0.1	-3.1	0.1				
		RH.	-0.4	-0.65	0.1	-0.4	0.4				
	Plant age ¹ - age ³ Combined effect		-	-	-	-	-	61.5	4.26	0.04	
			-	-	-	-	-	64.4	1.5	0.3	

Plant age in weeks (Presenting the continuous nutritional values over the growing season) was considered as third degree of polynomial ($Y = a \pm b_1 \text{Age} \pm b_2 \text{Age}^2 \pm b_3 \text{Age}^3$).

Table (3): Mean values of temperatures and relative humidity registered in the weeks of sampling of *Bemisia tabaci* eggs and nymphs on cantaloupe in the three sowing dates over the 2016 summer plantation season in Qaha, Qalyubiya Governorate.

Sampling date	Temp. (°C)		RH. (%)		Mean of <i>Bemisia tabaci</i> eggs/ leaf			Mean of <i>Bemisia tabaci</i> nymphs/ leaf		
	Max.	Min.	Mean		Mar.16	Apr.2	Apr.16	Mar. 16	Apr. 2	Apr. 16
Apr. 17	29.71	18.86	45		7.29	-	-	1.03	-	-
Apr. 24	35.14	19.71	43.14		10.3	3.14	-	3.82	0.52	-
May 1	33.3	19.43	42.14		13.99	19.25	-	10.11	1.29	-
8	31	19.71	44.57		13.10	11.125	0.84	14.29	3.35	0.42
15	36.71	23	35.43		8.35	17.125	6.05	18.45	16.52	3.67
22	33	20.86	44.71		2.8	10.84	14.2	17.2	38.58	12.29
29	30.14	19.71	44.3		1.20	10.18	5.79	18	37.9	16.5
Jun. 5	38.43	25	29.57		0.73	13.16	3.03	25.1	32.96	16.61
12	35.14	21.71	40.3		0.31	6.25	1.61	16.35	21.43	16.4
19	36	24.3	48.14		-	2.21	0.74	-	24.8	10.2
26	37.71	24.86	51.6		-	-	0.51	-	-	5.07
Jul. 3	34.6	24.14	59		-	-	0.0875	-	-	2.04
10	35	24.71	57		-	-	0.29	-	-	0.85
Mean	34.3	22	44.99		6.45	10.36	3.31	13.82	19.70	8.41

Table (4): Multiple regression of abiotic factors and plant age on *Bemisia tabaci* egg numbers on different sowing dates over 2016.

Sowing date	Factor	Level	Simple corr. and reg.			Multiple reg.				
			r	B	P	b	P	E.V.%	F	P
Mar. 16	Weather factors	Max. T.	-0.2	-0.4	0.6	1.02	0.4	53.04	1.88	0.25
		Min. T.	-0.5	-1.33	0.2	-5.3	0.1			
		RH.	0.3	0.3	0.4	-1.1	0.3			
Apr. 2	Plant age ¹ - age ³	Combined effect	-	-	-	-	-	95.6	35.95	0.0008
		Combined effect	-	-	-	-	-	99.9	326.6	0.003
	Weather factors	Max. T.	-0.056	-0.12	0.9	-1.1	0.45	47.1	1.5	0.3
		Min. T.	-0.1	-0.3	0.9	-0.4	0.8			
		RH.	-0.5	-0.5	0.2	-0.9	0.1			
	Plant age ¹ - age ³	Combined effect	-	-	-	-	-	57.9	2.3	0.2
Combined effect		-	-	-	-	-	82.72	1.6	0.4	
Apr. 16	Weather factors	Max. T.	-0.3	-0.4	0.4	0.6	0.8	29.5	0.84	0.5
		Min. T.	-0.5	-0.95	0.2	-1.5	0.55			
		RH.	-0.3	-0.2	0.3	-0.1	0.8			
Plant age ¹ - age ³	Combined effect	-	-	-	-	-	68.8	4.4	0.06	
	Combined effect	-	-	-	-	-	94.4	8.42	0.05	

Plant age in weeks (Presenting the continuous nutritional values over the growing season) was considered as third degree of polynomial ($Y = a \pm b_1 \text{Age} \pm b_2 \text{Age}^2 \pm b_3 \text{Age}^3$).

Table (S): Mean values of temperatures and relative humidity registered in the weeks of sampling of *Bemisia tabaci* eggs and nymphs on cantaloupe cultivars in the three sowing dates over 2017 summer plantation season in Qaha, Qalyubiya Governorate.

Sampling date	Temp. (°C)		RH. (%) Mean	Mean of <i>Bemisia tabaci</i> eggs/ leaf			Mean of <i>Bemisia tabaci</i> nymphs/ leaf		
	Max.	Min.		Mar. 16	Apr. 2	Apr. 16	Mar. 16	Apr. 2	Apr. 16
Apr. 16	26.3	16.6	55.86	5.78	-	-	0.73	-	-
23	31.43	18.43	36.7	39.72	6.06	-	2.83	0.23	-
30	28.43	17	44.1	11.77	15.88	-	9.68	1.2	-
May 7	28.71	17.33	45.57	28.74	15.81	1.31	13.51	2.56	1.32
15	36.1	21.4	37.4	16.14	11.08	9.03	17.83	13.3	2.96
22	32	20.86	45.86	6.16	9.22	2.73	21.69	33.49	6.07
28	32.5	21	42.2	2.75	8.18	9.39	20.06	26.43	9.06
Jun. 4	33.3	21.86	47.86	1.42	9.14	3.80	15.28	26.59	18.89
12	36	24.125	41.5	2.11	4.01	1.80	7.7	21.78	14.29
18	35.2	23.5	49.83	0.64	2.25	0.75	7.4	14.33	10.05
26	34.9	23.4	52.9	-	1.08	0.17	-	7.25	5.57
Jul. 3	38	25.6	50	-	-	0.11	-	-	2.09
Mean	32.74	20.9	45.8	11.52	8.27	3.23	11.67	14.71	7.81

Table (6): Multiple regression of abiotic factors and plant age on *Bemisia tabaci* egg numbers in different sowing dates over 2017.

Sowing date	Factor	Level	Simple corr. and reg.			Multiple reg.			P	
			R	B	P	B	P	E.V.%		F
Mar. 16	Weather factors	Max. T.	-0.3	-1.1	0.4	2.6	0.6	70.9	4.87	0.05
		Min. T.	-0.5	-2.6	0.1	-5.98	0.2			
		RH.	-0.5	-1.2	0.1	-1	0.3			
	Plant age ¹ - age ³			-	-	-	-	60.97	3.12	0.1
		Combined effect		-	-	-	-	77.3	1.7	0.355
Apr. 2	Weather factors	Max. T.	-0.7	-1.36	0.01	0.3	0.8	67.33	4.12	0.07
		Min. T.	-0.8	-1.6	0.004	-2.56	0.1			
		RH.	-0.3	-0.2	0.4	-0.053	0.8			
	Plant age ¹ - age ³			-	-	-	-	81.74	8.95	0.01
		Combined effect		-	-	-	-	98.02	6.48	0.1
Apr.16	Weather factors	Max. T.	-0.1	-0.1	0.8	0.4	0.8	60.81	2.59	0.2
		Min. T.	-0.3	-0.5	0.4	-0.5	0.7			
		RH.	-0.8	-0.6	0.01	-0.5	0.56			
	Plant age ¹ - age ³			-	-	-	-	61.4	2.65	0.2
		Combined effect		-	-	-	-	99.2	39.31	0.025

Plant age in weeks (Presenting the continuous nutritional values over the growing season) was considered as third degree of polynomial ($Y = a \pm b_1 \text{ Age} \pm b_2 \text{ Age}^2 \pm b_3 \text{ Age}^3$).

Table (7): Multiple regression of abiotic factors and plant age on *Bemisia tabaci* nymphal infestation in different sowing dates over 2015.

Sowing date	Factor	Level	Simple corr. & reg.			Multiple reg.				
			r	b	P	b	P	E.V.%	F	P
Mar. 16	Weather factors	Max. T.	0.7	1.5	0.03	-0.5	0.65	77.8	7.03	0.02
		Min. T.	0.9	2.6	0.001	3.3	0.06			
		RH.	0.002	0.003	0.99	0.1	0.7			
	Plant age ¹ - age ³	-	-	-	-	-	87.8	14.43	0.004	
Apr. 2	Weather factors	Max. T.	0.6	3.8	0.07	0.01	0.99	71.96	4.28	0.1
		Min. T.	0.83	5.65	0.005	5.6	0.1			
		RH.	0.2	0.5	0.6	0.36	0.65			
	Plant age ¹ - age ³	-	-	-	-	-	92.7	21.04	0.003	
Apr. 16	Weather factors	Max. T.	0.1	0.45	0.7	-0.35	0.85	55.1	3.27	0.1
		Min. T.	-0.2	-0.9	0.5	-0.6	0.7			
		RH.	-0.7	-1.2	0.01	-1.2	0.04			
	Plant age ¹ - age ³	-	-	-	-	-	95.1	51.8	0.0001	
Combined effect	-	-	-	-	-	96.6	23.4	0.002		

Plant age in weeks (Presenting the continuous nutritional values over the growing season) was considered as the third degree of polynomial ($Y = a \pm b_1 \text{Age} \pm b_2 \text{Age}^2 \pm b_3 \text{Age}^3$).

Table (8): Multiple regression of certain abiotic factors and plant age on *Bemisia tabaci* nymphal infestation over 2016 summer plantation season.

Sowing date	Factor	Level	Simple corr. & reg.			Multiple reg.			F	P
			r	B	P	b	P	E.V.%		
Mar. 16	Weather factors	Max. T.	0.5	1.26	0.2	-1.3	0.3	75.9	5.25	0.05
		Min. T.	0.8	2.95	0.01	6.7	0.046			
		RH.	-0.6	-0.9	0.1	0.82	0.4			
	Plant age ¹ - age ³	-	-	-	-	-	90.66	16.18	0.005	
	Combined effect		-	-	-	-	99.4	59.31	0.02	
Apr. 2	Weather factors	Max. T.	0.04	0.2	0.9	-6.2	0.1	51.03	1.74	0.3
		Min. T.	0.4	3.1	0.2	8.7	0.1			
		RH.	-0.1	-0.35	0.7	-0.6	0.6			
	Plant age ¹ - age ³	-	-	-	-	-	82.2	7.7	0.026	
	Combined effect		-	-	-	-	96.2	8.44	0.1	
Apr.16	Weather factors	Max. T.	0.01	0.02	0.9	-0.7	0.8	34.97	1.1	0.4
		Min. T.	-0.2	-0.6	0.6	0.6	0.9			
		RH.	-0.6	-0.4	0.1	-0.5	0.3			
	Plant age ¹ - age ³	-	-	-	-	-	91.6	21.83	0.001	
	Combined effect		-	-	-	-	98.4	30.38	0.01	

Plant age in weeks (Presenting the continues nutritional values over the growing season) was considered as third degree of polynomial ($Y = a \pm b_1 \text{Age} \pm b_2 \text{Age}^2 \pm b_3 \text{Age}^3$).

Table (9): Multiple regression of abiotic factors and plant age on *Bemisia tabaci* nymphal infestation over 2017 summer plantation season.

Sowing date	Factor	Level	Simple corr. and reg.			Multiple reg.				
			r	b	P	b	P	E.V.%		
Mar. 16	Weather factors	Max. T.	0.3	0.7	0.3	-0.5	0.9	14.37	0.34	0.8
		Min. T.	0.3	0.8	0.4	1.3	0.8			
		RH.	-0.3	-0.3	0.4	-0.4	0.7			
	Plant age ¹ - age ³		-	-	-	-	90.53	19.11	0.002	
	Combined effect		-	-	-	-	94.83	9.17	0.05	
Apr. 2	Weather factors	Max. T.	0.4	1.7	0.3	-7.2	0.2	49.1	1.93	0.2
		Min. T.	0.5	2.5	0.1	10.7	0.1			
		RH.	0.1	0.3	0.7	-1.4	0.2			
	Plant age ¹ - age ³		-	-	-	-	82.4	9.37	0.01	
	Combined effect		-	-	-	-	93.1	6.7	0.1	
Apr. 16	Weather factors	Max. T.	0.1	0.1	0.9	-4.1	0.2	37.8	1.01	0.46
		Min. T.	0.2	0.6	0.5	5.4	0.1			
		RH.	0.01	0.01	0.98	-0.7	0.3			
	Plant age ¹ - age ³		-	-	-	-	80.35	6.82	0.03	
	Combined effect		-	-	-	-	80.72	1.4	0.5	

Plant age in weeks (Presenting the continuous nutritional values over the growing season) was considered as the third degree of the polynomial ($Y = a \pm b_1 \text{ Age} \pm b_2 \text{ Age}^2 \pm b_3 \text{ Age}^3$).

References

- Abdel-Rahman, Y.; Abd-Ella, A.; Gaber, A. and Abou-Elhagag, G. (2018):** Impact of weather factors and certain insecticides on the population density of cotton whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* (Genn.)(Homoptera : Aleyrodidae). Journal of Phytopathology and Pest Management, 5(1): 35-48.
- Arif, M. J.; Gogi, M.D.; Mirza, M.; Zia, K. and Kafeez, F. (2006):** Impact of plant spacing and abiotic factors on population dynamics of sucking pests of cotton. Pakistan Journal of Biological Science, 9 (7) : 1364-1369.
- Chaudhuri, G.B.; Bharpoda, T.H.; Patel, J.J.; Patel, K.I. and Patel, J.R. (1999):** Effect of weather on activity of cotton bollworms in middle Gujarat. Journal of Agrometerology, 1: 137-142.
- Devi, S. and Ram, P. (2018):** Effect of dates of sowing on population of sucking insect pests in desi cotton (*Gossypium arboreum* L.). Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies, 6 (1): 1041-1044.
- Hanafy, A.R.I. (2007):** Effect of certain climatic factors and plant age on the level of infestation with cotton and onion thrips *Thrips tabaci* Lind. on sweetpea plants in different planting dates. Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research, 85(6): 2051-2063.
- Khan, M.M.H.; Kundu, R.; Alam, M.Z. and Karim, A. J.M.S. (1999):** Relative role of plant nitrogen content and trichome density of ashgourd, *Benincasa hispida* (Thunb) congin in determining the population of the melon aphid, *Aphis gossypii* Glover. Bulletin of the Institute of Tropical Agriculture, Kyushu University, 22:5-14.
- Leite, G.L.D.; Picanco, M.; Guedes, R.N.C. and Ecole, C.C.(2006):** Factors affecting the attack rate of *Bemisia tabaci* on cucumber. Pesquisa Agropecuária Brasileira, (8):1241-1245.
- SAS Institute (1988):** SAS / capital state user's guide, 6.03 ed. SAS Institute, Cary, N.C.
- Selvaraj, S. and Ramesh, V. (2012):** Seasonal abundance of whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* Gennadius and their relation to weather parameters in cotton. International Journal of Food, Agriculture and Veterinary Sciences, 2 (3) : 57-63.
- Smith, C.M.(2005):** Plant Resistance to Arthropods: Molecular and Conventional Approaches. Springer, Dordrecht, The Netherlands.
- Soni, R. and Dhakad, N.K. (2017):** Seasonal dynamics of whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) on transgenic Bt cotton and their correlation with abiotic factors. International Journal of Entomology Research, 2 (1): 24-26.

Egyptian Journal of Plant
Protection Research Institute

www.ejppri.eg.net

***Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) infestation and yield cantaloupe production in relation to inorganic fertilization**

Abd Allah, Y. N. M.¹; Metwally, S. A. G.¹; Refaei, B.M.²; Ibrahim, S.A.¹
and El Sawaf, B.M.²

¹Plant Protection Research Institute, Agriculture Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

²Entomology Department, Faculty of Science, Ain Shams University, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 4/1/2022

Accepted: 28/2/2022

Keywords

Inorganic fertilizers,
Bemisia tabaci,
Cucumis melo, and
management..

Abstract:

Plant nutrition has a great impact on the susceptibility of host plants to herbivores pests. Fertilization affects herbivores especially hemipteran insects to large extent. The physiological, physical, and mechanical defense traits in plants can be enhanced by fertilizers. Fertilization concerns the chemicals required by the organism for its growth, tissue maintenance, and reproduction, and are necessary to maintain these functions. Many organic and inorganic compounds affect plant health but two of them; nitrogen and potassium play an important role in plant growth and the plant-pest relationship. In this study, the two inorganic fertilizers; nitrogen and potassium were used at three units (40, 50, and 60 units/fed.) as soil treatments for cantaloupe (*Cucumis melo* L.) in summer plantation of two growing seasons. Nitrogen was applied in the form of ammonium sulphate (20.6% N₂) and potassium in the form of potassium sulphate (48% K₂O) on *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) nymphal infestation. Different nine rates of nitrogen and potassium in combination were applied. Application of a high level of N₂ mixed to the lowest level of K₂O (60 N₂+40 K₂O units) remarkably resulted in high infestation (15.5 nymphs/leaf) in the two seasons of study. The population decreased at levels of N₂ and K₂O as follows (40 N₂ + 40 K₂O, 40 N₂ + 50 K₂O, and 40 N₂ + 60 K₂O units) with nymphal infestation 3.95, 3.46, and 2.8 nymphs/leaf, respectively over the two studied seasons. Moreover, the application of a lower level of N₂ mixed with higher levels of K₂O led to a higher cantaloupe yield of 4.01 kg/plot (i.e., 3.97 m²). So, the best treatment that could be recommended to fertile the soil of cantaloupe plants is the rate containing low N₂ and high K₂O (40 N₂ + 60 K₂O units).

Introduction

Integrated pest management in agro horticultural ecosystems needs the priority use of some unconventional methods including adequate inorganic fertilization (El-Zahi *et al.*, 2012). Fertilization practices may also affect crop tolerance pests by affecting the

growth pattern, the anatomy and morphology, and particularly the chemical composition (Michaud and Charbonneau, 1993). Many species of plant feeding Hemiptera are considered serious agricultural and horticultural pests, whose feeding leads to wilting, distortion, or stunting of shoots. Apart

from feeding, some also transmit plant viruses and other diseases and their sugary excreta (Honeydew) leads to the formation of black sooty moulds, which spoil leaves and fruits and can impair photosynthesis (Singh and Sood, 2017). To govern and reduce the severity of damage of *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Hemiptera : Aleyrodidae) in the field, there is an enormous demand to use safe and alternative strategies to chemical control (Abd Allah *et al.*, 2018). Sucking insects show a much stronger response to crop fertilization (Butler *et al.*, 2012). Increasing the number of whitefly nymphs in melon fields seriously hampers weight and number of boxes harvested, reduces product and quality due to sooty mold fungus, and decreases fruit size and total soluble solids content (Riley and Palumbo, 1995).

Plants, which are supplied with all necessary nutrients in a balanced manner, are shown to be more resistant to insect pests. This lowers the need for particular pest control measures and also can be integrated with insect-pest management programs (Singh and Sood, 2017). Understanding the relationship between plant nutrition and pest reproductive potential is necessary for pest management in modern agro-ecosystems (Zarasvanda *et al.*, 2013).

The current investigation is aimed at studying the influence of different rates of nitrogen and potassium in combination on *B. tabaci* nymphal infestation on cantaloupe plants and the resultant yield in order to reach the best treatment with lower infestation and high yield.

Materials and methods

The experiments were carried out in the Experimental Farm of Plant Protection Research Institute in Qaha region, southwest of Qalyubiya Governorate in Egypt over two successive growing seasons; 2015 and 2017 in summer plantation. Each plot is

represented by 3.97m². Cantaloupe seeds (cv. Darvina) were sown directly in successive single rows on the southern edges. Rows are designed as 7 plants per row spaced 0.30 m² apart.

All the recommended practices for cantaloupe cultivation in Egypt were completely adopted without the application of chemical pest control measures during the whole period of study in summer (Starting in Mar. until Jul.). The natural infestation of whiteflies was evaluated in the experiments.

In order to evaluate the effect of nitrogen/potassium mixture (NK) on the infestation rates by *B. tabaci* nymphs, the nine ratios of nitrogen (Ammonium sulphate 20.6%N₂) and potassium (Potassium sulphate 48% K₂O) fertilizers were used as follow:

- Recommended rate 150 kg fed⁻¹ which is represented by 50 unit /fed.) (feddan= 4200 m²).
- Sub recommended rate 120 kg fed⁻¹ which is represented by 40 unit/fed.
- Over recommended rate 180 kg fed⁻¹ which is represented by 60 unit/fed.

In this trial seeds of cantaloupe were sown on Mar. 19th and Mar. 31st in 2015 and 2017, respectively. The experiment in 2016 was repeated 2017 because the cantaloupe plants in this experiment didn't grow in a good way in 2016.

1. Experimental design and cultivation method:

The different nine rates of nitrogen (N₂) were applied in the form of ammonium sulphate (20.6 %N₂) and potassium (K) which were added as potassium sulphate (48% K₂O) 40, 50, and 60 units/fed. Nitrogen and potassium were mixed together and applied to the soil cultivated with cantaloupe after complete germination and during the flowering and fruiting stages.

However, calcium superphosphate (15.5% P₂O₅) was

added at the recommended rate only in agricultural practices during the preparation of the experiment for agriculture. An area of about 350 m² was chosen to carry out the experiment. The nine rates of the mixture of inorganic fertilizers (40, 50, and 60 units/fed.) were replicated three times as well as the control (Check) which was without fertilization. The experiment design was a Complete Randomized Block (CBRD). When cantaloupe fruits grew and reached the time to be harvested, the yield was picked out and weighted for estimation of yield during 2015 only.

2. Data analysis:

All the obtained data during the trials over the two growing seasons were subjected to analysis by using SAS (SAS Institute, 1988) program. Duncan's multiple range test was used to obtain the mean separation and arrange fertilization rates according to their degree of infestation by *B. tabaci* eggs and nymphs at the level of 5 % of probability.

Results and discussion

In the current study ammonium sulphate (20.6% N₂) and potassium sulphate (48% K₂O) were tested on the nymphal infestation. The two fertilizers were used at three units (40, 50, and 60 units/fed.) as a soil treatment.

1. Effect of different inorganic fertilization rates on nymphal infestation:

The data graphically illustrated in Figure (1) reveals that the population density of *B. tabaci* nymphs/cantaloupe leaf was significantly affected by the different rates of inorganic fertilization and control throughout the two studied seasons (2015 and 2017). In 2015, the lowest infestation rate of *B. tabaci* nymphs was estimated in the control experiment (Free from any fertilizer treatment 1.75 nymphs/leaf). The highest density of nymphs (21.8 nymphs/leaf) was recorded in leaves

that received a high level of N₂ mixed with the lowest level of K₂O (60 N₂+40 K₂O units). By decreasing N₂ to 50 units mixed to the lowest level of K₂O (40 units) giving decreased infestation (12.8 nymphs /leaf), the highest level of N₂ mixed to moderate level of K₂O (60 + 50 units, respectively) resulted in infestation with *B. tabaci* nymphs as 12 nymphs /leaf. The highest rate (60 N₂+60 K₂O units) led to infestation with *B. tabaci* as 11.3 nymphs/leaf. On the other hand, the recommended rate contains moderate levels of two fertilizers (50 N₂ + 50 K₂O), and the rate which had a moderate level of N₂ mixed with the highest level of K₂O (50 N₂+60 K₂O) remarkably resulted in a moderate infestation of nymphs of 8.9 and 8.6 nymphs /leaf, respectively. On the other extreme, application lowest level of N₂ (40 units) mixed with 40, 50, and 60 units of K₂O led to lower infestation means of nymphs as 4.99, 4.4, and 3.8 nymphs/leaf, respectively.

In 2017, the data illustrated in Figure (2) showed that increasing in infestation rates with *B. tabaci* nymphs (9.2 nymphs/leaf) was recorded by increasing the levels of N₂ and decreasing K₂O (60 N₂ + 40 K₂O units) followed by a moderate level of N₂ and the lowest level of K₂O (50 N₂ + 40 K₂O units) as the population density was 5.5 nymphs /leaf and (60 N₂ + 50 K₂O units) with infestation rate of 5.2 nymphs /leaf. The moderate infestation rate was recorded by applying 50 N₂ + 50 K₂O and 60 N₂ + 60 K₂O units which led to infestation rates of 4.01 and 3.69 nymphs/leaf, respectively. On the other hand, decreasing N₂ to the lowest level and increasing K₂O gradually led to decreasing nymphs' infestation as K₂O increased i.e. 40 N₂ + 40 K₂O, 40 N₂ + 50 K₂O, and 40 N₂ + 60 K₂O decreased the infestation to 2.9, 2.5 and 1.8 nymphs/leaf, respectively, which didn't differ significantly from the control

which had infestation rate as 1.75 nymphs/leaf.

As for the calculated means of the 2015 and 2017 cantaloupe seasons altogether, the results were in harmony with the trend as that obtained in each of the two seasons, as the plants harbored the highest infestation received the NK containing the highest level of N₂ (60 units). The highest infestation rate in cantaloupe was recorded (15.5 nymphs/leaf) at the highest level of N₂ mixed to the lowest level of K₂O (60 N₂ +40 K₂O). The opposite extreme was observed in the soil kept free from any fertilizers in the control which led to the lowest mean population density in the two years as 1.5 nymphs/leaf. Higher rates of *B. tabaci* nymphs were also detected when the highest levels of N₂ mixed with the lowest level of K₂O and the highest level of N₂ mixed with a moderate level of K₂O and the highest levels of N₂ mixed with K₂O (50 N₂ + 40 K₂O, 60 N₂ + 50 K₂O and 60 N₂+ 60 K₂O units) as 9.15, 8.6 and 7.6 nymphs/leaf, respectively. Moreover, the fertilization rates of moderate levels of N₂ mixed with moderate and highest levels of K₂O (50 N₂ + 50 K₂O and 50 N₂ + 60 K₂O units) resulted in infestation rates of 6.3 and 5.9 nymphs/leaf, respectively (Figure 2).

The lower infestation rates with *B. tabaci* nymphs which didn't significantly differ from the check or control at LSD= 3.84 in leaves received the lowest levels of N₂ and the population decreased as K₂O increased as follows (40 N₂ + 40 K₂O, 40 N₂ + 50 K₂O and 40 N₂ + 60 K₂O units) with the infestation of nymph counts as 3.95, 3.46 and 2.8 nymphs/leaf, respectively.

From the above mentioned results, it can be concluded that the highest levels of N₂ led to the higher infestation rates with nymphs of *B. tabaci* (Linear relationship, Figure 1). So, the best treatment that could be recommended to fertile the soil of cantaloupe plants was the rate containing low N₂ and high K₂O (40 N₂ + 60 K₂O units).

2. Effect of the combination of inorganic fertilizer rates on cantaloupe yield:

The obtained results in Figure (3) revealed that applying the combination of inorganic fertilizers NK led in most instances to an increase in the cantaloupe yield. Generally, the application of N₂ at a high level (60 units) mixed with moderate (50 units) 60 N₂ + 50 K₂O or highest (60 units) 60 N₂ + 60 K₂O led to the highest weight of cantaloupe 4.16 and 4.05 Kg/plot (This means by application this rate to fertile cantaloupe soil, cantaloupe may give about 4.4 and 4.3 tons/fed., respectively). Application of 40 N₂ + 60 K₂O and intermediate rate 50 N₂ + 40 K₂O yielded cantaloupe being 4.01 and 3.9 Kg/plot [LSD= 1.24]. While, fertilizers applied at the rate of 40 N₂ +40 K₂O and fertilizers as 50 N₂ +50 K₂O and 50 N₂+ 60 K₂O yielded moderate cantaloupe weight yield as 2.82, 2.87, 3.04 Kg/plot. These weights didn't differ significantly from the control (2.74 Kg/plot). On the contrary, the lower mean of weight 2.16 kg/plot resulted from applying 60 N₂ + 40 K₂O but it didn't significantly differ from the lowest weight in this season (1.99 kg/plot) which resulted from applying 40 N₂ + 50 K₂O.

Figure (1): *Bemisia tabaci* infestation in relation to nine rates of NK in combination (40, 50, and 60 units).

Figure (2): Mean population of *Bemisia tabaci* nymphs/leaf on cantaloupe under nine rates of NK fertilizer combinations and control over 2015 and 2017 summer plantations and an average of the two years. Bars topped with different letters are significantly different by Duncan’s multiple range test ($P < 0.05$).

Figure (3): Mean counts of *Bemisia tabaci* nymphs/leaf of cantaloupe plants which received different rates of NK fertilizers in combination over 2015 and 2017 summer plantations. Bars topped with different letters are significantly different by Duncan’s test ($P < 0.05$).

Plant pest defense mechanisms such as biochemical, physical, and mechanical properties can be enhanced by balanced fertilization with plant nutrients. Nitrogen and potassium affect plant health (Singh and Sood, 2017). Sucking insects have a much stronger response to crop fertilization (Balakrishnan *et al.*, 2007). The relationship between plant nutrition and

pest reproductive potential is important for pest management in modern agroecosystems (Zarasvanda *et al.*, 2013). Fluctuation in the nitrate (NO_3) led to increased susceptibility of plants to insects as its excessive use decreases lignin concentration, which is a substance used by plants as a physical defense against various pests (Torres-Olivar *et al.*, 2014).

In the present investigation of inorganic fertilizers, N and K in combination in the soil the populations of *B. tabaci* were largely affected. In general, the highest infestation rate of *B. tabaci* population was recorded in treatments with high nitrogen and lower potassium content. The highest infestation in leaves was recorded in case of high N₂ and low K₂O (60 N₂+40 K₂O units) followed by (50 N₂+40 K₂O units). However, the moderate fertilization rate (50 N₂+50 K₂O) led to moderate infestation. Application of a lower level of N₂ (40 units) mixed with either 40, 50, or 60 units of K₂O led to a lower infestation of nymphs. The treatments with high potassium and low nitrogen level lowered the infestation. The current investigation revealed that higher levels of nitrogen led to a higher infestation rate of *B. tabaci*. This result was obtained by many investigators Bi *et al.* (2001), Zurina *et al.* (2010), Draz *et al.* (2013) and Islam *et al.* (2017) recorded that increasing amount of nitrogen led to the increasing population of whitefly. However, an adequate supply of nitrogen is associated with high photosynthetic activity, vigorous vegetative growth, and the dark green color of the leaves (Zafar *et al.*, 2010). Application of nitrogenous fertilizer can alter the nutritional levels in the plant tissues and reduce plant resistance against herbivores, consequently feeding preference of herbivore, food consumption, survival, growth, reproduction, and population density will increase (Cipollini *et al.*, 2002; Prudic *et al.*, 2005; Ortega-Arenas *et al.*, 2006 and Zhong-xian *et al.*, 2007). Excessive use of nitrate (NO₃⁻) can increase the susceptibility of plants to insect pests by decreasing lignin concentration, which is a substance used by plants as a physical defense against various pests (Torres - Olivar *et al.*, 2014).

Moreover, an excessive N supply with unbalanced fertilization requires carbon (C) to metabolize it and these leaves have little C from the Krebs's cycle for the synthesis of secondary compounds, such as phenols and quinones. Also, phenolic compounds play an important role in the host/pest relationship, being the basis for many defense mechanisms. They act as phytoalexins or as precursors of lignin and suberin, which act as mechanical barriers in leaves and stems against insect-pest attacks (Imas, 2013). Potassium plays an important physiological role building up resistance to insect pests. Adequate amounts of K have been reported to decrease the incidence of insect damage. Plants excessively supplied with N and little K have soft tissue with little resistance to sucking and chewing insects. The yellowish discoloration of plants suffering from K deficiency acts as a signal to attract aphids (Liu *et al.*, 2013).

The high levels of potassium can enhance secondary compound metabolism, reduce carbohydrate accumulation, eliminate some amino acids, and increase the silica content of leaves and plant damage from insect-pests (Krauss, 2001 and Facknath and Lalljee, 2005). Biswas *et al.* (2009) recorded the highest number of *B. tabaci*, per leaf at a higher dose of nitrogen and found a positive correlation between whitefly abundance level and nitrogen dose. Ahmed *et al.* (2007) found highest N rate resulted in the highest mean population of *B. tabaci* being 0.44; 1.49, 1.43, and 1.62 per leaf at 50, 100, 150, and 200 kg N/ha, respectively.

Concerning the yield, it was noticed that the application of a low rate of nitrogen in combination with a high rate of potassium (40 N₂ + 60 K₂O units), moderate rate of nitrogen in combination with the lowest rate of

potassium (50 N₂ + 40 K₂O units) and the highest rate of nitrogen in combination with a moderate rate of potassium or highest rate of potassium (60 N₂ + 50 or 60 K₂O units, respectively) led to the high weight of cantaloupe. This means that the high infestation of nymphs resulting from high nitrogen levels didn't affect the cantaloupe weight. Our results were in harmony with El-Rafie (1999) evaluated three major phytonutrients (N, P, and K) in the infestation of tomatoes with *B. tabaci* in Egypt, his results revealed that plants treated with high levels of N resulted in an increased number of *B. tabaci* and decreased yields. These results didn't be the same as those obtained by Feltrin *et al.* (2002) they evaluated the infestation of *B. tabaci* on tomato plants fertilized with different sources of potassium KCl + K₂SO₄ + K₂SiO₃; KCl + K₂SO₄; K₂SO₄ + KCl. These different sources of potassium neither affect the *B. tabaci* infestation, nor the fruit yield and quality of the tomato fruits.

Agricultural practices like excessive and massive use of fertilizers can result in nutrient imbalance and finally into the increased attack of insects. Our findings concluded that application of the lowest rate of nitrogen (40) mixed with the highest rate of potassium (60) to cantaloupe soils could be successfully recommended in IPM program as lower infestation with high yield fruits.

References

- Abd Allah , Y. N.M. ; Metwally, S. A.G. ; Refaai, B. M. and El Sawaf, B. M. (2018):** Reducing infestations of *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) in cantaloupe using intercropping with non-host aromatic plants . Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst. , 1(1): 58-68.
- Ahmed, S.; Habibullah, S. S. and Ali, C.M. (2007):** Effect of different doses of nitrogen fertilizer on sucking insect pests of cotton, *Gossypium hirsutum*. Journal of Agriculture Research, 45(1): 43-48.
- Balakrishnan, N.; Baskaran, R.K.M. and Mahadevan, N.R. (2007):** Impact of manures and fertilizers on sucking pests of cotton. Annals of Plant Protection Sciences, 15(1): 235-281.
- Bi, J.L.; Ballmer, G.R.; Hendrix, D.L.; Henneberry, T.J. and Toscano, N.C. (2001):** Effect of cotton nitrogen fertilization on *Bemisia argentifolii* populations and honeydew production. Entomologia Experimentalis et Applicata, 99:25-36.
- Biswas, S.; Mahato, B.; Panda, P. and Guha, S. (2009):** Effect of different doses of nitrogen on insect pest attack and yield potentiality of Okra, *Abelmoschus esculentus*(L.) Moench at terai ecology of West Bengal. Journal of Entomological Research, 33(3): 219-222.
- Butler, J. L. ; Garratt, M. P. D. and Leather, S. R. (2021):** Fertilizers and insect herbivores: A meta-analysis. Annals of Applied Biology, 161(3):223-233.
- Cipollini, M.L.; Paulk, E. and Cipollini, D.F. (2002):** Effect of nitrogen and water treatment on leaf chemistry in horsenettle (*Solanum carolinense*), and relationship to herbivory by flea beetles (*Epitrix* spp.) and tobacco hornworm (*Manduca sexta*). Journal of Chemical Ecology, 28(12): 2377-2398.
- Draz, K. A. A. ; Darwish, A. A. E. and Tabikha, R. M. M. (2013):** Effect of different rates of

- nitrogen fertilizer on infestation level with piercing sucking insect pests of tomato crop, *Lycopersicon esculentum* L. Journal of Agricultural and environmental sciences Egypt, 12 (3): 20-31.
- El-Rafie, K.K. (1999):** Effect of different rates of (N, P, K) fertilizers on *Bemisia tabaci* (Genn.) infestation on tomato and its effect on the yield. Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research, 77(3): 1067-1073.
- El-Zahi, E.S.; Arif, S.A.; El-Naggar, J.B.A. and El-Dewy, M. E.H. (2012):** Inorganic Fertilization of Cotton Field-Plants In Relation To Sucking Insects and Yield Production Components of Cotton Plants. Journal of American Science, 8 (2): 509-517.
- Facknath, S. and Lalljee, B. (2005):** Effect of soil-applied complex fertiliser on an insect – host plant relationship: *Liriomyza trifolii* on *Solanum tuberosum*. Entomologia Experimentalis et Applicata, 115: 67–77.
- Feltrin, D.M.; Lourençao, A.L.; Furlani, P.R. and Carvalho, C.R.L. (2002):** Effect of potassium sources in *Bemisia tabaci* b biotype (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) infestation and in tomato fruits characteristics in protected cultivation. Bragantia, 61(1): 49-57.
- Islam, M.N.; Hasanuzzaman, A.T.; Zhang, Z.F.; Zhang, Y. and Liu, T.X. (2017):** High levels of nitrogen makes tomato plants releasing less volatiles and attracting more *B. tabaci*. Frontiers in Plant Science, 8 : 466.
- Krauss, A. (2001):** Potassium and biotic stress. In: The 1st Fauba Fertilizer. IPI. Workshop on potassium in Argentina's agricultural system, Buenos Aires, Argentina.
- Liu, J.L.; Zhang, H.M.; Chen, X.; Yang, X. and Wu, J.C. (2013):** Effects of rice potassium level on the fecundity and expression of the vitellogenin gene of *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stal) (Hemiptera: Delphacidae). Journal of Asia-Pacific Entomology, 16: 411–414.
- Michaud, M. H. and Charbonneau, F. (1993):** Plant nutrient composition as a component of crop protection. Acta Hortic., 339:85-98.
- Ortega-Arenas, L.D.; Miranda-Agagon, D.A. and Sandoval-Villa, M. (2006):** Whitefly *Trialeurodes vaporariorum* (West.) eggs and nymphs density on *Gerbera jamesonii* H. Bolus under different nitrogenous fertilizer regimes. Agrociencia, 40: 363–371.
- Prudic, K.L.; Oliver, J.C. and Bowers, M.D. (2005):** Soil nutrient effects on oviposition preference, larval performance, and chemical defense of a specialist insect herbivore. Oecologia, 143: 578–587.
- Riley, D.G. and Palumbo, J.C. (1995):** Interaction of silverleaf whitefly (Homoptera: Aleyrodidae) with cantaloupe yield. Journal of Economic Entomology, 88: 1726-1732.
- SAS Institute (1988):** SAS / capital state user's guide, 6.03 ed. SAS Institute, Cary, N.C.
- Singh, V. and Sood, A.K. (2017):** Plant Nutrition: A tool for the management of hemipteran insect-pests-A review. Agricultural Reviews, 38(4) : 260-270.

- Torres-Olivar, V.; Villegas-Torres, O.G.; Domínguez-Patino, M.L.; Sotelo-Nava, H.; Rodríguez-Martínez, A.; Melgoza-Alemán, R.M.; Valdez-Aguilar, L.A. and Alia-Tejagal, I. (2014):** Role of nitrogen and nutrients in crop nutrition. *Journal of Agricultural Science and Technology*, 4: 29-37.
- Zafar, U.Z.; Athar, H.U.R. and Ashraf, M. (2010):** Responses of two cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.) cultivars differing in resistance to leaf curl virus disease to nitrogen nutrition. *Pakistan Journal of Botany*, 42(3): 2085-2094.
- Zarasvanda, A.A.; Allahyarib, H. and Fattah-Hosseini, S. (2013):** Effect of nitrogen fertilization on biology, life table parameters and population abundance of greenbug; *Schizaphis graminum* (Rondani) (Hemiptera : Aphididae). *Archives of Phytopathology and Plant Protection*, 46(8): 882–889.
- Zhong-xian, L. ; Xiao-ping, Y. ; Heong, K. and Cui, H. (2007):** Effect of Nitrogen Fertilizer on Herbivores and Its Stimulation to Major Insect Pests in Rice. *Rice Science*, 14(1): 56-66.
- Zurina, M.; Mohamad Roff, M. N. and Idris, A. B. (2010):** Effect of nitrogen rates on the whitefly (*Bemisia tabaci*) population infesting Chilli (*Capsicum annum* L.). *Sains Malaysiana*, 39(6): 913-920.

Ecological aspects on California red scale *Aonidiella aurantii* (Hemiptera: Diaspididae) on mandarin trees in Sohag Governorate, Egypt

Salman, A.M.A.¹; Attia, S.A.²; Foad, H.A.¹ and Assakar, H.H.I.³

¹Faculty of Agriculture, Sohag University.

²Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

³Graduate Student.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 9/1/2022

Accepted: 15/3/2022

Keywords

California red scale, *Aonidiella aurantii*, mandarin trees, weather factors, seasonal abundance and Egypt.

Abstract:

Citrus is one of the most important fruit crops in Egypt. Its trees are attacked by many pests, especially scale insects. *Aonidiella aurantii* (Maskell) (Hemiptera: Diaspididae) is one of the dangerous pests that infest citrus trees in Egypt, especially in Upper Egypt. It was noted that mandarin trees were severely infested with this pest in the Shandawil Horticulture Research Station, Sohag Governorate during two successive consecutive seasons (2019-2020). Studying the population density of this pest revealed that, it had four activity periods simultaneously with the abundance of nymphal stage and recorded in nymphal stage, which had four peaks of activity per a year of study during as following, the period recorded on 8th March (End winter) with (114 nymphs/30 leaves), the second peak was recorded on 8th Jun (Spring peak) with (186 nymphs/30 leaves), the third peak, which recorded on 8th Sep. with (213 nymphs/ 30 leaves), finally the fourth peak that recorded on 8th Dec. (Early winter) with (179 nymphs/30 leaves) during 2019. Also recorded on 8th Mar., 8th Jun., 23rd Sep. and 8th Dec. with a population of (148, 242, 264 and 223 nymph/30 leaves) during 2020. As a result of these activity periods three overlapping generations/year. There was a positive significant relationship between abiotic factors and the nymphal stage and the total population of *A. aurantia*, while relative humidity relations were negative and insignificant in both years of study.

Introduction

Citrus is one of the first fruit crops with a high export value. Also, come second only to grapes in planting, production of fruit trees worldwide (Spiegel-Roy and Goldschmidt, 1996). The different varieties of orange are infested by different species of insects, among them the armored scale insects (Jacas- Miret and Garcia-Mari, 2001; Garcia- Mari, 2006 and Jendoubi *et al.*, 2008). The California red scale *Aonidiella aurantii* (Maskell)

(Hemiptera: Diaspididae) is considered a key pest of citrus that has spread during the last decades up to cover a vast extension of agricultural landscapes (Balboul and Helmy, 2019). It is one of the most important pests infesting citrus trees in different parts of the world (Abd-Rabou, 2009). The California red scale *A. aurantii* is considered one of the serious pests among them (Selim, 2014). This pest inserts its mouthparts deep into plant tissue and sucks sap from parenchyma

cells, where the prolonged infestation may cause leaf drop and defoliation and dieback of twigs and eventually large branches, also maturing fruit can become completely encrusted with scales; developing scales form prominent pits on young fruit which are still evident when the fruit matures. Such fruit tends to dry out and fall off. Even the trunk can become heavily infested (Bedford, 1998).

The seasonal abundance of the California red scale on Balady orange gave four peaks of abundance recorded, in February, June, September, and November (Selim, 2014). *A. aurantii* has three generations in spring, summer and autumn per year on lemon orchards in Adana, and Mersin provinces during 2004-2005 (Yarpuzlu *et al.*, 2008). *A. aurantii* had three overlapping generations under the field conditions during the two years on citrus trees and the effect of the maximum and minimum temperature on the total population during two years of study were positive significant correlation during the two years of study the same side the combined effect of climatic factors on California red scale *A. aurantii* during the two years of study was significant and the explained variance (E.V.) presented (68% and 57.7%) during the two years of study (Balboul and Helmy, 2019). The simple correlation between (Maximum and minimum temperature) and the *A. aurantii* total population were positive significant during the two years of study and the explained variance of all variables recorded (74 and 73 %) in Qena Governorate (Haris, 2015).

The present work is to study the population dynamics of the California red scale, *A. aurantii* infesting mandarin trees in Sohag Governorate for two successive consecutive seasons (2019-2020).

Materials and methods

1. Seasonal abundance of *Aonidiella aurantii*:

Recording abundance of *A. aurantii* on mandarin trees was carried out in the Shandawil Horticulture Research Station, Sohag area, Sohag Governorate during two successive consecutive seasons (2019-2020). The selected orchard does not receive any chemical control during both studied seasons and two years prior to the experiment. All trees received the same horticultural practices during the studied period. Samples of infested mandarin trees leaves were taken biweekly throughout the studying period (2019-2020). Samples of 30 leaves for each direction of mandarin orchard and 30 leaves were taken from the center, (150 leaves in total). Samples were kept in polyethylene bags with minute holes and transferred directly to the laboratory for examination. Samples were examined visually or with the aid of stereoscopic binoculars. All alive found on each surface were assorted and recorded as preadult (Nymphs), adult females, and adult gravid females. Scale insect was identified by the specialists of the Department of Scale insects and Mealybugs, Plant Protection Research Institute, Giza, Egypt.

2. Age structure calculation:

To calculate the age structure per sample, the mean number of each stage was divided by the total and multiplied by 100. This method gave a percent proportion of the total per sample regardless of the total number of presenting insects (i.e., Population density). The number and duration of generation were determined using the obtained data throughout the two successive years using the age-structure technique per sample over the year.

Generation was defined, as the time required for an insect to complete its life cycle (i.e., egg to egg). In the case of Diaspididae, eggs were

ovipositing under the female until they hatch and crawl out. Gravid females were defined as females with eggs. The presence of gravid females was considered in this study as the presence of the egg stage. This phenomenon was used to determine the end of each generation and the beginning of the next one (El-Amir, 2009).

3. Meteorological factors:

Weather factors data assumed to affect studied insects (i.e., maximum and minimum daily temperatures and mean percentage of daily relative humidity) were obtained for the Sohag area from the Egypt-Weather Underground

<https://www.wunderground.com/global/EG.html>. Obtained data was summarized for each fourteen days previous to the sampling date. Considered weather factors means over each determined generation was calculated and presented.

Results and discussion

1. Seasonal fluctuations of *Aonidiella aurantii* on mandarin trees during 2019-2020 at Sohag Governorate:

The red scale insect *A. aurantii* is one of the most damaging armored scales that infest citrus crops in Sohag Governorate. This study was carried out at the Shandaweel horticulture research station in Sohag Governorate, for two successive years starting from 8/1/2019 to 23/12/ 2020.

Data illustrated in Figures (1 and 2) illustrated the seasonal fluctuations of *A. aurantii* on mandarin leaves expressed as a live number of (Nymphs, adult female, and gravid female) and total population. Also, the abiotic or weather factors (Max. temp., min. temp. and relative humidity) were present in the same figures during the two years of study (2019-2020).

1.1. Nymphal stage:

Data illustrated in Figures (1 and 2) showed that the nymphal stage population had four peaks of activity per a year of study during the first year the first peak was the lowest peak due to slightly low temperature (End winter) and recorded on 8th March with (114 nymphs/30 leaves), the second peak was recorded on 8th Jun (Spring peak) with (186 nymphs/30 leaves) where the population increased as a result to temperature increase, the third peak which recorded on 8th September was the highest one due to the more favorable abiotic factors (Temperature and relative humidity) its population recorded (213 nymphs/ 30 leaves), finally the fourth peak that recorded on 8th December (Early winter) with (179 nymphs/30 leaves) its population somewhat decreased as a result of temperature decreasing.

Also, during the second year of study the nymphal stage population had four peaks of activity the first one recorded on 8th March which was a low peak activity with a population of (148 nymph/30 leaves), the second peak of activity recorded on 8th Jun and increased with the rising temperatures with (242 nymph/30 leaves), the third peak recorded on 23th Sep. and was the highest peak of activity due to the more favorable conditions where its population reached (264 nymph/30 leaves), finally the last peak of activity recorded on 8th Dec. and started to decreased again due to the noticeable drop in temperatures with a population of (223 nymph/30 leaves).

On the other hand, it is worth noting that nymphal stage number of the studying pest was present throughout the two years of study, but it decreased to some extent in winter season as a result of bad weather conditions

Figure (1): Seasonal fluctuation of *Aonidilla aurantii* different stages and total population during 2019.

Figure (2): Seasonal fluctuation of *Aonidiella aurantii* different stages and total population during 2020.

1.2. Adult female stage:

Data recorded in the same figures showed that adult female population curve had four peaks per a year of study. During the first year the recorded on 8th Feb., 23th May, 23rd Aug. and 23rd Nov. with (34, 35, 35, and 41 adult females/30 leaves). Also, the adult female curve of the second year had four peaks recorded nearly in the same time of the first year as follows 23th Feb., 23th May, 23rd Aug. and 23rd Nov. where its population was higher than the first year as follows (47, 46, 46, and 53 adult females/30 leaves), respectively. On the other side the adult female curve recorded their lowest bottom in summer season where it reached (15 adult females/30 leaves) during the tow studying years.

1.3. Adult female with nymph stage:

Data present in the same figures showed that (Adult females+ nymphs)

stage population curve had four peaks per a year of study recorded on 23rd Feb., 23rd May, 23rd and 23rd Nov. with (54, 51, 51 and 63 adult females+ nymphs), respectively for the first year of study. The same trend was recorded for the second year of study, four peaks recorded on 23rd Jan., 23rd May, 8th Sep. and 23rd Nov. with a population higher than the first year as follows (70, 66, 77, and 82 adult females+ nymphs), respectively. On the otherwise the low population of (Adult females+ nymphs) stage recorded through the first year of study in early spring and in late summer season for the second year of study.

1.4. Total population:

Total population curve of *A. aurantii* had four peaks during the first year of study recorded in 23rd Feb., 23rd May, 8th Sep. and 8th Dec. with 185, 251, 297 and 270 individual/30 leaves, respectively. On the same side during

the second year of study the total population curve had four peaks exhibited at 23rd Feb., 23rd May, 8th Sep. and 8th Dec. with 241, 326, 386, and 351 individuals/30 leaves, respectively. The insect pest was present in abundant numbers throughout the two years of study, but the population decreased somewhat in the winter specifically in January.

These results were agreement with that obtained by Moustafa (2012) reported that the population of red scale *A. aurantii* has two peaks in April and October. Haris (2015) in Qena, Egypt, who reported that the population had four peaks per a year of study recorded on spring, summer, autumn and winter seasons, respectively. The highest peaks were obtained in early Aug. (Summer) and mid Oct. (Autumn) with 3102 and 3327 individuals/30 leaves, respectively.

2. Duration and number of annual generations:

The result of applying the age structure technique to the seasonal abundance data of *A. aurantii* obtained from Sohag Governorate over the two years on mandarin trees are graphically illustrated on Figures (3) and (4). Obtained trend over two studied years indicated the occurrence of four generations per year for *A. aurantii* on mandarin at Sohag location (Table 1).

2.1. First year annual generation:

Over the first year the overwintering generation continued (Mainly

as adult females and adult females + nymphs) up to the end of January. The first generation (Winter/spring generation) started on 23rd Jan. until 8th Apr. (2.5 months), 2019 (Marked by maximum population of adult females and adult females + nymphs in much synchronized fashion). The date 8th Apr., 2019 was considered as the terminal for the first generation.

The second generation (Spring generation) started thereafter and continued until re-emergence of the gravid females on 23rd Jul., therefore its duration was 3.5 months (8th Apr. till 23rd Jul.). The third generation (Summer/autumn) which started from 23rd Jul. till 23rd Oct. with duration of 3 months and characterized by the high density of nymphs as a result of high temperature which accelerate appearance of crawlers. The fourth generation (Autumn/winter generation) which started on 23rd Oct. and it was terminated in the beginning of the second year (Next Jan.) and characterized by the high density of adult females and gravid females which overwintered as it was.

2.2. Second year annual generation:

Over the second year of study similar results were obtained with little delay. The relevant dates were 23rd Jan., 8th Apr., 8th Jul. and 8th Oct. 2020 where their durations were 2.5, 3 and 3 months, respectively. The fourth generation continued to the next year.

Figure (3): Age structure of *Aonidiella aurantii* different stages during 2019.

Figure (4): Age structure of *Aonidiella aurantii* different stages during 2020.

Table (1): Number and durations of the annual generations of *Aonidiella aurantii* on mandarin trees at Sohag Governorate (2019-2020).

Generations	Data from---- to	Duration in months
First year		
1 st Generation	23/1 to 8/4	2.5
2 nd Generation	8/4 to 23/7	3.5
3 rd Generation	23/7 to 23/10	3
4 th Generation	23/10 to the beginning of the following year	4
Second year		
1 st Generation	23/1 to 8/4	2.5
2 nd Generation	8/4 to 8/7	3
3 rd Generation	8/7 to 8/10	3
4 th Generation	8/10 to the beginning of the following year	4.5

El-Saadany *et al.* (1994) recorded that *A. aurantii* had four generation per a year of study on citrus. The 1st generation was observed at beginning of April till mid-July. The 2nd generation at mid of July till mid-October, while 3rd generation at the end of October till the early December. However, the 4th generation was shown at the mid February till mid-May. The red scale insect *A. aurantii* develops

three generations per year on two host plants: (1st) in summer (2nd) in spring and the (3rd) in autumn. This behavior can be explained by farther study on the influence of trophic factors (Belguendouz *et al.*, 2013). Haris (2015) in Qena revealed that *A. aurantii* exhibited four generation on mandarin. The 1st generation was from early-March to end June, lasted 3 months. The 2nd generation was from early-June

to mid-September and lasted 3 months. The 3rd generation was from mid-September to early-November and lasted 2 months. The 4th or last generation started from early-November to early-January and lasted 2 months.

3. Statistical analysis of the effect of abiotic factors on *Aonidiella aurantii* population on mandarin tree at Sohag 2019-2020:

Data in Tables (2 and 3) clearly showed the simple correlation and partial regression between *A. aurantii* (Different stages and total population) and abiotic factors were studied during two studied years (2019 and 2020) at Sohag Governorate.

3.1. Effect of daily maximum temperature:

During the two years of study as shown in Tables (2 and 3) max. temperature gave positive significant simple correlation with nymphal stage

and total population (0.7558 and 0.6790), respectively throughout 2019 and (0.75718 and 0.64986), respectively during 2020. Simple regression. Also, simple regression was positive significant for nymph stage and total population during the two years of study as following, (4.63857 and 4.59183) and (6.09928 and 5.80658), respectively. Whereas, the simple correlation was negative insignificant with adult female stage and positive insignificant with gravid female stage (-0.18572 and 0.08056), respectively throughout 2019 and (-0.23845 and 0.00888), respectively during 2020. Simple regression was the same in case of the two stages adult female and gravid female whereas recording (-0.17279 and 0.12605), respectively throughout the first year and (-0.29845 and 0.018190), respectively during the second year.

Table (2): Statistical analysis of the effect of abiotic factors on *Aonidiella aurantii* population on mandarin tree at Sohag 2019.

Tested factors		Simple correlation and partial regression	Nymph	Adult female	Adult+Nymph female	Total pop.
Abiotic factors	Max	R	0.7558	-0.18572	0.08056	0.67900
		P	<.0001	0.3849	0.7083	0.0003
		B	4.63857	-0.17279	0.12605	4.59183
	Mini	R	0.74166	-0.21713	0.04646	0.65395
		P	<.0001	0.3081	0.8293	0.0005
		B	4.25684	-0.18893	0.06799	4.13590
	RH	R	-0.44381	0.22808	0.11364	-0.34509
		P	0.0298	0.2838	0.5970	0.0986
		B	-2.03081	0.15821	0.13258	-1.74002
Analysis of variance	Abiotic factors	F*=10.26		E.V.%= 60.61		

Table (3): Statistical analysis of the effect of abiotic factors *Aonidiella aurantii* population on mandarin tree at Sohag 2020.

Tested factors		Simple correlation & partial regression	Nymph	Adult female	Adult+Nymph female	Total pop.
Abiotic factors	Max.	R	0.75718	-0.23845	0.00888	0.64986
		P	<.0001	0.2618	0.9671	0.0006
		B	6.09928	-0.29845	0.01890	5.80658
	Mini.	R	0.72671	-0.30375	-0.08151	0.59177
		P	<.0001	0.1490	0.7050	0.0023
		B	5.40103	-0.35077	-0.16007	4.87854
	RH.	R	0.0171	0.0360	0.1222	-0.29593
		P	-0.48186	0.42997	0.32424	0.1603
		b	-1.94790	0.27007	0.34634	-1.32700
Analysis of variance	Abiotic factors		F= 9.33		E.V.%= 58.32	

3.2. Effect of daily minimum temperature:

Also, the data in the same tables showed that, simple correlation was positive and significant with nymphal stage and total population (0.74166 and 0.65395), respectively throughout 2019 and (0.72671 and 0.59177), respectively during 2020. Whereas, the simple correlation was negative insignificant with adult female stage and positive insignificant with gravid female stage.

Simple regression was positive significant in case of nymphal stage and total population of *A. aurantii* (4.25684 and 4.13590), respectively throughout 2019 and (5.40103 and 4.87854), respectively during 2020. In case of adult female simple regression was negative insignificant and positive insignificant in case of gravid female recording (-0.18893 and 0.06799) during 2019 and it was negative insignificant in case of the two stages recording (-0.35077 and -0.16007) during 2020, respectively

3.3. The effect of relative humidity percentage:

Data in Two tables mentioned that, simple correlation was negative and significant with nymphal stage (-0.44381) and negative insignificant with total population (-0.34509), respectively throughout 2019 and likewise during 2020 recording (-0.48186 and -0.29593), respectively, in case of adult and gravid females stages the simple correlation were positive and insignificant throughout the two years of study (0.22808 and 0.11364) and (0.42997 and 0.32424), respectively.

Simple regression was positive significant in case of nymphal stage and total population of *A. aurantii* (4.25684 and 4.13590), respectively throughout 2019 and (5.40103 and 4.87854), respectively during 2020.

3.4. The combined effect of abiotic and biotic factors (Partial regression):

The combined effect of climatic (abiotic) factors on the *A. aurantii* different stages and total population

were significant ($F = 10.26$ and 9.33) and the explained variance (E.V.) presented (60.61 and 58.32 %), respectively during the two years of study.

Temperature gave positive significant relation in the 1st season and very significant in the 2nd season, while relative humidity relations was negative in 1st season and positive in the 2nd season but insignificant in both. The effect of all measures was very significant in the 1st season and insignificant in the 2nd season as the total effect was 89.71% and 61.51% during the 1st and 2nd seasons, respectively (Selim, 2014).

Statistical analysis of the relation between *A. aurantii* (Different stages and total population) and abiotic factors revealed that the Max. temp. was effective factors and the combined effect of all factors were significant and the E.V. more than 70% (Haris, 2015).

There was positive significant relationship between metrological factors and the total population of *A. aurantii* and a simultaneous occurrence of the total population of *A. aurantii*, while relative humidity relations was negative in first season and positive in the second season but insignificant in both. (Balboul and Helmy, 2019).

References

- Abd-Rabou, S. (2009):** Parasitoids attacking *Aonidiella aurantii* (Maskell) (Homoptera: Diaspididae) with emphasis on parasitoid fauna of this species in Baharia oasis. Egypt. J. of Agric. Res., 87(4): 939-946.
- Balboul, O. A. and Helmy, S. M. Y. (2019):** Ecological studies of California red scale, *Aonidiella aurantii* (Hemiptera: Diaspididae) infested *Citrus sinensis* in Giza Governorate Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst., 2 (1): 88-95.
- Bedford, E. C. G. (1998):** Red scale, *Aonidiella aurantii* (Maskell). In: Citrus pest in the Republic of South Africa (Bedford ECG *et al.*, ed.). Institute for Tropical and Subtropical Crops, Nelspruit., 132-144.
- Belguendouz, B. R. M.; Biche, R. and Allal-Benfekih, L. (2013):** Bio ecology of citrus pest *Aonidiella aurantii* (Maskell) (Hemiptera: Diaspididae): spatio temporal relationship with its host pants *Citrus limon* and *C. sinensis* in Algiers region. American-Eurasian Journal of Sustainable Agriculture (Special Issue), 7(1): 14-20.
- El-Amir, S. M. (2009):** Studies on some scale insects infesting citrus trees and their control. Ph. D. Thesis, Fac. Agric., Al-Azhar University.
- El-Saadany, G. B.; El-Hakim, A. M.; El-Abassi, T. S. and El-Shouny, K. Y. (1994):** Seasonal abundance and fluctuation of certain scale insects in citrus orchards at Qualubia and Fayoum Governorates. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 72 (3): 665-676.
- Garcia-Mari, F. (2006):** Phytosanitary status of citrus in Spain insects and mites. Informatore Fitopatologico, 56(1):28-31.
- Haris, H. M. A. (2015):** Seasonal and toxicological studies on the red scale insect *Aonidiella aurantii* (Maskell) on citrus in Upper Egypt. Ph. D. Thesis, Fac. of Agric., Sohag University.
- Jacas-Miret, J. A. and Garcia-Mari, F. (2001):** Side effects of pesticides on selected natural enemies occurring in citrus in Spain. Bull. OILB/SROP, 24(4): 103-112.
- Jendoubi, H.K.I.; Garissa, P. S. and Russo, A. (2008):** Scale insects (Hemiptera: Coccoidea) on

- citrus in Tunisia. IOPC/WPRC Bulletin, 38: 87-93.
- Moustafa, M. (2012):** Scale insects (Coccoidae: Hemiptera) infested citrus trees and their natural enemies, with a key of these pests in Egypt. *Egypt. Acad., Journal of biological sciences Entom.*, 5(1):1-23.
- Selim, A. A. (2014):** Ecological Studies on California red scale insect, *Aonidiella aurantii* (Mask.) on some orange varieties in relation to biotic and abiotic factor. *International Journal of Plant and Soil Science*, 3(6): 659-670.
- Spiegel-Roy, P. and Goldschmidt, E.E. (1996):** Biology of citrus. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Yarpuzlu, F.; Oztemyz, M. and Karacaodlu, M. (2008):** Natural enemies and population movement of the California red Scale *Aonidiella aurantia* Maskell (Homoptera: Diaspididae) with efficiency of parasitoid, *Aphytis melinus* (How.) (Hymenoptera: Aphelinidae) in Lemon Orchards. *J. Ent. Res. Soc.*, 10(1): 43-58.

Impact of aromatic plants intercropped with sugar beet on infestation by cotton leafworm, sugar beet fly and associated predators

Ibrahim, F. Khafagy ; Heba, S. Abd El-Aty and Ghada, M. Ramadan

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 17 /1 /2022

Accepted: 23/ 3 /2022

Keywords

Insect pests,
intercropping, sugar
beet, aromatic plants,
and predators.

Abstract:

The current work was carried out to study the Influence of aromatic plants; fennel (*Foeniculum vulgare*), dill (*Anethum graveolens*), coriander (*Corlandrum sativum*), and marjoram (*Majorana hortensis*) intercropped with sugar beet on the population of some insect pests and related predators in 2019/2020 and 2020/2021 seasons. Intercropping reduced damage of *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera, Noctuidae) (Eggs and larvae), and *Pegomya mixta* Villeneuve (Diptera: Anthomyiidae) (Eggs and larvae), especially in the case of fennel + sugar beet, and increased the density of associated predators. Intercropping dille + sugar beet was most attractive for *Coccinella undecimpunctata* L. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae). Fennel intercropping with sugar beet highly increased the population of *Chrysoperla carnea* (Stephens) (Neuroptera : Chrysopidae) while intercropping coriander + sugar beet attracted *Paederus alfieri* Koch. (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae), intercropping marjoram + sugar beet was most attractive to *Scymnus* spp. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) . The highest density of spiders was found in the case of intercropping sugar beet with fennel, followed by sugar beet with marjoram.

Introduction

Sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris* L.) (Family: Chenopodiaceae) is an important sugar crop in Egypt. It has been introduced into the Egyptian agricultural rotation in 1982, and proved to be grown in both fertile and newly reclaimed soils (El-Khouly, 1998). In addition, sugar beet could be used as forage for livestock and for pectin production (Fouad , 2011).

Several insects attack this crop, e.g., *Pegomya mixta* Villeneuve (Diptera: Anthomyiidae) causing considerable damage to yield (Shalaby, 2001). *P. mixta* lives in leaves and eats the leaf tissue, its feeding at first creates twisting mines causing acute damage in

chlorophyll content (Shaheen, 1992 and Muska, 2007). Bazazo (2019) reported that *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera, Noctuidae) may be a detrimental dangerous insect for sugar beet crop, particularly the early plantation. In this case, the insect can negatively affect the plant stand, consequently great reductions in yield, unless insecticidal control measures are applied. The numbers of *Chrysoperla carnea* (Stephens) (Neuroptera : Chrysopidae), *Coccinella undecimpunctata* L. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae), *Scymnus* spp. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae), *Paederus alfieri* Koch. (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae) and *Cydonia vicina*

isis Cr. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) were studied on sugar beet fields by El-Khouly (2006) and Sherief *et al.* (2013).

Intercropping between different crops and their effect on the occurrence of pests is recommended in some cases. Khafagy (2011) found that intercropping of five aromatic plants + kidney beans have reduced whitefly population density. El-Naggar *et al.* (2008) reported that aphids were reduced significantly in plots treated with marjoram extract than in untreated ones.

Aromatic plants having volatile oils may overlap with the host plant location, mating feeding, and distribution and reduce pest abundance (Lu *et al.*, 2007). In general, repellent plants keep insect pests off the main crop (Hjalten *et al.*, 1993).

Therefore, the current work was conducted to highlight the influence of aromatic plants on infestation by cotton leafworm, sugar beet fly, and related predators on the sugar beet crop.

Materials and methods

Field experiments were carried out during two successive cropping seasons; 2019/2020 and 2020/2021 in the experimental field at Sakha Agricultural Research Station, Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate, Egypt to study the influence of aromatic plants intercropped with sugar beet (Table 1) on sugar beet infestation by cotton leafworm, *S. littoralis*, sugar beet fly *P. mixta* and associated predators.

Table (1): Aromatic plants intercropped with sugar beet.

No.	Common name	Scientific name	Plant family
1	Fennel	<i>Foeniculum vulgare</i>	Umbelliferae
2	Dill	<i>Anethum graveolens</i>	Umbelliferae
3	Coriander	<i>Corlandrum sativum</i>	Umbelliferae
4	Marjoram	<i>Majorana hortensis</i>	Labiatae

Results and discussion

1. Impact of intercropping aromatic plants with sugar beet on *Spodoptera littoralis* infestation:

1.1. Mean number of laid eggs on sugar beet plants:

An area of one feddan was prepared and divided into 5 strips, each was 840 m². Each strip was divided into four replicates each was (210 m²) in RCB design. Sugar beet cultivar Faten was cultivated on 15th September in both seasons, as 2-3 seeds per hill. The seeds were sown on the northern side of rows (60 cm width) at a distance of 25 cm. On the southern side, four aromatic plants, fennel, dill, coriander, and marjoram were planted. All agricultural practices regarding the timing of plantation, varieties, and sampling techniques were followed as recommended.

Weekly Samples were taken 30 days after cultivation and continued till the harvest time. Each sample consisted of 10 plants, randomly chosen, from each plot. Samples were examined on the two leaf surfaces with the aid of a Lens and recorded in the field for *S. littoralis* (Eggs and larvae), *P. mixta* (Eggs and larvae), *C. undecimpunctata* (Larvae and adults), *C. carnea* (Larvae and adults), *P. alfierii* (Adults), *Scymnus* spp. (Larvae and adults), and true spiders (Spiderlings and adults).

Statistical Analysis

Reduction % = infestation in control (untreated) - infestation in treatments/ infestation in control × 100. Data were subjected to ANOVA and any significant differences among the mean of the treatments according to Duncan's (1955) method through SPSS Statistics (2015) computer program.

Data in Table (2) show the influence of aromatic plants intercropped with sugar beet on the number of *S. littoralis* laid eggs and larvae on sugar beet plants. In 2019/20, solid sugar beet plants (control)

received the highest number of cotton leafworm eggs (841.25 eggs /10 plants) compared to sugar beet intercropped with aromatic plants that received 20.75 - 199.75 eggs /10 plants. Thus,

Table (2): Mean number and reduction percentage of *Spodoptera littoralis* eggs /10 sugar beet plants under the intercropping system.

Intercropping pattern	2019/20 season		2020/21 season	
	Mean No. eggs	Reduction %	Mean No. eggs	Reduction %
Sugar beet +Fennel	20.75 e	97.53	26.25 e	96.86
Sugar beet +Dill	55.50 d	93.40	65.00 d	92.24
Sugar beet +Coriander	99.75 c	88.14	93.75 c	88.80
Sugar beet +Marjoram	199.75 b	76.26	215.75 b	74.23
Solid sugar beet	841.25a	-	837.25 a	-

Means bearing the same small letters within a column are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

1.2. Mean number of larvae on sugar beet plants:

In 2019/2020 and 2020/2021 seasons (Table 3), solid sugar beet had the highest larval population; 388.75 and 403.75 larvae/ 10 plants, respectively. The second rank of the larval population was detected on the sugar beet + marjoram intercropping pattern; with values of 101.50 and 122.50 larvae / 10 plants in the first and second seasons, respectively. The third

Table (3): Mean number and reduction percentage of *Spodoptera littoralis* larvae/ 10 sugar beet plants under intercropping system.

Intercropping pattern	2019/20 season		2020/21 season	
	Mean No. of Larvae	Reduction % of Larvae	Mean No. of Larvae	Reduction % of Larvae
Sugar beet +Fennel	7.00 e	98.20	11.50 e	97.15
Sugar beet +Dill	33.75 d	91.32	42.25 d	89.54
Sugar beet +Coriander	74.25 c	80.90	82.00 c	79.69
Sugar beet +Marjoram	101.50 b	73.89	122.50 b	69.66
Solid sugar beet	388.75 a	-	403.75 a	-

Means bearing the same small letters within a column are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

2. Effect of intercropping aromatic plants with sugar beet on *Pegomya mixta* infestation:

2.1. Mean number of laid eggs on sugar beet plants:

All intercropping patterns significantly reduced the numbers of *P. mixta* eggs laid on sugar beet leaves as compared to solid sugar beet which received 176.25 eggs / 10 plants (Table 4). The best combination was sugar beet+ dill as the eggs were reduced by

intercropping aromatic plants with sugar beet significantly achieved a 76.26 - 97.53 % reduction in *S. littoralis* eggs. In 2020/2021 season, almost the results were the same as the first season.

rank of the larval population was found on the sugar beet+ coriander intercropping pattern. On the other hand, the least larval population was detected on sugar beet+ fennel intercropping, as this pattern achieved the highest reduction in *S. littoralis* larval population; 98.20 and 97.15% reduction, in the first and second seasons, respectively. The differences among intercropping patterns were significant.

88.51 and 87.48 % in the first and second seasons, respectively. The second rank was that fennel intercropped + sugar beet, with 82.41 and 80.82 % egg reductions, in 2019/2020 and 2020/2021 seasons, respectively. However, the combination of sugar beet + marjoram appeared as the least efficient intercropping pattern with 61.70% and 60.27 % egg reduction in two seasons, respectively.

Table (4): Mean number and reduction percentage of *Pegomya mixta* eggs / 10 sugar beet plants under the intercropping system.

Intercropping pattern	2019/2020 season		2020/2021 season	
	Mean No. of eggs	Reduction %	Mean No. of eggs	Reduction %
Sugar beet +Fennel	31.00 d	82.41	35.25 d	80.82
Sugar beet +Dill	20.25 e	88.51	23.00 e	87.48
Sugar beet +Coriander	40.75 c	76.88	44.25 c	75.92
Sugar beet +Marjoram	67.50 b	61.70	73.00 b	60.27
Solid sugar beet	176.25 a	-	183.75 a	-

Means bearing the same small letters within a column are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT

2.2. Mean number of larvae on sugar beet plants:

Data in Table (5) show that solid sugar beet harbored significantly the highest population of *P. mixta* larvae in two seasons; 166.25 and 170.75 larvae / 10 plants of sugar beet, respectively. Sugar beet + marjoram intercropping pattern occupied the second rank of larvae in sugar beet leaves; 55.00 and

59.25 larvae / 10 plants in 2019/2020 and 2020/2021 seasons, respectively. However, the most efficient intercropping pattern in reducing the pest larvae in sugar beet leaves was sugar beet + dill; 92.93 and 91.80 % larval population reductions in 2019/2020 and 2020/ 2021, respectively.

Table (5): Mean number and reduction percentage of *Pegomya mixta* larvae/ 10 sugar beet plants field under intercropping system.

Intercropping pattern	2019/20 season		2020/21 season	
	Mean No. of Larvae	Reduction % of Larvae	Mean No. of Larvae	Reduction % of Larvae
Sugar beet +Fennel	18.25 d	89.02	20.25 d	88.14
Sugar beet +Dill	11.75 e	92.93	14.00 e	91.80
Sugar beet +Coriander	32.50 c	80.45	33.75 c	80.23
Sugar beet +Marjoram	55.00 b	66.92	59.25 b	65.30
Solid sugar beet	166.25 a	-	170.75 a	-

Means bearing the same small letters within a column are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

3. Influence of intercropping aromatic plants with sugar beet on predatory population:

Sugar beet intercropping with aromatic plants significantly encouraged all considered predators and true spiders compared with solid sugar beet (Table 6). In 2019/ 2020 season, the highest populations of *C. carnea*; 68.00 and 55.25 individuals / 10 plants were obtained with sugar beet + fennel and sugar beet + dill intercropping patterns, respectively.

The number of *C. undecimpunctata* was highest with sugar beet +dill and sugar beet + fennel, followed by sugar beet + coriander, but it was low in plots of solid sugar beet and sugar beet + marjoram pattern. The

highest densities of *P. alfieri* were detected with sugar beet + coriander and sugar beet + fennel, with values of 63.75 and 48.25 individuals /10 plants, respectively. The highest densities of *Scymnus* spp., 60.25 and 49.75 individuals /10 plants were obtained with sugar beet + marjoram followed by sugar beet + coriander intercropping pattern, respectively.

The true spider populations proved to be highest in the case of sugar beet + fennel (62.75), followed by sugar beet + marjoram (52.25 spiderlings and adults /10 plants). The highest number of spiders were found in plots with solid sugar beet, followed by sugar beet intercropped with coriander. Other intercropping patterns resulted in

intermediate population densities of true spiders. Predatory population densities in 2020 /2021 season took a

trend similar to that of 2019 / 2020 season.

Table (6): Mean Number of predators in case of sole and aromatic plants intercropped with sugar beet

Intercropping pattern	<i>Chrysoperla carnea</i>	<i>Coccinella undecimpunctata</i>	<i>Paederus alferii</i>	<i>Scymnus</i> spp.	True spider
Mean number during 2019/20 season					
Sugar beet +Fennel	68.00 a	59.50 b	48.25 b	43.50 c	62.75 a
Sugar beet +Dill	55.25 b	77.75 a	27.25 d	21.00 d	43.25 c
Sugar beet +Coriander	31.50 c	38.00 c	63.75 a	49.75 b	27.55 d
Sugar beet +Marjoram	26.25 d	24.30 d	42.00 c	60.25 a	52.25 b
Solid sugar beet	15.00 e	13.25 e	11.40 e	5.00 e	22.30 e
Mean number during 2020/21 season					
Sugar beet +Fennel	64.50 a	58.25 b	52.25 b	45.00 c	68.50 a
Sugar beet +Dill	52.75 b	65.50 a	30.75 d	23.50 d	49.25 c
Sugar beet +Coriander	29.25 c	31.25 c	68.25 a	52.75 b	33.75 d
Sugar beet +Marjoram	22.5 d	21.00 d	45.25 c	61.00 a	63.00 b
Solid sugar beet	13.25 e	12.00 e	13.00 e	7.50 e	27.50 e

Means bearing the same small letters within a column are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

The current results showed that intercropping aromatic plants with sugar beet reduced the population of *P. mixta* compared to solid sugar beet. It was also clear that aromatic plants were most attractive to predators than solid sugar beet. These results are in line with those of other authors who proved that intercropping increases the predatory populations (Khafagy, 2015). Khafagy *et al.* (2020) found that intercropping of sugar beet + four aromatic plants increased the number of predatory insects and true spiders compared with sole sugar beet and reduced the infestation percentage with *Cassida vittata* Vill. (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) (All stages), especially in the case of intercropping coriander + sugar beet. El-Gobary *et al.* (2014) found that okra plants intercropped with aromatic plants increased the associated numbers of predators and reduced *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hübner) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) compared to control (Solid okra). Companion flowering plants have been used in different cropping systems to enhance

the number of natural enemies (Begum *et al.*, 2006). The abundance of main natural enemies of aphids (Hoverflies, lacewings, and ladybirds) and syrphids richness was greatly enhanced in tailored flower strips compared with sole potato. This increased the average number of eggs deposited by syrphids and lacewings by 127 and 48%, respectively, and reduced the number of aphids by 75% in adjacent potato crops (Tschumi *et al.*, 2016). The increase in the population of natural enemies was attributed to supplying access to nectar-producing plants such as alyssum (*Lobularia maritima* L.). Zytynska *et al.* (2021) hypothesized that the flowers themselves would be important for general natural enemy recruitment, as they are considered as a nectar resource for many of the adult parasitoid/predators. Overall, companion flowering plants with some crops are recommended to activate predators (Jonsson *et al.*, 2008). A literature survey showed that 68 (53%) of the total of 130 natural enemy species had a higher population density

in polycultures compared to monocultures (Andow, 1991). However, floral planting studies often focus on how flowering plants attract natural enemies rather than the whole ecological system (Hatt *et al.*, 2019).

References

- Andow, D. A. (1991):** Vegetational diversity and arthropod population response. *Annu. Rev. Entomol.*, 36 (1): 561-586.
- Bazazo, K. G. (2019):** The role of cotton leafworm control with certain insecticides in increasing sugar beet crop productivity. *Zagazig, J. Agric. Res.*, 46(6): 2229-2238.
- Begum, M.; Gurr, G. M.; Wratten, S. D.; Hedberg, P. R. and Nicol, H. I. (2006):** Using selective food plants to maximize biological control of vineyard pests. *J. Appl. Ecol.*, 43 (3): 547-554.
- Duncan, D. B. (1955):** Multiple Ranges and Multiple F. test. *Biometrics*, 11: 1-24.
- El-Gobary, A.; Khafagy, I. F. and Soma, H. M. (2014):** The role of three intercropping aromatic plants in reducing the American cotton bollworm, *Helicoverpa armigera* (HUB.) infestation and its associated predators on okra, *Abelmoschus esulentus* (L.). *Egypt. J. Plant. Pro. Res.*, 2(4):1-9.
- El-Khouly, M. I. I. (1998):** Ecological studies and control of the tortoise beetle, *Cassida vittata* Villers in sugar beet ecosystem. Ph.D. Thesis, Fac. Agric, Al-Azhar University.
- El-Khouly, M. I. I. (2006):** Population fluctuations of the beet fly, *Pegomyia mixta* Vill. and the tortoise beetle. *Cassida vittata* (Vill) in relation to certain associated natural enemies in sugar beet fields at Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate. *Egypt. J. Biolo. Pest Control*, 16(1): 311-321.
- El-Naggar, A. A. M.; El-Naggar, H. and Fawakhry, F. M. (2008):** Physiological studies on growth and flowering of *Cyprus papyrus*, L. Effect of growing media and water requirements. *Alex. J. Agric. Res.*, 49(3): 93-105.
- Fouad, H. A. M. (2011):** Control of some pests infesting sugar beet at Sharkia Governorate. M. Thesis, Fac. Agric, Mansoura Univ., 172 pp. Fac. of Agric. Kafr El – Sheikh, Tanta University.????
- Hatt, S.; Uytendroek, R.; Lopes, T.; Mouchon, P.; Osawa, N.; Piqueray, J.; Monty, A. and Francis, F. (2019):** Identification of flower functional traits affecting abundance of generalist predators in perennial multiple species wildflower strips. *Arthropod- Plant Interactions*, 13: 127–137.
- Hjalten, J.; Danell, K. and Lundberg, P. (1993):** Herbivore avoidance by association. *Oikos*, 128: 125-131.
- Jonsson, M.; Wratten, S. D.; Landis, D. A. and Gurr, G. M. (2008):** Recent advances in conservation biological control of arthropods by arthropods. *Biol. Control*, 45(2): 172-175.
- Khafagy, I. F. I. (2011):** Promising role of some aromatic plants for the management of *Bemisia tabaci*. Ph.D. Thesis, Fac. Agric., Kafr El-Sheikh University.
- Khafagy, I. F. I. (2015):** The role of some aromatic plants

- intercropping on *Tuta absoluta* infestation and the associated predators on tomato. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res., 3(2): 38-54.
- Khafagy, I. F.; Samy, M. A. and Hamza, A. M. (2020):** Intercropping of some aromatic plants with sugar beet, its effects on the tortoise beetle *Cassida vittata* Vill. infestation, appearance predators and sugar beet yield. J. of Plant Prot. and Path., Mansoura Univ., 11 (2):455-461.
- Lu, W.; Hou, M. L.; Wen, J. H. and Li, J.W. (2007):** Effects of plant volatiles on herbivorous insects. Plant Prot., 33: 7-11.
- Muska, F. (2007):** Damaging presence of aphids on sugar beet and beet in Czech Republic - Historical summary until 2005. (LISTY CUKROV REPAR), 123(9-10):284-287.
- Shaheen, F. A. H. (1992):** Efficiency of field spray insecticides against some sugar beet pests, in relation to their effect on yield and sugar content. J. Agric. Sci. Mansoura. Univ., 17(11): 3642-3647.
- Shalaby, G.A.M. (2001):** Ecological studies on some important sugar-beet pests and natural enemies and their control. Ph. D. Thesis, Fac. of Agric, Kafr El-Sheikh, Tanta university.
- Sherief, E. A. H.; Said, A. A. A.; Shaheen, F. A. H. and Fouad, H. A. M. (2013):** Population fluctuation of certain pests and their associated predator insects on sugar beet in Sharkia governorate, Egypt. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 91 (1): 139-150.
- SPSS Statistics (2015):** IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 23.0. Armonk, NY: IBM Corp.
- Tschumi, M.; Albrecht, M.; Collatz, J.; Dubsy, V.; Entling, M. H.; Najjar- Rodriguez, A. J. and Jacot, K. (2016):** Tailored flower strips pro-mote natural enemy biodiversity and pest control in potato crops. Journal of Applied Ecology, 53: 1169–1176.
- Zytynska, S. E.; Eicher, M.; Fahle, R. and Weisser, W. W. (2021):** Effect of flower identity and diversity on reducing aphid populations via natural enemy communities. Journal of Ecology and Evolution, 11:18434–18445.

Egyptian Journal of Plant
Protection Research Institute

www.ejppri.eg.net

Impacting of some selected plant and cattle dung powders as protectants against *Tribolium castaneum* (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) and *Sitophilus oryzae* (Coleoptera Curculionidae) adults

Raafat, Badr Abo Arab and Nariman, M. El-Tawelah

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 26 /1/2022

Accepted: 30/ 3 /2022

Keywords

Plant oils, plant powders, stored product, toxicity, biology and germination.

Abstract:

Wheat is one of the main crops in Egypt, where the vast majority of the population depends on it for their food. This crop is subjected to sweeping attacks from stored product pests which cause qualitative and quantitative losses. *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst) (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) and *Sitophilus oryzae* (L.) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) are two of the most important insect species which invade the grain crops in store. The aim of this study was to evaluate the efficiency of six plant powders of cotton stem, maize stem, mulberry bough wood, rice haulm, sycamore branch wood, and citrus bough wood, and an animal origin powder, cattle dung against the two mentioned insects, through some of the standard bioassays. The results showed that the two types of powders, either plant or animal achieved moderate toxicity, especially with the highest rates of concentration against the two insects. In addition, they reduced the number of progeny and the weight loss of wheat. The efficiency of all powders fluctuated against the insects and none of them had the first place with the tested parameters. In general, mulberry bough was the one with *S. oryzae* while citrus bough had the same rank against *T. castaneum* based on LC₅₀. Meanwhile, the *S. oryzae* adults were more susceptible than *T. castaneum*. For reduction in progeny and % weight loss, cotton stem powder achieved the lowest effect with *S. oryzae* while rice haulm powder was the premier. On the contrary, rice haulm powder had the fifth position with *T. castaneum* for a reduction in progeny. Maize stem and mulberry bough powder had the third and the fourth order, with both *S. oryzae* and *T. castaneum*, respectively. The effectuation of cattle dung had the same trend as plant powders with the two tested insects, since *T. castaneum* was more tolerant than *S. oryzae* with the all investigated criteria, toxicity, progeny, or weight loss. Findings obtained explained that the rate of 5% of both plant and cattle dung powders had the percent of germination equal to that of control. These current studies suggest introducing these powders as an aspect of an integrated pest management program against stored grain insects especially *S. oryzae* and *T. castaneum* adults.

Introduction

Wheat is one of the main crops in Egypt, where the vast majority of the population depends on it for their food. The volume of Egypt's production of wheat ranges between 8 to 9 million tons annually, while the volume of its consumption reaches 18 million tons per year, the state and the private sector are responsible for filling the gap that ranges between 9-10 million tons by import. The world consumption of wheat in 2020-2021 amounted to 774.3 million tons. This crop is subjected to sweeping attacks from warehouse pests, especially insect pests, which cause a reduction in quality and quantity, as well as the percentage of germination, which costs the state huge burdens.

Most of the postharvest losses can be attributed to storage insect pests (Giga *et al.*, 1991 and Bett and Nguyo, 2007). The rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae* (L.) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) is a major important pest of stored cereal grain products on the farm or in large commercial elevators in the world. Feeding by *S. oryzae* larvae and adults can reduce grain weight by as much as 56-74% (Koura and El-Halfway, 1972 and Adams, 1976). The adult rice weevil is able to survive up to two years under unfavorable environmental conditions and may transfer to field crops due to its flying capability (Jacobs and Calvin, 2001). The weevils reduce germination resulting in lower prices for seed grain (Kern and Koehler, 1994).

For grain weight losses caused by *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst) (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) feeding was highest for wheat followed by rice then maize (Ali *et al.*, 2016). During development, a *T. castaneum* larva consumes a total of 13 mg of wheat flour, and adults during their lifetime consume 315 mg of wheat flour (Hagstrum and Subramanyam, 2000).

T. castaneum also can influence fungal, bacterial and tapeworm problems in grain or animal feeds and at bakeries. Yun *et al.* (2018) found that *T. castaneum* can spread fungal contamination in stored rice and may consequently increase the mycotoxin problem. There are many ways to combat these pests, the most important of which is the control of chemical pesticides. However, it causes the development of insect resistance and environmental pollution resulting from residues of these pesticides, which has a negative impact on human health. The researchers attention turned to searching for alternative methods that are safe, environmentally friendly, easy to obtain, cheap, highly effective on the pest, relatively quickly to decomposing, and have no harmful residues. Plant materials were the acceptable alternative, as they had previously been used successfully on some pests of stored materials.

In recent years, many workers, have given greater attention to the control of stored grain pests by using some plant products to control postharvest loss caused by some stored product insect pests (Enobakhare and Law-Ogbomo, 2002; Law-Ogbomo and Enobakhare, 2007; Tesema *et al.*, 2015; Ntonifor *et al.*, 2010). Botanical insecticides containing different compounds derived from plants secondary metabolism have been tested in order to control stored grain pests with promising results as an alternative to chemical insecticides (Lale, 2002; Koul *et al.*, 2008 and Isman, 2006). The practice of using botanical insecticides in agriculture dates back at least two millennia in ancient China, Egypt, Greece, and India (Isman and Machial, 2006).

Botanical insecticides act on the physiology and behavior of insects and can be classified as a repellent (Abo-Arab *et al.*, 2014; Elbrense *et al.*, 2021;

Guruprasad and Pasha, 2014 and Rahdari and Hamzei, 2017), feeding deterrents antifeedants (Ebadollahi, 2011; Stefanazzi *et al.*, 2011 and Rajkumar *et al.*, 2019), toxicants (Chaubey, 2007 and 2012; Rajkumar *et al.*, 2019; Elbrense *et al.*, 2021), oviposition inhibitors and growth retardation (Akhtar and Isman, 2004; Yusuf *et al.*, 2011) and fumigant (Ajayi *et al.*, 2004). Plant powders were reported by many researchers as insecticidal agents (Ashouri and Shayestch, 2009; Malgorzata and Anna, 2015 and Omran *et al.*, 2020), reducing progeny F₁ (Mahama *et al.*, 2018), reducing the weight loss (Wazid *et al.*, 2020). Many research workers (Gunther *et al.*, 1958; Khare and Agrawal, 1972; Chhlanjeevi, 1991 and Sudheer Reddy *et al.*, 1993) investigated some animal origin inert materials as grain protectants, insecticides as well as repellent and desiccation properties with little or no mammalian toxicity.

Therefore, the present study was carried out to evaluate the efficiency of some plant and cattle dung powders against *S. oryzae* and *T. castaneum* adults through some standard experiments, to determine toxicity, population build up, and weight loss of grain as well as their effect on germination under laboratory conditions.

Materials and methods

1. Insects cultures:

The two tested insects were reared and maintained at the laboratory of Stored Product Res. Dept., Plant Protection Research Institute, Sakha Agric Research Station.

1.1. The red flour beetle, *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst) (Tenebrionidae) (Coleoptera):

Insects were reared on wheat grain mixed with wheat flour. Grain was cleaned and sterilized by heating at 70°C for one hour and put in a glass jar

each containing 400g (30% wheat flour) and provided with (100-200) adult insects. Jars were covered and placed under laboratory conditions of 30±2°C and 65±5% RH. The newly emerged adults (1-2 weeks old) were used in the further tests.

1.2. Rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae* (Curculionidae) (Coleoptera):

The adults of rice weevil, *S. oryzae* were reared on wheat grains under the laboratory conditions of 26±1°C, 65±5% RH. Insects were maintained in small glass jars, each containing 200 gm of wheat grains and 100-200 adult insects. Adults were left for two weeks for egg laying in the jars and were then removed. Two weeks later, insects were collected by sieving the culture using a 10-mesh brass sieve. Insects (1- 2 weeks old) were collected to use in further experiments.

2. Powders

2.1. Plant materials:

Cotton stem, maize stem, mulberry bough wood, rice haulm, sycamore branch wood, and citrus bough wood used as experimental materials were collected from Farm and agricultural land in Kafr El-Sheikh governorate. The collected plant materials were placed in polyethylene bags to prevent the loss of moisture during transportation to the laboratory.

2.2. Procedure of the preparation of the powders:

The experiments mentioned above were washed with distilled water and dried at room temperature to remove residual moisture, then placed in a paper envelope and oven-dried at 55°C for 24 hrs. (Abuye *et al.*, 2003 and Aletor and Adeogun, 1995). The dried stems were ground into powder using a pestle and mortar and sieved through a 300 mesh sieve. The stem powders were used in the next experiments.

2.3. Cattle dung powder:

Cattle dung used as experimental material was collected

from Animal Production Farm, Sakha Agriculture Research Station, Kafr El-Sheikh. Cattle dung was freshly taken, then dried in shade with diffuse light, and then, ground into a fine powder using a hand mill (Quern). Cattle dung powder was sieved using a 300 mesh sieve. The sieved powder was used for experiments.

3. Bioassay application method:

The appropriate amount of the plant or cattle dung powder which gives the required concentration was thoroughly mixed with wheat grains (whole or crushed) at four rates (0.5, 1, 2, and 5% w/w). for plant powders and (5, 10, 20, and 25% w/w) for cattle dung powder. 20 adults of *T. castaneum* and *S. oryzae* (1-2 weeks) were introduced to each glass jar (3 x 10 cm) containing 20 gm of treated medium (crushed and whole grain) for the two insects, respectively.

The jars were covered with muslin cloth fixed with the rubber band and kept in the same rearing conditions. Each treatment was conducted in three replicates. In addition, three replicates of untreated grains were used as the control for comparison. The temperature and relative humidity (RH.) conditions of the laboratory were recorded daily until the end of the experiment. The mean daily temperature and R.H. in the laboratory ranged from (20- 35°C) and (66.5-76.5%), respectively.

4. Lethal activity

Mortality was assessed 7 days after treatment application. The number of dead adult insects in each replicate was converted into the proportion of the total number of adult insects introduced and expressed as a percentage. Mortality data were corrected for control mortality using Abbott's correction formula:

$$\%CM = \frac{(\%T - \%C)}{\%C} \times 100 \quad (\text{Abbott, 1925})$$

$$(100 - \%C)$$

Where:

CM = The corrected mortality

T = The mortality in treated seeds

C = the mortality in untreated seeds

Concentration - mortality response lines were drawn, LC₅₀ and slope values were calculated according to the method of Finney (1952).

4.1. F₁ progeny emergence:

At the end of 7 days period, mortality counts of insects were recorded for each treatment, then we removed the dead and lived insects from jars. Jars were covered with muslin kept in position with rubber bands and stored under laboratory conditions to allow insects to complete their life cycle. At the end of the life cycle period, the number of F₁ progeny was recorded.

Adults emerged were counted and the reduction of progeny was calculated as follows:

$$\% \text{ Reduction} = [(C-T)/C] \times 100$$

Where:

C = No. of adults emerged in control

T = No. of adults emerged in treatment.

4.2. Weight loss:

The contents of each jar were sieved to remove the dust, frass, and any insects present in the grain. The re-weight of the grains was computed as (Harris and Linblad, 1978).

$$\% \text{ wt loss} = (W_i - W_f) 100/W_i$$

Where:

W_i = Initial weight

W_f = Final weight

4.3. Seed germination:

In order to assess the viability of treated seeds after F₁ emergence of *T. castaneum* and *S. oryzae* adults, seed germination was tested using 20 randomly picked seeds from undamaged grains after separation of damaged and undamaged grains in each jar. The seeds were placed on a moistened filter paper in plastic Petri dishes and the number of germinated seeds was recorded after 10 days.

Results and discussion

1. Effect of botanical powders on stored products insects:

In order to reduce the dependence of the farmers on synthetic insecticides for protecting stored food, attempts were made to derive a treatment using a locally available substitute. In the present trials, a variety of botanical powders have been tested on *S. oryzae* and *T. castaneum*. Botanical powders tested were cotton stem, maize stem, mulberry bough wood, rice haulm, sycamore branch wood, and citrus bough.

Table (1) included the results which explain the effectiveness of the tested powders against the two tested insect adults. Based on LC₅₀ except for citrus bough powder, *S. oryzae* adults were more susceptible than *T. castaneum*. LC₅₀ values ranged from 0.1 – 1.29 and 0.36 – 1.87 w/w for *S. oryzae* and *T. castaneum* 7 days post treatment, respectively. The induction of all powders increased with increasing concentration with the two tested insects. Mortality percent was from 15.60 – 100.00 at the all concentrations with the two tested species,

This difference in response may depend on the ability of the tested insect to pick up the tested powder, the surface of the insect exposed to powder, and the abraded wax layer after 7 days of treatment. Moreover, the behavior of movement and habit of nutrition perhaps play a role belonging to the response of tested insects to the tested powders. In addition, the variation of efficacy probably depends on the type of powder (Its persistence and its degradation during the period of the experiment) and the taxonomy position of the tested insect species.

Additionally, the differentiation in toxicity of the used plant powder results from a group of factors such, as the type of tested insect

species, the type of plant used, and the ambient conditions. Also, results showed that mulberry had the greatest action against *S. oryzae* while citrus bough had the first order among the powder against *T. castaneum*. Maize stem powder had the least effective against both insects. There is no significant difference between rice and sycamore powders against *S. oryzae* or between mulberry and sycamore against *T. castaneum*.

2. Effect of plant powders on the biology of tested insects:

The present trials were conducted to evaluate the powders of cotton stem, maize stem, mulberry bough wood, rice haulm sycamore branch wood, and citrus bough as stored product protectants on biology and weight loss besides the germination percentage of seeds exposed to *T. castaneum*, and *S. oryzae*. Results in Table (2) comprised the efficacy of plant powders admixed with wheat grains on number of F₁ adult emergence, reduction percent of progeny, and loss weight % of wheat grains. The reduction in F₁ progeny of the two tested insects ranged between 1.49 and 91.79% with all concentrations of all powders. The results showed that *S. oryzae* had a higher response (in F₁ reduction 9.38 – 91.79) compared to *T. castaneum* with F₁ reduction (1.49 – 87.38) (Table 2).

The increase in mortality percent and the decrease of progeny compared to control led to the reduction of weight loss percentage in the all tested quantity of powder and the response paralleled with the different levels of powder. Percent loss of weight in grains treated with powder significantly reduced with all levels where the loss percentage ranged between (1.24 – 15.33) for *S. oryzae* and (0.5 – 19.1) with *T. castaneum* compared to control which caused % weight loss between 23.40 to 43.22 for

T. castanum and *S. oryzae*, respectively.

Also, there is no significant difference between the highest level (5%) of all powders which achieved the greatest reduction in progeny (F_1). Based on the numbers of progeny and the percent of wheat weight loss may divide the powders into two groups, the first includes the strongest powders, maize, mulberry, rice, and sycamore powders. While the second group comprised that of the least effective, cotton stem and citrus bough powders. For *T. castaneum*, the powders had directions that differ from that of *S. oryzae* except for cotton and rice powders, these achieved the same effect on both *S. oryzae* and *T. castaneum*.

Most may divide the effect of powders on *T. castaneum* adults into 3 categories concerning wheat weight loss since citrus bough was the premier followed by rice, mulberry, sycamore, and maize powders as the second category, then cotton stem powder as the third group which had the least effect. In belonging to the F_1 progeny the cotton stem was the least agent among the tested powders while the other remainder powders present the best compared to the control. In general, the response of the two insects to powders obviously differed, since *S. oryzae* was more susceptible than *T. castaneum*.

These differences between the two insect species may depend on some factors such as morphology (Area of insect surface), physiology, genetics, sensory organs, and eating habits. Results showed that the weight loss often parallels the number of progenies of each insect. One of the abnormal observations is that the many numbers consume less food than the few numbers, and this may be due to the indirect effect of the tested materials on the vital processes inside the insect. F_1 progeny of all treatments decreased

compared to control. The corresponding reduction rates in F_1 progeny were from 1.49 – 91.79 with the two tested species. Weight loss percentage was also significantly reduced in treated grains compared to control where % loss was from 0.5 – 19.10 in treated seeds while control was from 23.40-43.22% by the all tested insects.

Stored grains are subjected to attack by a group of insects which might cause serious losses. The use of insecticides on food materials possess many problems. Nowadays, the attention is going to the control of the stored product pests using save alternative agents instead of the traditional toxicants. These alternatives included botanical materials, different inert chemicals, and others (Golob *et al.*, 1982; Ivbijaro, 1984; Su, 1985 and Halawa *et al.*, 1998).

In many areas of the world locally available materials are widely used to protect stored produce against damage by insect infestation (Golob and Webley, 1980). There are various mineral substances, which can be added to stored grains such as fine sand, clay dust, quicklime, and wood ash. The admixture of such mineral materials to the harvest crops causes invisible injury to the protective wax layer of stored product insects, leading to dehydration. The addition of ash to cereal grain legumes is widespread in tile African countries (El-Lakwah *et al.*, 1996).

Also, the findings of the current study are in agreement with the results of Golob *et al.* (1982) studied the effectiveness of wood ash, tobacco dust, and sawdust when admixed with maize to protect the grain during storage. They found that all tested ash materials restricted infestation. The effectiveness was directly related to dosage. Also, they found that the protection afforded by wood ash admixed at 30% by weight was of the

same order as that provided by admixing pirimiphos-methyl at 8.8 ppm. Don-Pedro (1985) tested the toxicity of powdered sun-dried orange and grapefruit peels to *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Fabricius) (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) and *Dermestes maculatus* DeGeer (Coleoptera : Dermestidae) in the laboratory at rates of 4 and 5.62, 14.13 and 14.29%. Orange and grapefruit peels deterred adult test insects produced from admixed cowpea and dried fish chips, respectively.

Orange peel at high dosages was also shown to depress progeny development of *D. maculatus*. Golob and Hanks (1990) reported that paddy husk ash provided good protection against *P. truncatus* and *S. oryzae* when applied to maize grain. El-Lakwah *et al.* (1996) studied the effect of cotton stem ash against *S. oryzae*, *R. dominica*, and *T. castaneum* in the laboratory. Results revealed that mortalities increased with increasing concentration and exposure period and the mortalities ranged from 60-65%, 35-45% and 33-55% for *S. oryzae*, *R. dominica*, and *T. castaneum*, respectively at rates from (1-4% wt/wt).

El-Kashlan (1999) evaluated the effectiveness of burned rice husks compared to malathion against *S. oryzae* L., *R. dominica* F., and *C. maculatus* (F.). Results indicated that malathion was the most toxic. Burned rice husks showed promising results and could be used as a grain protectant against stored product insects. El-Lakwah *et al.* (2000) investigated the effects of maize husk ash on mortality and reduction in F₁ progeny of *S. oryzae*, *R. dominica*, *T. castaneum*, and *C. maculatus*.

Results showed that adult mortalities were concentration and exposure period dependent. Reduction in F₁ progeny was also concentration dependent and reached its maximum at the highest concentration used. Mahdi

and Khalaquzzaman (2006) tested the paddy husk ash admixed with cowpea seeds on *C. maculatus*. They found that LD₅₀ was 1479.29 and 974.11 ppm after 24 and 48 h, respectively. Golob (1997) stated that dusts such as ash are required in quantities of at least 5% by weight to be effective protectants against storage pests. Smith *et al.* (2006) reported that in the longer term the use of ash may be more effective on *Prostephanus truncatus* despite the lower initial rate of mortality. It has been suggested that ash can cause mortality by clogging insect spiracles and tracheae (Katanga-Apuuli and Villet, 1996).

Dusts also, cause insect mortality by desiccation because of absorption of cuticular wax (Golob, 1997). Swain and Baral (2005) determined the effect of different ashes (Wood ash, rice straw ash, bamboo ash, and rice husk ash) for controlling rice weevil, *S. oryzae*, and pulse beetle *C. chinensis* in the laboratory in a humidity chamber on wheat and pulse seeds, respectively. The wheat and pulse seeds were thoroughly mixed with ash at 0.5 g/100 g seeds. The results revealed that the different ashes significantly hindered the normal growth of the insect population. Rice husk ash was considered the best in controlling the insects in comparison to other ashes tested.

3. Effect of cattle dung:

Results summarized in Table (3), indicate the percent of mortality increased with increasing concentration with the two tested insects. In addition, *T. castaneum* adults were more tolerant than *S. oryzae* based on the LC₅₀. Results in Table (4), showed that the effect of cattle dung powder on the studied parameters had the same trend as the plant powders for the two insects.

Since the produced F₁ and the weight loss reduced with the increasing of powder rate. Also, the % weight loss was parallel with the insect number, and

S. oryzae adults were more susceptible than *T. castaneum*. All rates of concentration had a significant deterrent effect on the investigated criteria compared to control with the two insects. Except for citrus bough powder which reduced the germination of wheat grain at all concentrations, the highest concentrations of plant powders (2 and 5%) and the lowest concentration (5%) of cattle dung gave a percent of germination equal to that of control.

Overall, the tested materials, plant, and cattle dung powders, the presented results revealed that all plant powders had the greatest deterrent effect in comparison with cattle dung with the two insect species *S. oryzae* and *T. castaneum* on the all studied standards. Bruce Robin *et al.* (2018) reported that cow dung ash was effective in controlling bean bruchid since there was less bruchid population and damage as compared to control and cow urine seeds. Pradhan (2016) stated that cow dung ash and cow urine are less toxic than commercial insecticides in the market and easy for the local farmers. Ash is reported as an effective measure against bruchid by Chinwada and Giga (1997) and Baier and Webster (1991). According to Sivakumar and Amutha (2012) and Venkatasubramaniam *et al.*, (2017), the major content of cow dung ash

composition is silica which has insecticidal properties (EPA, 1991).

4. Effect of tested powders on germination:

A Series of experiments were carried out in the laboratory to estimate % the germination of treated wheat grains exposed to tested insects. Batches of wheat grain were admixed with the tested powders at the required rates of 0.5, 1, 2, and 5% of the treated medium. and exposed to *S. oryzae*, and *T. castaneum* adults. At the end of the experiment, after removing the adults of F₁ progeny, a number of grains were soaked in water and were placed on wet filter paper in a Petri dish, then after 10 days, % germination was estimated and summarized in Table (5).

Despite insect infestation of wheat grains germination percentages were from 87.0-95, with the two types of powders and their rates in comparison with control which reached 96 with *S. oryzae*, and *T. castaneum*. The highest percent germination was found with the higher rates of powder (5%) while the lowest germination was at the least quantity of powder (0.5%). These findings may be due to the decrease of infestation at the highest rates of tested ashes.

Table (1): Comparative toxicity of the tested powders against *Sitophilus oryzae* and *Tribolium castaneum* adults after 7 days post treatment.

Plant powder	Conc.	<i>Sitophilus oryzae</i>				<i>Tribolium castaneum</i>				
		% M 7 day	LC50	C.L	S.V	% M	LC50	C.L	S.V	
Cotton stem	0.5	34.33		0.82		23.40				
	1.0	46.72	1.04	1.26	1.54	42.00	1.26	1.05-1.50	1.74	
	2.0	63.40								67.50
	5.0	87.90								83.43
Maize stem	0.5	17.20				15.60				
	1.0	42.40	1.29	1.12-1.47	2.46	24.50	1.87	0.94-2.65	2.23	
	2.0	59.80								43.70
	5.0	96.20								89.40
Mulberry bough	0.5	76.70				46.60				
	1.0	86.70	0.10	0.09-0.18	0.95	66.70	0.52	0.30-0.71	1.14	
	2.0	93.30								73.40
	5.0	100.00								86.60
Rice haulm	0.5	56.6				36.70				
	1.0	70.00	0.46	0.32-0.55	2.2	46.70	0.94	0.64-1.16	1.92	
	2.0	94.70								66.50
	5.0	100.00								97.00
Sycamore branch	0.5	53.40				36.70				
	1.0	64.32	0.49	0.31-0.65	1.39	66.70	0.70	0.52-0.86	1.59	
	2.0	80.20								76.60
	5.0	93.35								90.00
Citrus bough	0.5	45.20				53.40				
	1.0	48.70	0.80	0.56-1.03	1.24	66.70	0.36	0.14-0.57	0.93	
	2.0	66.40								80.00
	5.0	86.70								83.40
Control	0.00	0.00								

Table (2): Response of *Sitophilus oryzae* and *Tribolium castaneum* adults to wheat grain mixed with the tested powders.

Powder	Conc.	<i>Sitophilus oryzae</i>			<i>Tribolium castaneum</i>		
		No. of F1 progeny	Reduction in F1	% Loss of wheat grain	No. of F1 progeny	Reduction in F1	% Loss of wheat grain
Cotton stem	0.5	116.00ghi	9.38	15.33g	132.00ij	1.49	18.41ij
	1.0	103.00gh	19.13	13.43.fg	130.00ij	2.98	19.10j
	2.0	99.00g	22.01	9.35ef	113.00i	15.67	12.40h
	5.0	72.00e	43.75	7.74cde	62.00ef	53.73	4.70cde
	Cont.	128.00i	-	43.22h	134.00ij	-	23.40k
Maize stem	0.5	55.00de	57.03	5.40cd	75.00fg	43.88	7.53fg
	1.0	42.00d	66.64	4.37bc	69.00efg	28.29	6.41e
	2.0	30.00bc	75.85	3.99abc	41.cd	69.15	5.37e
	5.0	10.00a	91.79	2.71ab	16.00a	87.38	4.52cd
	Cont.	128.00i	-	43.22h	134.00ij	-	23.40k
Mulberry bough	0.5	38.00cd	69.68	5.52cd	76.00fg	43.28	7.10efg
	1.0	41.00d	97.81	3.14abc	72.00fg	46.26	6.53de
	2.0	38.00cd	70.31	2.21ab	52.00de	60.82	3.47c
	5.0	22.00ab	82.81	1.71a	48.00cde	63.65	1.43ab
	Cont.	128.00i	-	43.22h	134.00ij	-	23.40k
Rice haulm	0.5	43.00d	66.95	5.65cd	102.00h	23.88	7.60gh
	1.0	32.00bcd	74.37	3.93abc	92.00h	31.34	6.70fg
	2.0	25.00ab	80.46	2.13ab	68.00efg	49.25	2.70bc
	5.0	13.00a	89.84	1.24a	38.00bc	71.64	0.50a
	Cont.	128.i	-	43.22h	134.00ij	-	23.40k
Sycamore branch	0.5	41.00d	67.72	6.22cde	62.00ef	53.73	7.23fg
	1.0	35.00cd	72.18	4.11bc	53.00de	60.44	6.67ef
	2.0	29.00bc	77.03	3.19abc	39.00c	70.89	4.35cd
	5.0	22.00ab	82.50	2.65ab	16.00a	87.38	3.99c
	Cont.	128.00i	-	43.22h	134.00ij	-	23.40k
Citrus bough	0.5	92.00fg	28.12	11.04efg	74.00fg	44.77	3.70c
	1.0	87.00ef	32.03	9.82ef	53.00de	60.44	2.10b
	2.0	42.00d	66.48	7.40cde	32.00b	76.11	1.30ab
	5.0	22.00ab	82.10	5.43cd	22.00a	83.05	0.90a
	Cont.	128.00i	-	43.22h	134.00ij	-	23.40k

Means followed by the same letter are not significant at (p=0.05).

Table (3): Toxicity of cattle dung powder on *Sitophilus oryzae* and *Tribolium castaneum* adults after 7 days posttreatment.

Insects	Conc.	% Mortality	LC50	C.L.		Slope value
				Lower	Upper	
<i>Sitophilus oryzae</i>	5	48.33	5.03	2.73	11.79	2.30
	10	80.00				
	20	86.00				
	25	98.00				
<i>Tribolium castaneum</i>	5	37.00	8.57	6.17	10.75	1.32
	10	56.70				
	20	65.00				
	25	75.00				

Table (4): Response of *Sitophilus oryzae* and *Tribolium castaneum* adults to cattle dung powder after 7 days at the indicated concentration.

Insects	Conc.	No. of F1 progeny	Reduction in F1	% Loss weight wheat
<i>Sitophilus oryzae</i>	5	36ef	68.69	5.33c
	10	28cde	75.65	3.22abc
	20	18abc	84.34	2.40ab
	25	9ab	91.47	1.99ab
	control	115i	-	38.33i
<i>Tribolium castaneum</i>	5	65h	57.79	18.43de
	10	42fg	72.70	17.33de
	20	25cd	83.76	9.40cd
	25	20bc	87.01	5.33c
	control	154j	-	29.44f

Table (5): Germination of wheat grain treated with the plant powders and cattle dung after F₁ emergence of *Sitophilus oryzae* and *Tribolium castaneum* adults.

Powder	Conc. % w/w	<i>Sitophilus oryzae</i>	<i>Tribolium castaneum</i>
Cotton	0.5	91.00 b-f	90.00 a-d
	1.0	91.00 b-f	92.00 b-e
	2.0	92.70 d-h	92.50 b-f
	5.0	93.00 d-h	94.00 ef
Maize	0.5	89.00 abc	89.00 ab
	1.0	90.60 a-d	91.00 ae
	2.0	93.40 e-h	93.00 c-f
	5.0	94.20 fgh	93.40 def
Mulberry	0.5	91.00 b-f	89.00 ab
	1.0	91.50 c-f	91.00 a-e
	2.0	93.00 d-h	93.00 c-f
	5.0	94.20 fgh	94.00 ef
Rice	0.5	90.00 a-d	91.00 a-e
	1.0	90.70 b-e	91.50 a-e
	2.0	92.00 c-g	93.00 c-f
	5.0	95.00 gh	93.90 e-f
Sycamore	0.5	88.00 ab	89.00 ab
	1.0	89.00 abc	89.00 ab
	2.0	91.00 b-f	91.00 a-e
	5.0	93.00 d-h	92.00 b-e
Citrus	0.5	87.00 a	88.00 a
	1.0	89.70 a-d	89.50 abc
	2.0	91.00 b-f	91.00 a-e
	5.0	93.00 d-h	92.00 b-e
Cattle dung	0.5	93.00 d-h	95.00 f
	1.0	92.70 c-g	93.00 cf
	2.0	89.00 a-d	91.00 a-e
	5.0	87.00 a	89.70 abc
Control		96.00 h	96.00 f

References

- Abbott, W. W. (1925):** A method computing the effectiveness of an insecticide. *J. Econ. Entomol.*, 18: 265-267.
- Abo-Arab, R.B.; Awadalla, S.S.; Abd El-Salam, A.H. and El-Maodowy, E.A. (2014):** Toxicity and repellent activity of spinosad and orange oil against *Rhizopertha dominica* F. and *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst). *J. Plant Prot. and Path. Mansoura Univ.*, 5(1): 23-32.
- Abuye, C.; Urga, K.; Knapp, H.; Selmar, D.; Omwega, A.; Imungi, J. and Winterhalter, P.A. (2003):** Survey of wild, green, leafy vegetables and their potential in combating micronutrient deficiencies in rural populations. *East Afr. Med. J.*, 80: 247-252.
- Adams, J.M. (1976):** Weight loss caused by development of *S. oryzae*. *J. Stored Prod. Res.*, 12:269-272.
- Ajayi, O.E.; Apple, A.G. and Fadamiro, H.Y. (2014):** Fumigation toxicity of essential oil monoterpenes to *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Bruchinae). *Journal of insects* volume, Article ID917212, 7 pages <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2014/9/17212>.
- Akhtar, Y. and Isman, M.B. (2004):** Comparative growth inhibitory and antifeedant effects of plant extracts and pure allelochemicals on four phytophagous insect species. *J. Appl. Entomol.*, 128: 32-38.
- Aletor, V. and Adeogun, O. (1995):** Chemical analysis of the fruit of *Vitex doniana* (Verbenaceae). *Food Chem.*, 53: 375-379.
- Ali, Q.M.H.; Hasan, Q.M.; Sagheer, M.; Ranjh, M.H. and Shahbaz, M. (2016):** Appraisal of quantitative losses caused by *Trogoderma granarium* (Everts) and *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst) in different genotypes of wheat, rice and maize during storage. *J. Appl. Biol. Sci.*, 10: 8-14.
- Ashouri, S., and Shayesteh, N. (2009):** Insecticidal activities of black pepper and red pepper in powder form on adults of *Rhizopertha dominica* (F.) and *Sitophilus granarius* (L.). *Pak. Entomol.*, 31:2.
- Baier, A. H. and Webster, B. D. (1992):** Control of *Acanthoscelides obtectus* Say (Coleoptera: Bruchidae) in *Phaseolus vulgaris* L. seed stored on small farms—I. Evaluation of damage. *J. Stored Prod. Res.*, 28: 289-293.
- Bett, C. and Nguyo, R. (2007):** Post-harvest storage practices and techniques used by farmers in semiarid Estem and central Kenya. *African Crop. Sci. Conf. Pro.*, 8: 1023-1227.
- Bruce Robin, N.; Gorret, K. and Ronald, N. (2018):** Evaluating the effectiveness of cow dung ash and cow urine against bean bruchid beetles. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/326655580>.
- Chaubey, M.K. (2007):** Toxicity of essential oils from *Cuminum cyminum* (Umbelliferae), *Piper nigrum* (Piperaceae) and *Foeniculum vulgare* (Umbelliferae) against stored-product beetle *Tribolium castaneum* Herbst (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae). *Electr. J. Environ Agric. Food Chem.*, 6: 1719-1727.

- Chaubey, M.K. (2012):** Biological effects of essential oils against Rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae* L. (Coleoptera: Curculionidae). J. Essent. Oil Bear. Plants, 15: 809-815.
- Chinwada, P. and Giga, D.P. (1997):** Traditional seed protectants for the control of bean bruchid. (www.researchgate.net).
- Chlranjeevi, C.M. (1991):** Efficacy of some indigenous plant materials and ashes on the damage and viability of greengram seed infested by pulse beetle, *Callosobruchus chinensis* (L.). Bulletin of Grain Technology, 29: 84-88.
- Don-Pedro, K.N. (1985):** Toxicity of some citrus peels to *Dermestes maculatus* Deg. and *Callosobruchus maculatus* (F). Journal of Stored Products Research, 21(1): 31-34.
- Ebadollahi, A. (2011):** Antifeedant activity of essential oils from *Eucalyptus globulus* Labill and *Lavandula stoechas* L. on *Tribolium castaneum* Herbst (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae). Bihar., 5(1): 8-10.
- Elbrense, H.; El-Hussieny, I.; Abo El Makarem, H.; Abo Arab, R. and Elkholy, S. (2021):** Insecticidal, antifeedant and repellent efficacy of certain essential oils against adult rust red flour beetle, *Tribolium castaneum* (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae). Egypt J. Chem., 65(1): 167-178.
- El-Lakwah, F. A., Sanaa M. Mahgoub and Salwa M. Mohamed. (2000):** Effect of maize husk ash and mustard seeds powder (*Brassica arvensis*) as grains protectants on some stored product insects. Annals of Agric. Sci., Moshtohor, 38 (1): 565-571.
- El-Lakwah, F. A.; Khaled, O.M. and Halawa, Z. A. (1996):** Effect of modified atmosphere of more than 99% nitrogen or enriched with carbon dioxide on mortality of some stored product insects, seed germination, chlorophyll and carotene contents of certain crop seedlings. Annals of Agric. Sci., Moshtohor, 34 (4): 1869-1877.
- Enobakhare, D.A. and Law-Ogbomo, K.E. (2002):** Reduction of post-harvest loss caused by *Sitophilus zeamais* (Motsch) in three varieties of maize treated with plant products. Postharvest Sci., 1: 1-6.
- EPA (1991):** Silicon dioxide and silica gel (<https://archive.epa.gov/pesticides/reregistration>).
- Finney, D. J. (1952):** Probit analysis: A statistical treatment of the sigmoid response curve (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- Giga, D.P.; Mutemerewa, S.; Moyo, G. and Neeley, D. (1991):** Assessment and control of losses caused by insect pests in small farmers' stores in Zimbabwe. Crop Protection, 10 (4): 287-292.
- Golob, P. (1997):** Current status and future perspectives for inert dusts for control of stored product insects. Journal of Stored Products Research, 3(1): 69-79.
- Golob, P. and Hanks, C. (1990):** Protection of farm stored maize against infestation by *Prostephanus truncatus* in Tanzania. Journal of Stored Products Research, 26: 187-198.

- Golob, P. and Webley, D. J. (1980):** The use of plants and minerals as traditional protectants of stored products. G138. Chatham, UK: Natural Resources Institute.
- Golob, P.; Mwambula, j.; Mhango, V. and Ngulube, F. (1982):** The use of locally available materials as protectants of maize grain against insect infestation during storage in Malawi. *Journal of Stored Products Research*, 18: 67-74.
- Gunther, F.A.; Lindgren, D.H. and Blinn, R.C. (1958):** Biological effectiveness and persistence of malathion and lindane used for protection of stored wheat. *Journal of Economic Entomology*, 51: 843- 844.
- Guruprasad, B.R. and Pasha, K. (2014):** Assessment of repellency and insecticidal activity of *Ajuga parviflora* (Benth) and *Trichilia connaroides* (W&A) leaf extracts against stored product insects. *J. Entomol. Zool. Stud.*, 2(4): 221-226.
- Hagstrum, D.W. and Subramanyam, B.H. (2000):** Monitoring and decision tools ed. Bh. Subramanyam, D.W. Hagstrum Alternatives to pesticides in stored product IPM. pp 1-28. Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- Halawa, Z. A.; Mohamed, R. A. and El-Kashlan, I. H. (1998):** Laboratory evaluation of some plants and insecticides against cowpea beetle (*Callosobruchus maculatus*, F.) infesting stored products. *Egypt. J. Agric. Res.*, 76 (1): 85-94.
- Harris, K.L. and Linblad, C.J. (1978):** Post harvest loss assessment methods. A manual of methods for the evaluation of post-harvest losses. American Association of Cereal Chemists, 75-79.
- Isman, M.B. (2006):** Botanical insecticides, deterrents, and repellents in modern agriculture and an increasingly regulated world. *Annu. Rev. Entomol.*, 50: 45-66.
- Isman, M.B. and Machial, C.M. (2006):** Pesticides based on plant essential oils: from traditional practice to commercialization. In M. Rai and M.C. Carpinella (eds.), *Naturally Occurring Bioactive Compounds*, Elsevier, BV, 29–44.
- Ivbijaro, M. F. (1984):** Toxic effects of groundnut oil on the rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae*. *Insect Sci., Appl.*, 5: 251-252.
- Mahdi, S. H. A. and Khalequzzaman, M. (2006):** Toxicity Studies of Some Inert Dusts with the Cowpea Beetle, *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Fabricius) (Coleoptera: Bruchidae). *Journal of Biological Sciences*, 6: 402-407.
- Jacobs, S. and Calvin, D. (2001):** Weevils on Stored Grain. Penn State College of Agricultural Sciences. Retrieved from the web on October 18th, 2016 from <http://ento.psu.edu/extension/factsheets/pdf/weevilsgrain.pdf>.
- Katanga-Apuuli, J.K. and Villet, M.H. (1996):** The use of wood ash for the protection of stored cowpea seed (*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp) against Bruchidae (Coleoptera). *African Entomology*, 4: 97-99.
- Kern, W.H. Jr. and Koehler, P.G. (1994):** Rice weevil, *Sitophilus oryzae* (Coleoptera: Curculionidae). Fact sheet ENY-261, A Series of the

- Entomology and Nematology Department Florida Cooperative Extension service, Institute of Food and Agricultural Sciences, University of Florida.
- Khare, B.P. and Agarwal, R. K. (1972):** Effect of nontoxic materials on insect infestation in stored grain. *Indian Journal of Entomology*, 34:169-172.
- Koul, O.; Walia, S. and Dhaliwal, G.S. (2008):** Essential oils as green pesticides: potential and constraints. *Biopesticides Int.*, 4(1): 63-84.
- Koura, A. and El-Halfawy, M.A. (1972):** Weight loss in stored grains caused by insect infestation in Egypt. *J. Egypt Entomol. Soc.*, 56: 413-417.
- Lale, N.E.S. (2002):** Stored product entomology and acarology in tropical Africa. 204 p. Mole Publications, Maiduguri, Nigeria.
- Law-Ogbomo, K. E. and Enobakhare, D.A. (2007):** The Use of Leaf Powders of *Ocimum gratissimum* and *Vernonia amygdalina* for the management of *Sitophilus oryzae* (Lin.) in Stored Rice. *Journal of Entomology*, 4(3):253-257.
- Mahama, A.; Saidou, C. ;Tofel, H.K.; Ali, A. ; Adj, M.B. and Nukenine, E.N. (2018):** Efficacy of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* leaf extracts against the pea beetle *Callosobruchus maculatus* and their impact on biochemical and microbiological properties of the treated bambara groundnut grains. *J. Entomol. and Zoology Studies*, 6(2): 869–877.
- Malgorzata, K. and Anna, P. (2015):** The mortality *Oryzaephilus surinamensis* L. (Coleoptera: Silvanidae) induced by powder plants. *J. plant protection Research*, 55(1): 110-116.
- Ntonifor, N.N.; Oben, E.O. and Konie, C.B. (2010):** Use of selected plant-derived powders and their combinations to protect stored cowpea grains against damage by *Callosobruchus maculatus*. *ARPN J.Agric. Biol.Sci.*, 5:13-21.
- Omran, I.M.; Hassan, K.S. and Almansour, N. (2020):** Effect of some plant powders and insecticides admiral and runner against saw-toothed grain beetle *O. Surinamensis* L. (Silvanidae: Coleoptera). *Plant Archives*, 20 (2): 774-778.
- Pradhan, B. (2016):** Cow urine replaces pesticide in Sikkim farms. <https://www.livemint.com/Politics/k8Q1uQ8LvZL5eIQG5OiHcN/Cow>.
- Rahdari, T. and Hamzei, M. (2017):** Repellency effect of essential oils of *Mentha piperita*, *Rosmarinus officinalis* and *Coriandrum sativum* on *Tribolium confusum* Duval (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae). *Chem Res. J.*, 2(2): 107-112.
- Rajkumar, V.; Gunasekaran, C.; Christy, I. K.; Dharmaraj, J.; Chinnaraj, P. and Paul, C. A. (2019):** Toxicity, antifeedant and biochemical efficacy of *Mentha piperita* L. essential oil and their major constituents against stored grain pest. *Pestic. Biochem. Physiol.*, 156:138–144.
- Sivakumar, G. and Amutha, K. (2018):** Studies on silica obtained from cow dung ash. *Advanced Materials*, 584(9): 470-473.

- Smith, . M.; Moore, D.; Oduor, G. et al. (2006):** Effect of wood ash and conidia of *Beauveria bassiana* (Balsamo) Vuillemin on mortality of *Prostephanus truncatus* (Horn). Journal of Stored Products Research, 42(3):357-366.
- Stefanazzi, N.; Stadler, T. and Ferrero, A. (2011):** Composition and toxic, repellent and feeding deterrent activity of essential oils against the stored-grain pests *Tribolium castaneum* (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) and *Sitophilus oryzae* (Coleoptera: Curculionidae). Pest Manag. Sci., 67(6): 639-646.
- Su, H. C. F. (1985):** Laboratory evaluation of biological activity of *Cinnamomum cassia* to four species of stored product insects. J. Ent. Sci., 20 (2): 247-253.
- Sudheer Reddy, V.; Ramesh Babu, T. and Hussaini, S.H. (1993):** Effect of inert materials on germination and grain damage by stored grain pests of sorghum. Seed Research, 1: 285- 287.
- Venkatasubramanian, C.; Muthu, D.; Aswini, G.; Nandhini, G. and Muhilini, K. (2017):** Experimental Studies on Effect of Cow Dung Ash (Pozzolanic Binder) and Coconut Fiber on Strength Properties of Concrete, IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science. Retrieved from <http://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1755-1315/80/1/012012/pdf>.
- Wazid, W.S.; Nadagouda, A.; Prabhuraj, R.H.; Shahuntala; N. N.M. and Sharanagouda, H. (2020):** The persistence of residual toxicity of zinc, copper and silica green nanoparticles against important storage pests. J. Entomol. Zool. Studies, 8(5): 1207-1211.
- Yun, T.S; Park, S.Y.; Yu, J.Y.; Hwang, Y.J. and Hong, K.J. (2018):** Isolation and identification of fungal species from the insect pest *Tribolium castaneum* in rice processing complexes in Korea. Plant Path. J., 34: 356-366.
- Yusuf, A.U.; Dike, M.C.; Adebitan, S.A. and Ahmed, B. I. (2011):** Comparative efficacy of seven plant products on the cowpea burchid, *Callosobruchus maculatus* F. development and damage. J. Biopestici, 4(1): 19-26.

Efficacy of different natural compounds on cotton and tomato whitefly *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) and its parasitoid *Eretmocerus mundus* (Hymenoptera: Aphelinidae) on vegetable crops

Shaaban, Abd-Rabou¹; El-Amir, S. M.¹ and Xiao-Wei, Wang²

¹Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

²Ministry of Agriculture Key Laboratory of Molecular Biology of Crop Pathogens and Insects, Institute of Insect Sciences, Zhejiang University, Hangzhou 310058, China.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 1 /2/2022

Accepted: 28/ 3 /2022

Keywords

Bemisia tabaci ,
Eretmocerus mundus, squash, cucumber, natural compounds, and Egypt.

Abstract:

The cotton and tomato whitefly *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) is a widely distributed and highly harmful plant pest species. In this study, we evaluated the insecticidal effects of insecticides and botanical oils against the cotton and tomato whitefly *B. tabaci* infested squash and cucumber and its parasitoid *E. mundus* in Garbiya and Minufiya Governorates, respectively, throughout the experiment period 2020 and 2021. The results indicated that the confidor was the most effective treatment against *B. tabaci* and its parasitoid *Eretmocerus mundus* (Mercet) (Hymenoptera: Aphelinidae). Lemon oil compound caused the lowest reduction against *B. tabaci* and its parasitoid *E. mundus*. It is concluded that essential oil and plant extract are promising compounds to control *B. tabaci* and are safe to survive the parasitoid *E. mundus*.

Introduction

The cotton and tomato whitefly *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae), a pest with piercing-sucking mouthparts, is the most significant pest of agriculture and horticulture worldwide and is widely distributed throughout tropical and subtropical regions (Brown and Bird, 1992 and Abd-Rabou and Simmons, 2010)).

B. tabaci is not a single species but a complex of 46 cryptic species, which are potential vectors of approximately 320 begomovirus species, most of which are significant plant viruses (De Barro *et al.*, 2011). High populations of *B. tabaci* induce losses in plant productivity by direct feeding, fungal growth associated with

honeydew contamination, and plant physiological disorders. Losses also occur from *B. tabaci* due to the efficient transmission of *Begomovirus*, a genus of the taxonomic family Geminiviridae that causes leaf yellow mosaic and mottling, leaf distortion, and stunting (Oliveira *et al.*, 2001 and Morales, 2007).

Synthetic chemical pesticides have served as a main tool in crop protection over the past 50 years (Chandler *et al.*, 2011). However, excessive and injudicious use of these synthetic pesticides has resulted in management failure and damage to human health and the environment (Palumbo *et al.*, 2001 and Isman, 2006). The use of pesticide products based on “old” chemistry is becoming more

difficult and being withdrawn because of the development of heritable resistance and new health and safety legislation (Chandler *et al.*, 2011). Despite the urgent need for alternative tactics, the rate at which new and more environment-friendly chemicals such as biopesticides are being developed is very low (Thacker, 2002). To date, pyrethrum and neem are well established in the marketplace, and plant essential oil products have been recently added to the arsenal (Pimentel, 2005).

The management of *B. tabaci* has been typically carried out by chemical pesticides. In the last decade, however, there has been an increasing interest in natural products, particularly those of plant origin, to control this pest species. In a recent review article by Chandler *et al.* (2011) only four biopesticides including *Bacillus thuringiensis var kurstaki* (Bacterium), *Beauveria bassiana* (Fungus), *Cydia pomonella* GV (Virus), and azadirachtin (Biochemical) were listed as active ingredients in the representative examples of commercially available biopesticides. For *B. tabaci*, previous studies indicate that pyrethrum, neem-based formulation, and essential oils have promising potentials to control whiteflies (Golmohammadi *et al.*, 2014). Simmonds *et al.* (2002) stated that for the whitefly *Trialeurodes vaporariorum* (Westwood) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae), applications of pyrethrum resulted in fast and high mortality to the adults but also showed high toxicity on a whitefly parasitoid *Encarsia formosa* Gahan (Hymenoptera: Aphelinidae). In the same study, the authors concluded that a commercial neem-based formulation had the most potential for use in an IPM program because the neem product caused 50% mortality of adult

whiteflies in 6 h with very low toxicity to the parasitoid.

Limonene is an active insecticidal compound in several pesticides used as insecticides, insect repellents, and dog and cat repellents (Hebeish *et al.*, 2008). The potential adverse effects of insecticides on plants have been studied with various synthetic and natural compounds (Liu *et al.*, 2006). A recent study showed the deterrence and toxicity effects of citronellol and geraniol on *B. tabaci* (Baldin *et al.*, 2014). In many studies, the activity of essential oil against insects is explained by the major compounds (Ipek *et al.*, 2005). Cruz-Estrada *et al.* (2013) stated that the most promising compounds of four essential oils (Cumin, cinnamon, citronella, and lemongrass) for pest control applications and the most promising compounds for net treatments were cinnamaldehyde, limonene, citronellol, citronellal, citral, and geraniol because their associated whitefly net-crossing rates were low. The identified volatile candidates may be emitted by companion plants or by diffusers, e.g., Chemically impregnated nets, to repel whiteflies. Essential oils could be used alone or in mixtures to establish an olfactory barrier as a supplement to the visual and physical barrier of an insect-proof net in order to protect vegetables (Deletre *et al.*, 2016).

In this study, we evaluated the insecticidal effects of insecticides and botanical oils against the cotton and tomato whitefly *B. tabaci* infested squash and cucumber and its parasitoid *E. mundus* in Garbiya and Minufiya, Governorates, respectively.

Materials and methods

1. Efficacy of insecticides and botanical oils against the cotton and tomato whitefly *Bemisia tabaci* and its parasitoid:

The current study was carried out to evaluate the field performance of

eight insecticides in their respective commercial formulations available on the market. The insecticide generic and chemical information is given in Table (1). The concentrations used were based on the recommendations of the Egyptian Ministry of Agriculture for each insecticide to control the pest insects under field conditions.

A field trial was conducted on squash and cucumber plants grown on a farm located in Garbiya and Minufiya Governorates, respectively, during two consecutive summer seasons of 2020 and 2021. The infested plants with cotton and tomato whitefly were identified, selected, and labeled before the application of insecticides. This area did not receive any insecticidal treatments before the start of the experiment. The trial of nine treatments (Eight insecticides + control) was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replicates. A spray was applied with a CP3 knapsack sprayer (Cooper Pegler Co. Ltd., Northumberland, England). The insecticides were used in the commercial formulation and the concentrations were prepared using

Table (1): Insecticides and botanical oils with their trade name, the active ingredient, and rate of application.

Trade Name	Common Name	Rate/ L Water
KZ oil	Mineral oil	1 Litre oil/ 100 Liter water
Biovar	<i>Beauveria bassiana</i>	200 gm / 100 L.
Bioranza	<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i>	200 ml/100 L.
Azadirachtin	<i>Azadirachtin indica</i>	5 ml/Lw
Lemon oil	Lemon oil	5 cm/1L
Applaud	Buprofezin	600 cm ³ /fed.
Garlic oil extraction	Garlic oil extraction	5 cm/1L
Confidor 20 SL	Imidacloprid	30 cm /100L

Results and discussion

1. Efficacy of insecticides and botanical oils against the cotton and tomato whitefly *Bemisia tabaci* and its parasitoid in Garbiya on squash during 2020-2021:

The obtained data shown in (Tables 2-5) revealed that the confidor was the most effective treatments against *B. tabaci* throughout the

water as a diluent. Insecticides were sprayed in the early morning when the insects were active, and the environmental conditions minimize the potential risk of spray drift and evaporation. Control plots were sprayed with water only. Thirty plants with a heavy infestation of whitefly and associated the parasitoid were randomly selected in the field. Plant to plant distance was 30 cm. Each plant acted as a replicate. The spray application was done on 20th and 30th October during 2020 and 2021, respectively. Data were recorded on the selected plants before spraying and 7, 14 and 21 days after application. The mean numbers cotton whitefly per plants and associated parasitoid were recorded.

2. Statistical Analysis:

The data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) and the means were compared with LSD test at 0.05 level, using the SAS. The percent reduction of the whitefly population and associated parasitoid in all treatments compared to the control were calculated according to the Henderson and Tilton formula (1955).

experiment period 2020 and 2021. Whereas the reduction percentage for confidor was 91.97 and 93.35, respectively. In addition, Kz oil gave (89.17 and 90.22%) reduction followed by garlic oil (85.62 and 86.56%), applaud (85.01 and 84.01), bioranza (83.63 and 85.71), azadirachtin (82.88 and 93.42), biovar (80.53 and 81.17) and lemon oil (80.0 and 78.68),

respectively. Considering the probable occurring side effects of the tested compounds on the non-targeted parasitoid *E. mundus* during 2020 and 2021, the data shown in (Tables 2 to 5) illustrate that lemon oil compound caused a lowest reduction effect (58.86 and 57.5%) followed by ascending by azadirachtin (62.91 and 64.26%), then bioranza (63.71 and 64.26 %), and garlic oil (63.87 and 69.34%) with no significant differences between them. Then confidor, KZ oil, biovar and applaud where they caused highest parasite reduction percentage reached (73.18 and 74.54%), (69.32 and 70.79%), (69.32 and 66.95 %) and (69.95 and 68.88%) in respect without no significant differences between them. Results of statistical analysis (F value and L.S.D.) (Tables, 3-5) showed that seven treatments had significant effect on populations.

2.Efficacy of insecticides and botanical oils against the cotton and tomato whitefly *Bemisia tabaci* and its parasitoid in Minufiya on cucumber 2020-2021:

The obtained data shown in (Tables, 6 - 9) revealed that the confidor was the most effective treatments against *B. tabaci* throughout the experiment period 2020 and 2021. Whereas the reduction percentage for confidor was 92.02, respectively. In addition, KZ oil (91.58 and 90.85) reduction followed by garlic oil (85.97 and 84.85%), applaud (85.97 and 83.84%), bioranza (84.71 and 85.07), biovar (83.33 and 82.62), azadirachtin (82.67 and 80.40), and lemon oil (79.9 and 81.91), respectively. Considering the probable occurring side effects of the tested compounds on the non-targeted parasitoid *E. mundus* during 2020 and 2021, the data shown in (Table 6 and 9) illustrate that lemon oil compound caused a lowest reduction effect (62.77 and 53.98 %) followed by ascending by garlic oil (65.76 and 60.87

%), azadirachtin (66.54and60.72 %) and applaud (66.72-62.48) (With no significant differences between them. Then KZ oil, confidor, bioranza, biovar. Where they caused the highest parasite reduction percentage reached (75.58 and 78.45%), (72.78 and 68.42%), (70.61 and 68.4 %) , (68.72and 64.76%) in respect without no significant differences between them.

Results of statistical analysis (F value and L.S.D.) (Tables, 7 and 9) showed that seven treatments had a significant effect on populations.

The results of the present work indicated that Kz oil gave (89. 17 and 90.22%) reduction followed by garlic oil (85.62 and 86.56%), and lemon oil (80.0 and 78.68%), respectively, during the two years under consideration in Garbiya on squash. While KZ oil (91.58 and 90.85%) was reduced followed by garlic oil (85.97 and 84.85%), and lemon oil (79.9 and 81.91%), respectively. during the two years under consideration in Minufiya on cucumber.

Essential oils of *Cymbopogon citratus*, *Cymbopogon winterianus*, *Cuminum cyminum* and *Cinnamomumzeylanicum* showed toxic effects at 1%, i.e. 96.3% mortality for cinnamon oil, 64.7% for citronella oil, 61.0% for lemongrass oil and 30.0% for cumin oil (Deletre *et al.*, 2016). The present work results indicated that the effect of azadirachtin on *B. tabaci* were (82.88 and 93.42%) in Garbiya on squash and (82.67and 80.40 %) in Minufiya on cucumber 2020-2021, respectively. Plant extracts are currently being studied as an ecologically friendly alternative to manage plant pests. Studies on botanical insecticides against *B. tabaci* have focused particularly on essential oils of different plants, such as *Thymus vulgaris*, *Allium cepa*, *Allium sativum*, *Satureja hortensis*, *Achillea biebersteinii*, *Cinnamomum verum*, *Syzygium aromaticum*, *Alkanna strigosa*, *Ballota undulate*, *Galium longifolium*, *Lepidium sativum*, *Peganum harmala*,

Pimpinella anisum, *Ruta chalepensis*, *Retama raetam* and *Urtica pilulifera*, where 60-100% mortality has been reported (Ateyyat *et al.*, 2009). Other authors have also documented the insecticidal effects of seed oil from *Azadirachta indica*, and their principle active ingredient azadirachtin on *B. tabaci* (Aslan *et al.*, 2004; Pinheiro *et al.*, 2009 and Lynn *et al.*, 2010). In general, the insecticidal properties of most of the native and adapted plants in Yucatan have been scarcely studied. In this work, all aqueous and ethanolic extracts of tested plants caused high mortality on *B. tabaci* eggs, however, on *B. tabaci* nymphs only ethanolic extracts were active (Cruz-Estrada *et al.*, 2013).

Studies on the insecticidal properties of *A. squamosa* have been focused mainly on the activity of its seed extracts, where activity has been attributed to the metabolites squamocin, annotemoyin and neoannonin, which target Diptera, Coleoptera and Lepidoptera, (Castillo-Sánchez *et al.*, 2010). This is worth noting that among all plant species tested, only in *Petiveria alliaceae* both types of extracts (Aqueous and ethanolic) were active on immature *B. tabaci*. The insecticidal activity of extracts of leaves and other organs of *P. alliaceae* has been previously reported. For example, García-Mateos *et al.* (2007) reported that aqueous, methanolic and dichloromethane extracts of leaves caused 100% mortality on the whitefly *Trialeurodes vaporariorum* (Westwood). The plant extracts *Trichilia arborea* showed high insecticidal activity. To the best of our knowledge, no reports of insecticidal activity or chemical constituents of this endemic species was previously available. Nevertheless, *Trichilia* genus belongs to the Meliaceae family, as *Azadirachta indica*, for instance we might expect *T. arborea* to have insecticidal properties. Other species of *Trichilia*, like *T. pallida*, has shown insecticidal effects. For

example, Baldin *et al.* (2007) documented those aqueous extracts of branches and leaves of *T. pallida* caused high mortality on *B. tabaci* nymphs in tomato plants under greenhouse conditions.

The plant extracts tested in this study, particularly those of *T. arborea* and *P. alliaceae* showed the potential to be developed into compounds for the management of immature whitefly. Further research will focus on evaluating these extracts through a bioassay-guided process, to determine the metabolites responsible for the insecticidal effect on immatures of *B. tabaci*. In the long term, our goal is to develop safer alternatives to manage *B. tabaci*. These natural products might be considered an important component of the integrated pest management system.

The family Aphelinidae contains many *B. tabaci* parasitic wasps including the most important genus *E. mundus* is indigenous to the Mediterranean region and is used commercially for *B. tabaci* management in many parts of the world (Urbaneja *et al.*, 2007). The three most promising plant extracts (*Alkanna strigosa*, *Peganum harmal* and *Ruta chalepensis*) were tested to determine if they adversely affect *E. mundus*. The results showed that the extracts *P. harmala* and *R. chalepensis* were not detrimental to the parasitoid; however, *A. strigosa* adversely affected the emergence of *E. mundus* from *B. tabaci* parasitized pupa. The identification of selective chemicals with little or no harmful effects on the *B. tabaci* parasitoid is a desirable goal for the development of sound and effective management strategies.

It is concluded that essential oil and plant extract are promising control methods for *B. tabaci* and are safe to survive the parasitoid *E. mundus*. Also, it plays a good role in the integrated management of this pest.

Table (2): Average numbers of the cotton whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* and its associated parasitoid on squash plants in Garbiya during summer season 2020.

Treatment	Rate of Applic. /L.W.	Pre spraying count						Post spraying count after:						Average number					
		7			15			21			A			N			P		
		A	N	P	A	N	P	A	N	P	A	N	P	A	N	P	A	N	P
KZ oil	1 Litre oil/ 100 Liter water	78.8	314	81.1	14.1	38.9	28.2	11.7	28	27	26.1	9.9	17.5	26.1	11.9	28.1	20	27.1	
Biovar	200 gm / 100 L.	84.9	362	83.7	24.9	81.0	34.3	22.3	61.3	32.9	31.8	19.1	43.1	31.8	22.1	61.8	41.95	33.0	
Bioranza	200 ml/100 L.	87.7	408	86.2	20.1	79.7	36.2	18.3	64.3	34.7	32.8	15.3	56.0	32.8	17.9	66.66	42.28	34.5	
Azadirachtin	5 ml/Lw	81.3	325.9	78.2	18.1	69.3	32.9	17.9	54.0	31.2	30.7	15.1	43.1	30.7	17.03	55.46	36.24	31.6	
Lemon oil	5 cm/1L	92.3	433.8	99.8	29.3	99.5	48.1	23.3	78.7	44.3	42.2	18.1	65.0	42.2	23.56	81.06	52.31	44.8	
Applaud	600 cm3 /fed.	82.8	330	79.3	21.6	46.3	27.4	19.0	36.7	26.1	25.2	14.8	22.5	25.2	18.46	35.16	26.81	26.2	
Garlic oil extraction	5 cm /1L	90.9	429.7	85.5	18.7	72.2	35.0	16.3	58.3	33.9	32.3	13.9	49.0	32.3	16.3	59.83	38.06	33.7	
Confidor 20 SL	30 cm /100L	88.7	389.4	83.0	12.0	26.7	26.3	9.3	28.7	24.0	22.3	6.8	18.0	22.3	9.36	27.8	18.58	24.2	
Control		91.6	421.7	94.6	96.3	45.7	77.1	101.1	47.2	103.3	110.0	108.2	489.3	110.0	101.8	472.1	287.0	103.46	
A. Adult																			
N.Nymph																			
P. Parasitoid																			
T. Total																			

Table (3): Reduction percentage of different compounds on the cotton whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* and its parasitoid on squash plants in Garbiya during summer season 2020.

Treatment	Rate of Applic. /L.W.	%Reduction after:											
		15				30				45			
		A	N	P	A	N	P	A	N	P	A	N	P
KZ oil	1 Litre oil/ 100 Liter water	82.98	89.4	66.13	86.55	92.13	69.52	89.37	95.28	72.33	92.05	89.17	69.32
Biovar	200 gm / 100 L.	72.11	79.36	60.08	76.21	84.82	64.01	80.96	89.74	67.33	84.64	80.53	63.80
Bioranza	200 ml/100 L.	78.69	84.98	59.09	81.52	85.87	63.14	85.56	88.18	67.28	85.34	84.13	63.17
Azadirachtin	5 ml/Lw	78.83	80.38	59.02	80.06	85.14	63.47	84.28	88.61	66.24	84.71	82.88	62.91
Lemon oil	5 cm/1L	69.81	78.84	53.05	77.13	83.73	59.35	83.4	87.09	63.64	83.22	80.0	58.68
Applaud	600 cm3/fed.	75.04	87.06	66.34	79.09	90.03	69.86	84.78	94.13	72.57	90.40	85.01	69.59
Garlic oil extraction	5 cm/1L	80.44	84.5	60.12	83.76	87.84	63.7	87.06	90.18	67.52	87.50	85.62	63.78
Confidor SL	30 cm /100L	87.14	91.31	69.13	90.51	93.39	73.52	93.51	96.02	76.9	93.57	91.97	73.18
F value													
L.S.D.													

A. Adult N.Nymph P. Parasitoid T. Total

A b c d letters indicating significantly differences between treatments

Table (4): Average numbers of the cotton whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* and its associated parasitoid on squash plants in Garbiya during summer season 2021.

Treatment	Rate of Applic. /L.W.	Pre spraying count						Post spraying count after:						Average number								
		7		15		21		7		15		21		A		N		T		P		
		A	N	P	A	N	P	A	N	P	A	N	P	A	N	P	A	N	P	A	N	P
KZ oil	1 Litre oil/ 100 Liter water	82.1	328.3	78.8	41.1	28.2	9.7	29.7	25.1	6.1	18.1	22.9	10.2	29.63	19.91	25.4						
Biovar	200 gm / 100 L.	79.6	301.3	72.7	77.3	27.7	17.7	55.9	26.9	14.1	38.1	25.5	18.03	57.1	37.56	26.7						
Bioranza	200 ml/100 L.	84.2	345.2	83.7	69.1	32.1	13.9	43.2	29.3	9.9	38.1	27.9	14.3	50.13	32.21	29.76						
Azadirachtin	5 ml/Lw	80.9	316.4	76.6	600.7	31.8	17.9	45.5	30.7	14.8	37.7	28.4	17.43	47.96	32.69	30.3						
Lemon oil	5 cm/1L	75.9	289.9	68.4	75.7	33.9	20.7	53.1	32.8	17.8	41.9	29.7	20.9	56.9	38.9	32.1						
Applaud	600 cm3 /fed.	86.3	361.2	85.5	48.9	31.0	21.4	35.1	29.0	19.7	25.7	28.4	21.66	36.56	29.11	29.46						
Garlic oil extraction	5 cm/1L	77.9	293.2	74.7	44.3	26.2	31.1	36.6	25.3	9.4	28.3	24.4	13.43	36.4	24.91	25.3						
Confidor 20 SL	30 cm /100L	87.1	377.0	88.2	34.1	27.9	8.3	19.0	24.4	4.8	6.9	22.0	8.0	20.0	14.0	24.76						
Control		81.9	320.2	79.9	34.33	82.1	89.7	371.1	89.2	94.2	404.0	95.8	89.33	372.8	231.06	689.03						
A. Adult	N.Nymph	P. Parasitoid	T. Total																			

Table (5): Reduction percentage of different compounds on the cotton whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* and its parasitoid on squash plants in Garbiya during summer season 2020.

Treatment	Rate of Applic. /L.W.	Average %reduction																	
		%Reduction after: 15						%Reduction after: 30						%Reduction after: 45					
		A	N	P	A	N	P	A	N	P	A	N	P	A	N	P			
KZ oil	1 Litre oil/100 Liter water	82.4 5	88.33	65.13	89.22	92.2	71.47	93.55	95.64	75.77	88.40	92.05	90.22 ab	70.79 ab					
Biovar	200 gm / 100 L.	72.7 2	76.08	62.92	79.7	84.0	66.86	84.6	89.98	70.75	79.0	83.35	81.17 c	66.84 ab					
Bioranza	200 ml/100 L.	77.9 1	81.33	62.68	84.93	89.14	68.65	89.78	91.21	72.2	84.20	87.22	85.71 ab	67.84 ab					
Azadirachtin	5 ml/Lw	76.4 1	82.11	59.6	79.8	87.6	64.11	84.1	90.56	69.08	80.10	86.75	83.42 bc	64.26 bc					
Lemon oil	5 cm/1L	68.9 6	75.65	51.7	75.1	84.2	57.05	79.62	88.55	63.79	74.56	82.8	78.68 c	57.51 c					
Applaud	600 cm3 /fed.	73.0 4	87.38	64.72	77.36	91.62	69.62	80.3	94.37	72.3	76.9	91.12	84.01 bc	68.88 ab					
Garlic oil extraction	5 cm/1L	77.7 5	85.91	65.87	84.65	89.23	69.67	89.51	92.35	72.76	83.97	89.16	86.56 abc	69.43 ab					
Confidor SL	20 30 cm /100L	87.8 2	91.57	69.22	91.3	95.66	75.22	95.2	98.55	77.2	91.44	95.26	93.35 a	73.88 a					
F value													2.79	3.38					
L.S.D.													8.48	7.98					

A. Adult N.Nymph P. Parasitoid T. Total

A b c d letters indicating significantly differences between treatments

Table (6): Average numbers of the cotton whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* and its associated parasitoid on cucumber plants in Minufiya during summer season 2020.

Treatment	Rate of Applic. /L.W.	Pre spraying count						Post spraying count after:						Average number					
		15			30			45			60			75			90		
		A	N	P	A	N	P	A	N	P	A	N	P	A	N	P	A	N	P
KZ oil	1 Litre oil/ 100 Liter water	91.2	414.1	93.7	13.9	40.0	27.3	11.0	30.9	26.0	7.3	19.3	24.9	30.06	20.39	26.06			
Biovar	200 gm / 100 L.	87.7	387.2	86.3	21.1	75.0	32.1	19.0	63.2	31.0	16.8	51.2	30.0	63.13	41.04	31.03			
Bioranza	200 ml/100 L.	93.7	431.3	98.2	22.0	76.6	34.0	18.1	64.3	33.1	16.3	49.0	32.5	63.3	41.05	33.2			
Azadirachtin	5 ml/Lw	97.8	482.0	102.1	23.9	101.0	41.1	21.3	83.9	38.8	18.9	69.0	37.9	84.63	52.99	39.26			
Lemon oil	5 cm/1L	89.9	406.4	91.1	26.1	93.3	39.8	23.0	81.0	38.9	20.2	69.9	38.4	81.4	52.25	39.03			
Applaud	600 cm3 /fed.	94.7	449.1	96.3	22.1	67.9	37.7	20.7	55.6	37.0	17.0	38.3	35.9	53.93	36.93	36.86			
Garlic oil extraction	5 cm/1L	88.9	382.0	90.0	18.9	61.5	36.0	16.8	52.0	35.5	15.6	36.7	34.9	50.06	33.58	35.46			
Confidor SL	30 cm /100L	85.9	351.2	83.8	12.0	33.1	28.0	9.1	24.0	26.2	7.3	17.1	24.3	24.73	17.09	26.1			
Control		95.7	4221.0	91.2	103.2	449.3	76.7	111.3	468.1	104.3	122.1	499.7	115.9	472.3	292.25	105.6			

A. Adult N.Nymph P. Parasitoid T. Total

Table (7): Reduction percentage of different compounds on the cotton whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* and its parasitoid on cucumber plants in Minufiya during summer season 2020.

Treatment	Rate of Applic. /L.W.	%Reduction after:													
		15				30				45					
		A	N	P	A	N	P	A	N	P	A	N	P		
KZ oil	1 Litre oil/100 Liter water	85.87	90.93	72.53	89.63	93.28	75.74	93.73	96.07	79.09	93.42	89.74	93.42	91.58 ab	75.78 a
Biovar	200 gm /100 L.	77.69	81.81	64.92	81.38	85.29	68.6	84.99	88.84	72.65	85.31	81.35	85.31	83.33 C	68.72 bc
Bioranza	200 ml/100 L.	78.23	83.32	67.35	83.4	86.56	71.24	86.37	90.41	73.96	86.76	82.66	86.76	84.71 C	70.61 ab
Azadirachtin	5 ml/Lw	77.34	80.32	62.04	81.28	84.31	66.78	84.86	87.91	70.8	84.18	81.16	84.18	82.67 C	66.54 bc
Lemon oil	5 cm/1L	73.08	78.44	58.8	78.01	82.03	62.67	82.39	85.48	66.84	81.98	77.82	81.98	79.9 C	62.77 c
Applaud	600 cm3 /fed.	78.36	85.8	63.08	81.21	88.84	66.41	85.93	92.8	70.67	89.14	81.83	89.14	85.48 Bc	66.72 bc
Garlic oil extraction	5 cm/1L	80.29	84.88	62.28	83.76	88.32	65.51	86.25	92.33	69.49	88.51	83.43	88.51	85.97 Ab	65.76 c
Confidor 20 SL	30 cm /100L	87.05	91.15	68.49	90.9	93.84	72.67	93.34	95.89	77.19	93.62	90.43	93.62	92.02 A	72.78 ab
F value														4.20	3.58
L.S.D.														6.16	6.66

A. Adult N.Nymph P. Parasitoid T. Total

A b c d letters indicating significant differences between treatments

Table (8): Average numbers of the cotton whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* and its associated parasitoid on cucumber plants in Minufiya during summer season 2021.

Treatment	Rate of Applic. /L.W.	Pre spraying count						Post spraying count after:						Average number							
		15		30		45		15		30		45		A		N		T		P	
		A	N	P	A	N	P	A	N	P	A	N	P	A	N	P	A	N	T	P	
KZ oil	1 Litre oil/ 100 Liter water	89.3	395.8	91.3	13.8	42.4	30.0	10.4	37	28.8	7.4	23.7	27.4	10.53	34.36	22.44	28.73				
Biovar	200 gm / 100 L.	96.6	465.9	111.0	25.3	88.9	46.0	21.5	76.6	45.7	19.1	66.0	44.8	21.96	77.16	49.56	45.5				
Bioranza	200 ml/100 L.	85.6	361.4	83.9	18.9	65.7	32.0	16.1	53.0	31.3	14.9	35.2	29.0	16.63	51.3	33.96	30.76				
Azadirachtin	5 ml/Lw	92.9	427.8	107.2	25.0	91.2	51.1	22.9	86.0	48.7	21.1	73.9	46.9	23.0	83.7	53.35	48.9				
Lemon oil	5 cm/1L	98.1	481.0	118.3	24.6	88.7	64.0	22.8	83.3	63.5	21.9	80.2	62.5	23.1	84.06	53.58	63.33				
Applaud	600 cm3 /fed.	87.8	392.7	89.8	25.9	58.8	40.8	22.8	41.0	38.7	18.7	28.8	37.9	22.46	42.86	32.66	39.13				
Garlic oil extraction	5 cm/1L	90.3	398.9	96.1	21.7	65	45.0	19.0	49.3	43.9	16.8	41.3	42.2	19.16	51.86	35.51	43.7				
Confidor SL	30 cm /100L	93.1	433.4	98.2	14.0	41.8	31.1	11.1	28.3	30.8	7.1	15.9	29.0	10.7	28.6	19.65	30.3				
Control		91.8	409.2	96.2	97.1	425.3	103	106.5	454	113.3	117	489.6	121.3	106.8	456.3	281.55	112.46				
A. Adult	N.Nymph	P. Parasitoid		T. Total																	

Table (9): Reduction percentage of different compounds on the cotton whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* and its parasitoid on cucumber plants in Minufiya during summer season 2021.

Treatment	Rate of Applic. /L.W.	%Reduction after:												
		15				30				45				
		A	N	P	A	N	P	A	N	P	A	N	P	
KZ oil	1 Litre oil/ 100 Liter water	85.39	89.7	69.31	89.97	91.58	73.22	93.5	95.0	76.16	89.62	92.09	90.85	72.89
Biovar	200 gm / 100 L.	75.32	81.65	61.3	80.88	85.19	65.05	84.54	88.17	67.94	80.24	85.0	82.62	64.76
Bioranza	200 ml/100 L.	79.13	82.51	64.38	83.79	86.79	68.33	86.35	91.86	72.55	83.09	87.05	85.07	68.42
Azadirachtin	5 ml/Lw	74.56	79.49	55.48	78.76	81.89	61.43	82.18	85.56	65.25	78.5	82.31	80.40	60.72
Lemon oil	5 cm/IL	76.3	82.62	49.48	79.97	84.4	54.43	82.49	86.07	58.04	79.58	84.24	81.91	53.98
Applaud	600 cm3 /fed.	72.12	85.6	57.57	77.62	90.59	63.41	77.62	93.88	66.48	77.67	90.02	82.91	62.48
Garlic oil extraction	5 cm/IL	77.29	84.33	56.27	81.87	88.87	61.22	85.41	91.35	65.12	81.52	88.18	84.85	60.87
Confidor 20 SL	30 cm /100L	85.79	90.73	70.43	89.73	94.12	73.37	94.02	96.74	76.55	89.84	93.93	91.88	73.45
F value													4.09	8.01
L.S.D.													6.17	7.02

A. Adult N.Nymph P. Parasitoid T. Total

A b c d letters indicating significantly differences between treatments

References

- Abd-Rabou, S. and Simmons, A.M. (2010):** Survey of Reproductive Host Plants of *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) in Egypt, including New Host Records. *Entomological News*, 121: 456-465. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3157/021.121.0507>.
- Ateyyat, M.A.; Al-Mazra, A. M.; Abu-Rjai, T. and Shatnawi, M.A. (2009):** Aqueous extracts of some medicinal plants are as toxic as imidacloprid to the sweet potato whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci*. *Journal of Insect Science*, 9:15.
- Baldin, E.L.L.; Vendramim, J.D. and Lourenção, A.L. (2007):** Interaction between resistant tomato genotypes and plant extracts on *Bemisia tabaci* (Genn.) biotype B. *Scientia Agricola*, 64 (5): 476-481.
- Brown, J.K. and Bird, J. (1992):** Whitefly-transmitted geminiviruses and associated disorders in the Americas and the Caribbean Basin. *Plant Disease*, 76(3): 220-225.
- Castillo-Sánchez, L.E.; Jiménez-Osornio, J.J. and Delgado-Herrera, M.A. (2010):** Secondary metabolites of the Annonaceae, Solanaceae and Meliaceae families used as biological control of insects. *Tropical and Subtropical Agroecosystems*, 12(3): 445-462.
- Chandler, D.; Bailey, A.S.; Tatchell, G.M.; Davidson, G.; Greaves, J. and Grant, W.P. (2011):** The development, regulation and use of biopesticides for integrated pest management. *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. Lond. B. Biol. Sci.*, 366 (1573):1987–1998.
- Cruz-Estrada, A. ; Gamboa-Angulo, M.; Borges-Argáez, R. and Ruiz-Sánchez, E. (2013):** Insecticidal effects of plant extracts on immature whitefly *Bemisia tabaci* Genn. (Hemiptera: Aleyroideae). *Electronic Journal of Biotechnology*, 16(1). <http://dx.doi.org/10.2225/vol16-issue1-fulltext-6>.
- De Barro, P.J.; Liu, S.S.; Boykin, L.M. and Dinsdale, A.B. (2011):** *Bemisia tabaci*: a statement of species status. *Annu. Rev. Entomol.*, 56: 1-19.
- Deletre, E.; Chandre, F.; Barkman, B. ; Menut, C. and Martina, T. (2016):** Naturally occurring bioactive compounds from four repellent essential oils against *Bemisia tabaci* whiteflies. *Pest Manag. Sci.*, 72: 179–189.
- García-Mateos, M.R.; Elizalde-Sánchez, E.; Espinosa-Robles, P. and Álvarez-Sánchez, M.E. (2007):** Toxicity of *Petiveria alliacea* L. on greenhouse whitefly (*Trialeurodes vaporariorum* West.). *Interciencia*, 32(2): 121-124.
- Golmohammadi, G.; Hosseini-Gharalari, A.; Fassihi, M. and Arbabtafti, R. (2014):** Efficacy of one botanical and three synthetic insecticides against silverleaf whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) on cucumber plants in the field. *J. Crop Prot.*, 3(4):435–441.
- Hebeish, A.; Fouda, M.M.; Hamdy, I.A.; El-Sawy, S.M. and Abdel-Mohdy, F.A. (2008):** Preparation of durable insect repellent cotton fabric: limonene as insecticide. *Carbohydr Polym*, 74(2):268–273.
- Henderson, C. F. and Tilton, E. W. (1955):** Test with acaricides against the brown wheat mite. *J. Econ. Entom.*, 48: 157 -161.
- Ipek, E.; Zeytinoglu, H.; Okay, S.; Tuylu, B.A.; Kurkcuoglu, M. and Husnu, Can Baser K. (2005):** Genotoxicity and antigenotoxicity of origanum oil and carvacrol evaluated by Ames Salmonella/microsomal test. *Food Chem.*, 93:551–556.
- Isman, M.B. (2006):** Botanical insecticides, deterrents, and repellents in modern agriculture and an increasingly regulated

- world. *Annu. Rev. Entomol.*, 51:45–66.
- Liu, C.H.; Mishra, A.K.; Tan, R.X.; Tang, C.; Yang, H. and Shen, Y.F. (2006):** Repellent and insecticidal activities of essential oils from *Artemisia princeps* and *Cinnamomum camphora* and their effect on seed germination of wheat and broad bean. *Bioresour Technol.*, 97(15):1969–1973.
- Lynn, O.M.; Song, W.G.; Shim, J.K.; Kim, J.E. and Lee, K.Y. (2010):** Effects of azadirachtin and neem-based formulations for the control of sweet potato whitefly and root-knot nematode. *J. Korean Soc. Appl. Biol. Chem.*, 53(5):598–604.
- Morales, F.J. (2007):** Tropical whitefly IPM project. *Advances in Virus Research*, 69:249-311.
- Oliveira, M.R.V.; Henneberry, T. J. and Anderson, P. (2001):** History, current status, and collaborative research projects for *Bemisia tabaci*. *Crop Prot.*, 20: 709-723.
- Palumbo, J.C.; Horowitz, A.R. and Prabhaker, N. (2001):** Insecticidal control and resistance management for *Bemisia tabaci*. *Crop Prot.*, 20(9):739–765.
- Pimentel, D. (2005):** Environmental and economic costs of the application of pesticides primarily in the United States. *Environ. Dev. Sustain.*, 7(2):229–252.
- Pinheiro, P.V.; Quintela, E.D.; De Oliveira, J.P. and Seraphin, J.C. (2009):** Toxicity of neem oil to *Bemisia tabaci* biotype B nymphs reared on dry bean. *Pesquisa Agropécuaria Brasileira*, 44(4): 354-360.
- Simmonds, M.S.J.; Manlove, J.D.; Blaney, W.M. and Khambay, B.P.S. (2002):** Effects of selected botanical insecticides on the behaviour and mortality of the glasshouse whitefly *Trialeurodes vaporariorum* and the parasitoid *Encarsia formosa*. *Entomol. Exp. Appl.*, 102(1):39-47.
- Thacker, J.R. (2002):** An introduction to arthropod pest control. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- Urbaneja, A.; Sánchez, E. and Stansly, P. (2007):** Life history of *Eretmocerus mundus*, a parasitoid of *Bemisia tabaci*, on tomato and sweet pepper. *Bio Control*, 52:25–39.

**Leaf morphological characters can be a factor for intra-varietal preference of whitefly
Bemisia tabaci (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) among certain cantaloupe cultivars**

Abd Allah, Y. N. M.¹; Metwally, S. A. G.¹; Refaei, B.M.² and El Sawaf, B.M.²

¹Plant Protection Research Institute, Agriculture Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

²Entomology Department, Faculty of Science, Ain Shams University, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 8/ 2/2022

Accepted: 22/ 3 /2022

Keywords

Bemisia tabaci,
Aleyrodidae, *Cucumis melo*, trichomes,
morphological aspects,
scanning electron
microscope,
cantaloupe growth
stages, and antixenosis

Abstract:

Cantaloupe, *Cucumis melo* L. (Family: Cucurbitaceae) is commercially one of the most importantly tasty, nutritional summer vegetable crops cultivated in Egypt and many countries worldwide. The whitefly *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) is one of the most serious pests attacking cantaloupe, causing direct and direct damage and consequently a significant reduction in plant production. To search for alternative methods of chemical control, the relative susceptibility of four tested cantaloupe cultivars; Arava, Majus, Darvina, and Royal 481 was assessed in field trials over 2015, 2016, and 2017 summer plantations. Arava and Majus hosted the lowest *B. tabaci* eggs and nymphs. Darvina was the most susceptible cultivar, especially to the nymph population. Royal 481 hosted the highest deposited eggs number. The morphological cultivars traits by scanning electron microscope clarified the rejection or attraction features to *B. tabaci* found in leaves over cantaloupe growth. The lowest infested cultivar "Majus" had high trichomes density. Royal 481 had the lowest density and longest trichomes, which facilitate adults landing to lay eggs and feed. Long trichomes can act as shelters for *B. tabaci* immature stages.

Introduction

Cantaloupe, *Cucumis melo* L. (Family: Cucurbitaceae) is commercially one of the most importantly tasty, nutritional, and exportable summer cucurbitaceous vegetable crops. It is adapted to be cultivated to several types of soils (FAO, 2006) in tropical and temperate climates on all continents in dry and irrigated conditions, directly seeded or transplanted in the open field or under plastic tunnels (Dogimont and Boissot, 2016). In Egypt, the cultivated areas of cantaloupe in old and new land reached about 42,037 feddans and produces about 475,817 tons of fruits in summer

plantations (Anonymous, 2015). Cantaloupe contains vitamins viz., vitamin A, and different groups of vitamin B such as Thiamin (Vit. B₁), Riboflavin (Vit. B₂), Niacin (Vit. B₃), and Ascorbic acid (Watt and Merrill, 1963). Tomato and cotton whitefly; *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) found to be one of the most serious pests attacking cantaloupe (Metwally *et al.*, 2013).

B. tabaci is a major pest invading the world, especially in tropical and subtropical regions (Toscano *et al.*, 1994 and Denholm *et al.*, 1996). The worldwide spread of *B. tabaci* continues to cause severe crop

losses on many crops (tomato, cucurbits, beans, cotton, potatoes, and sweet potatoes). It has an extensive host range covering 118 species of plants in 79 genera belonging to 28 families in Egypt (Abd-Rabou and Simmons, 2010). *B. tabaci* has become the most important pest for melon crops in several countries, causing losses of millions of dollars/years (Perring *et al.*, 1993; Polston and Anderson, 1999 and Azevedo and Bleicher, 2003). Nymphs and adults cause direct damage by removing phloem nutrients and inoculating salivary toxic enzymes, which weakens plants and reduces crop yield and quality (Inbar and Gerling, 2008). The indirect damage arises from sooty mold fungi proliferation on whitefly excrements of honey-dew deposited on leaves and impairing respiration and photosynthesis and development of disorders including silver leaf and irregular ripening of fruit (Oliveira *et al.*, 2001 and Byrne *et al.*, 2003).

B. tabaci transmits more than 100 virus species the majority of which belong to Begomovirus genus such as the tomato yellow leaf curl virus (Jones, 2003). Insecticides can affect pollinators which are essential to the successful production of cantaloupe crops. The development of new control tactics and viable alternatives to conventional pesticides for population management is crucial (Attia *et al.*, 2012). Whitefly control using resistant cultivars may be considered an ideal option in integrated pest management programs (Alves *et al.*, 2005). So, selecting resistant cultivars to be included in the control program is a must from the morphological point of view. The highest density of trichome was found in the resistant cultivar (Baldin *et al.*, 2012).

This work aimed at selecting low-infested cultivars with high production to be involved in the IPM

program. Moreover, recommendation their morphological characters in the breeding program.

Materials and methods

1. Field tests:

All field trials were carried out in the Experimental Farm of Plant Protection Research Institute at Qaha region, southeast of Qalyubiya Governorate (30°17'00 "N, 31° 12'00 "E of 133 meters (436 ft) below sea level) in Egypt over three successive growing seasons; 2015, 2016 and 2017 plantation summer. The four tested cantaloupe cultivars i.e., Arava, Majus, Darvina and Royal 481 were assessed. Cantaloupe seeds were obtained from Horticultural Research Institute Agricultural Research Center (ARC), Ministry of Agriculture and land Reclamation.

2. Experimental design and cultivation method:

An area of about 350 m² was used to establish the field experiments. It was divided to three plots. Each cultivar is represented by three plots (Replicates) running in 9 rows laying out using statistical design in a complete randomized block (CRBD). Each plot (replicate) measured 11.9 m² represented by three rows. seeds were directly sown in the field on Mar.16 in successive single rows on the southern edges. Rows are designed as 7 plants per row spaced 0.30 m apart. All the recommended agronomic practices for cantaloupe cultivation including irrigation, hoeing land, pruning, recommended fertilization, and harvesting adopted keeping the whole experimental plot area free from employing any insecticidal, fungicidal, and herbicidal plant protection measures during the whole period of study in summer (starting on Mar. until Jul.). The natural infestation of whiteflies was evaluated in the experiments.

3. Whitefly sampling procedures:

During the three vegetative growing seasons (2015, 2016, and 2017) assessments were conducted 15 days following plant settlement in the field and continued weekly. Concerning the susceptibility of different cultivars to *B. tabaci* infestation, one hundred and twenty leaves (10 leaves * 3 plots (Replicates) * 4 cultivars) for 15 weeks were randomly picked up from the three plant levels (upper, middle, and lower) in the morning before noon.

All leaf samples of each experiment were kept separately in polyethylene bags to be transferred to the laboratory. The presence of whitefly *B. tabaci* eggs and nymphs was examined with the aid of a binocular stereomicroscope. The number of eggs and nymphs was assessed on the abaxial leaf surface. Then, the number of eggs and nymphs per the three replicates in each experiment was estimated.

4. Laboratory tests:

Morphological aspects as shown by scanning electron microscope:

Morphological aspects such as trichomes density and length were generally correlated with the variations in oviposition on the four tested cultivars.

Sampling of young leaves were successfully taken 21 days after cultivation in the vegetative growth stage. However, older leaves were taken in interfering between the flowering and development of fruit stages 54 days after cultivation in the summer plantation of 2017. Leaf samples of each cultivar were picked randomly up early in the morning from the same place of each plant and were of the same age to obtain an accurate comparison between assessments. The chosen leaves were then transferred to the icebox on the same day in order to be scanned in the Central Laboratories Sector, The Egyptian Mineral Resources Authority, The Ministry of Petroleum, Egypt.

To obtain the number and length of leaf trichomes present in 1 mm² of the abaxial leaf surface (Where whiteflies usually feed and lay eggs), leaves of each material (Cultivar) were scanned immediately using Scanning Electron Microscope Model Quanta 250 FEG (Field Emission Gun attached with EDX Unit (Energy Dispersive X-ray Analyses), with accelerating voltage 30 K.V., magnification 14x up to 1000000 and resolution for Gun.1n). Trichomes density and length were estimated using Compu Eye, according to Bakr (2005).

5. Data analysis:

All the obtained data during the trials over the three growing seasons were subjected to analysis by using SAS Institute (1988) program. Duncan's multiple range test was used to obtain the mean separation and arrange cultivars according to their degree of infestation by *B. tabaci* eggs and nymphs at the level of 5 % of probability.

Results and discussion

1. Preference of cultivars for oviposition over 2015:

Results of mean weekly numbers of *B. tabaci* eggs/leaf in the field on four different cantaloupe cultivars (i.e., Arava, Majus, Darvina, and Royal 481) in the 2015 summer season were illustrated in Fig. 1. Darvina and Royal 481 were the most preferred and *B. tabaci* adults oviposited the high number of eggs. They harbored during the whole season total mean numbers (Mean \pm SD) of 10.02 \pm 2.42 and 10.3 \pm 3.4, respectively. Arava and Majus were the least preferred cultivars and had mean counts of 5.6 \pm 1.54 and 4.94 \pm 1.5, respectively ($P = 0.006$).

2. Preference of cultivars for nymphal infestation over 2015:

The mean population density of *B. tabaci* nymphs on different tested cantaloupe cultivars revealed that there

were significant differences among nymphs infesting tested cultivars. The highest mean counts of *B. tabaci* nymphs were recorded on leaves of Darvina and Royal 481 (17.4 ± 4.6 and 16.45 ± 3.1 , respectively), followed by

Arava and Majus cultivars (9.76 ± 2.35 and 9.3 ± 1.83 , respectively) ($P < 0.05$) (Figure 1).

Figure (1): Mean numbers (\pm SE) of *Bemisia tabaci* eggs and nymphs per leaf on the four cantaloupe cultivars over 2015 summer plantation season. Bars topped with different letters are significantly different by Duncan’s multiple range test ($P < 0.05$).

3. Preference of cultivars for oviposition over 2016:

The preference for oviposition by *B. tabaci* can be categorized into the following groups; the first group of higher oviposition preference is represented by Darvina and Royal 481 with seasonal mean counts of 6.2 ± 2.35 and 6.8 ± 2.3 , respectively. The second group of lower preference cultivars is represented by Arava (3.02 ± 1.01) and Majus (2.02 ± 0.6).

4. Preference of cultivars for nymphal infestation over 2016

Data illustrated in Figure (2) clearly indicated different levels of attractiveness for *B. tabaci* nymphs depending on the different cantaloupe cultivars throughout 13 weeks in 2016. Darvina had the same trend as in egg numbers. It still suffered from the severe infestation and it was significantly the most infested cultivar with mean population of 18.3 ± 4.3 . Darvina significantly followed by Royal 481 (13.2 ± 1.95). Arava and Majus were recorded with low number of *B. tabaci* nymphs (6.8 ± 1.6 and 6.34 ± 1.3 , respectively) [LSD= 4.1].

Figure (2): Mean numbers (\pm SE) of *Bemisia tabaci* eggs and nymphs per leaf in the four cultivars over 2016 summer plantation season. Bars topped with different letters are significantly different by Duncan’s multiple range test ($P < 0.05$).

5. Preference of cultivars for oviposition over 2017:

Results illustrated in Figure (3) revealed the variations in the oviposition preference throughout the whole season of study (Apr. 16 throughout Jul. 10) over the third season of 2017. Concerning the mean of eggs laid/leaf, "Majus" cultivar was the

least oviposited by females of *B. tabaci* adult (3.91 ± 1.3) (Figure 3) followed by Arava cultivar (5.2 ± 2.15) but it didn’t differ significantly from Majus [LSD=7.1]. The highest preferred cultivars for egg oviposition were "Royal 481" (14.12 ± 7.5) ($P < 0.0001$) and "Darvina" (12.45 ± 4.4).

Figure (3): Mean numbers (\pm SE) of *Bemisia tabaci* eggs and nymphs per leaf in the four cantaloupe cultivars over 2017 summer plantation season. Bars topped with different letters are significantly different by Duncan’s multiple range test ($P < 0.05$).

6. Preference of cultivars for nymphal infestation over 2017:

The overall mean of the four tested cantaloupe cultivars revealed that the highest infestation rate of *B. tabaci* nymphs was also recorded on Darvina and the mean count was 16.1 ± 3.01 . On the contrary, the Royal 481 cultivar (11.02 ± 2.7) which had the highest mean number of eggs harbored a moderate number of nymphs. However, Arava (6.42 ± 1.81) or Majus cultivar (5.94 ± 1.5) expressed slight infestation [LSD= 3.8].

7. Effect of leaf trichomes density and length in cantaloupe cultivars on laying *Bemisia tabaci* eggs in the early stage:

Data in Figure (4) clearly indicated that, the mean number of cantaloupe trichomes in the early stage. Majus had the highest mean number of trichomes (47.7 trichome/ 1mm^2). However, Darvina and Arava had a moderate leaf trichome density (31.1 and 26.2 trichome/ 1mm^2 , respectively). The lowest mean number of trichomes was recorded in the highest infested cultivar Royal 481 (20.5 trichome / 1mm^2). As shown in Figure (4) the trichome density in cantaloupe leaves had a linear

relationship with egg numbers deposited

Concerning mean length, the longest trichomes were recorded in Royal 481 ($377.7\ \mu\text{m}$), followed by the moderate length in Arava ($272.5\ \mu\text{m}$) and Majus ($209.8\ \mu\text{m}$). On the other hand, Darvina had the shortest trichome length ($115.1\ \mu\text{m}$). Royal 481 was the most infested cultivar with eggs (14.2 eggs/leaf in the early stage) and had the lowest mean number of trichomes (20.5 trichome/ 1mm^2) and the longest length of trichomes ($377.7\ \mu\text{m}$) (Figures 4 and 5).

On the contrary, the tolerant cultivar Majus (6.8 eggs/leaf) was found to have the highest mean number of trichomes (47.7 trichome / 1mm^2) and shorter trichome length ($209.8\ \mu\text{m}$). However, the shortest trichome length ($115.1\ \mu\text{m}$) was recorded in the susceptible cultivar Darvina cultivar (12.9 eggs/leaf). Statistical analysis of these data indicated a polynomial relationship concerning the length of trichomes (Figure 4). Figures (6-9) show scanning electron micrographs of cantaloupe leaf showing trichomes density and length in the four cultivars under consideration during the early stage.

Figure (4): Correlation between mean number of trichomes/ 1mm^2 and eggs on Arava, Majus, Darvina and Royal 481 cultivars in the early stage.

Figure (5): Correlation between mean trichomes length (µm) and eggs on Arava, Majus, Darvina and Royal 481 cultivars in the early stage.

Figure (6): Scanning electron micrographs of cantaloupe leaf showing trichomes density and length in Arava cultivar during the early stage.

Figure (7): Scanning electron micrographs of cantaloupe leaf showing trichomes density and length in Majus cultivar during the early stage.

Figure (8): Scanning electron micrographs of cantaloupe leaf showing trichomes density and length in Darvina cultivar during the early stage.

Figure (9): Scanning electron micrographs of cantaloupe leaf showing trichomes density and length in Royal 481 cultivar during the early stage.

8. Effect of leaf trichomes density and length in cantaloupe cultivars on laying *Bemisia tabaci* eggs in the late stage:

The highest mean number of leaf trichomes in the older leaves is still recorded in Majus (79.5 trichome/1mm²), followed by the moderate mean which was represented by Royal 481 and Darvina (43.6 and 38.5 trichome/1mm², respectively). The lowest mean number of leaf trichomes was recorded in Arava (27.7 trichome/1mm²).

As shown in Figure (10) trichomes density in the late stage had polynomial relation with eggs number. Regarding the mean length of trichomes, the longest trichome was found in Majus cultivar (266

µm) followed by Royal 481 (227 µm). Darvina had short trichomes (173.1 µm). However, the shortest leaf trichome in this stage was recorded in Arava (164.3 µm).

Data in Figure (11) revealed that the trichome length had polynomial relation with egg numbers in this stage. This means *B. tabaci* eggs didn't increase or decrease according to change in trichome length. One can conclude that the lowest mean number of eggs in the late stage was recorded in Majus leaves (3.7 eggs/leaf) corresponding to the highest mean of trichomes density and length.

On the contrary, the susceptible cultivars, "Darvina and Royal 481" showed a moderate mean number of trichomes.

Figures (12-15) show scanning electron micrographs of cantaloupe leaf showing trichomes density and length in

the four cultivars under consideration during the late stage.

Figure (10): Correlation between mean number of trichomes/1 mm² and mean number of eggs on Arava, Majus, Darvina and Royal 481 cultivars in the late stage.

Figure (11): Correlation between mean of trichomes length (µm) and mean number of eggs on Arava, Majus, Darvina and Royal 481 cultivars in the late stage.

Figure (12): Scanning electron micrographs of cantaloupe leaf showing trichomes density and length in Arava cultivar during the late stage.

Figure (13): Scanning electron micrographs of cantaloupe leaf showing trichomes density and length in *Majus* cultivar during the late stage.

Figure (14): Scanning electron micrographs of cantaloupe leaf showing trichome density and length in *Darvina* cultivar during the late stage.

Figure (15): Scanning electron micrographs of cantaloupe leaf showing trichome density and length in Royal 481 cultivar during the late stage.

9. Oviposition preference in relation to trichomes in cantaloupe early and late stages:

The data in Figure (16) demonstrated that the preference of *B. tabaci* adults to lay eggs decreased as cantaloupes grew (10.97 and 6 eggs/leaf, respectively). However, the mean number of leaf trichomes increased with the growing cantaloupe (31.4 and 37.3 trichome/1mm², respectively) and this may explain decreasing laying eggs by *B. tabaci*

adults in the late stage than the early one because of the high numbers of leaf trichomes which might prevent adults to lay its eggs in an easy way.

On the other hand, the mean length of leaf trichomes hadn't significantly affected by plant ageing (243.8 and 207.7 μm, respectively). In other words, trichome length became shorter in the older leaves compared to the younger ones but this decrease didn't be significant (Figure 17).

Figure (16): Difference between mean number of eggs in cantaloupe early and late stages. Bars topped with different letters are significantly different by Duncan's multiple range test ($P < 0.05$).

Figure (17): Difference between trichomes density and length in early and late stages. Bars topped with different letters are significantly different by Duncan's multiple range test ($P < 0.05$).

The obtained results revealed that, the four tested cantaloupe cultivars varied in their susceptibility to *B. tabaci* eggs and nymphs. Regarding, the mean number of eggs laid/leaf in the cantaloupe cultivars, the eggs were recorded in the highest significant numbers in 2015, 2016, and 2017 in leaves of Darvina and Royal 481 cultivars. Antibiosis symptoms, expressed as the failure of some whitefly eggs to hatch to nymphs (Less number of eggs) was on Royal 481 leaves. The data obtained over the years 2016 and 2017, that, Royal 481 was more attractive to *B. tabaci* to lay eggs in high numbers but the population of nymphs was low on the leaves of this cultivar as the plant grows. This may indicate less egg hatching. This result was in agreement with the results of Coelho *et al.* (2009) who investigated the resistance of melon cultivars to *B. tabaci* biotype B. The authors suggested that the antibiosis was the mechanism of resistance. Vieira *et al.* (2011) observed the high number of eggs on two soybean genotypes and a reduced number of nymphs, indicating antibiosis. Silva *et al.* (2019) depicted resistance expression in some commercial common bean cultivars to the whitefly. The resistance was

expressed as low egg deposition on certain cultivars and others showed lower adult infestation.

On the other hand, Arava and Majus showed a low preference for *B. tabaci* in this investigation, this could be attributed to antibiosis or antixenosis, or other physiological traits. Baldin *et al.* (2012) recorded that, the four cultivars Vereda, 'Amarelo Ouro' and 'AF646' were least infested with whitefly. They suggested that regardless of the chemical components or morphological characters the non preference of melon cultivar to *B. tabaci* infestation is good management that prevents oviposition, feeding, physiological disorders, and virus transmission. Royal 481 cultivar, which showed high infestation with *B. tabaci* eggs, had a high yield which didn't differ significantly from the resistant cultivar Majus. The susceptible cultivar Darvina had a lower yield.

Arava cultivar had lower *B. tabaci* colonialization and had the lowest weight cantaloupe yield. In a similar study, Baldin *et al.* (2009) found that the lowest deposited squash cultivar with *B. tabaci* eggs didn't give the highest weight of fruits.

Cultivation whitefly-resistant or tolerant cantaloupe cultivars is now one

of the most environmentally safe strategies in Integrated Pest Management. The search for resistant cultivars for the control of whiteflies can easily be combined with other control techniques that are environmentally friendly, such as the application of biological pesticides or biological agents (Stansly and Natwick, 2010; Vieira *et al.*, 2011 and Baldin *et al.*, 2012). Host plant resistance is characterized by the use of cultivars that have chemical, physical, and/or morphological mechanisms acting alone or in combination to reduce insect infestation by affecting herbivore preference (Antixenosis) and performance (antibiosis) or by keeping or promoting plant fitness after herbivory (Tolerance) (Emden, 2002 and Mitchell *et al.*, 2016). The assessment of novel cultivars for whitefly resistance traits is fundamental to providing farmers with options for pest control (Silva *et al.*, 2019). The development of sustainable methods for crop production and pest management such as organic agriculture and biological control is necessary (Togni *et al.*, 2019).

The scanning electron micrographs of the Royal 481 leaves revealed that the early stage had the low trichome density and the longest trichomes these may explain the preference of *B. tabaci* to lay their eggs on Royal 481 leaves. This is in agreement with Sulistyono and Inayati (2016) found that the resistant soybean genotype to *B. tabaci* infestation had the longest trichomes and the lowest mean trichomes number. In contrast, high density and short trichomes were recorded in leaves of Majus, which might alter egg laying and acts as protection means against *B. tabaci*. This is in agreement with War *et al.* (2012) who reported that leaf trichomes disrupt the movement of insect on the leaf surface, and thus prevents the insect to reach the leaf

epidermis. The high infested cultivar Darvina had short trichomes, which may explain egg preference and high nymphal infestation recorded in this cultivar. Generally, plant growing stages may alter whitefly egg deposition. One factor was the trichomes numbers and shapes. Our speculations are also supported by several other investigators e.g. Baldin *et al.* (2012) who found that the highest density of trichome was recorded in the resistant melon (*C. melo*) cultivar compared to other tested cultivars. Neiva *et al.* (2013) found that the high trichomes density in tomato lines expressed resistance to *B. tabaci* nymphs. On the other hand, Chu *et al.* (2000) reported that the top young leaves of cotton cultivar contain more stellate trichomes than the older leaves and suggested other factors in addition to trichomes affecting *B. tabaci* population development.

Some cantaloupe cultivars have shown levels of resistance to *B. tabaci*, these cultivars provide farmers options for pest control. Arava and Majus cultivars showed low infestation. The lowest infested cultivar "Majus" had the highest trichomes density this information should be involved in genetic breeding programs for cantaloupe, targeting the development of commercial cultivars less susceptible to whitefly.

References

- Abd-Rabou, S. M. and Simmons, A. M. (2010):** Survey of reproductive host plants of *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera : Aleyrodidae) in Egypt, including new host records. Entomological news, 121(5): 456-465.
- Alves, A.C.; Lourenção, A.L. and Melo, A. M. T. (2005):** Resistência de genótipos de aboboreira a *Bemisia tabaci* (Genn.) biótipo B (Hemiptera:

- Aleyrodidae). Neotropical Entomology, 34:973-979.
- Anonymous (2015):** Cultivated area in the old and new land. Agriculture directorates of governorates. Egyptian Ministry of Agriculture.
- Attia, S.; Griss, K.L.; Mailleux, A.C.; Lognay, G.; Heuskin, S.; Mayoufi, S. and Hance, T. (2012):** Effective concentrations of garlic distillate (*Allium sativum*) for the control of *Tetranychus urticae* (Tetranychidae). Journal of Applied Entomology, 136:302–312.
- Azevedo, F.R. and Bleicher, E. (2003):** Distribuicao vertical e setorial das ninfas de mosca-brancanasfolhas do meloeiro. Horticultural Brasileira, 21: 464-467.
- Bakr, E. M. (2005):** A new software for measuring leaf area, and area damaged by *Tetranychus urticae* Koch. Journal of Applied Entomology, 129 (3): 173-175.
- Baldin, E.L.L.; Beneduzzi, R.A.; Souza, D.R. and Souza, E.S. (2009):** Resistência de Genótipos de Abobrinha a *Bemisia tabaci* (Genn.) Biótipo B (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae). Neotropical Entomology, 38 (4): 526-530.
- Baldin, E.L.L.; Silva, J.P.G.F. and Pannuti, L.E.R. (2012):** Resistance of melon cultivars to *Bemisia tabaci* biotype B. Horticultura Brasileira, 30 (4):600–606.
- Byrne, F.J.; Castle, S.; Prabhaker, N. and Toscano, N.C. (2003):** Biochemical study of resistance to imidacloprid in B biotype *Bemisia tabaci* from Guatemala. Pest Management Science, 59:347-352.
- Chu, C.C.; Henneberry, T. J. and Natwick, E. (2000):** Silverleaf whitefly-trichome density relationships on selected upland cotton cultivars. (College of Agriculture, University of Arizona (Tucson, AZ), 2000).
- Coelho, S.A.M.P.; Lourenção, A.L.; Melo, A.M.T. and Schammass, E.A. (2009):** Resistência de meloeiro a *Bemisia tabaci* biótipo B. Bragantia, 68(4) :1025-1035.
- Denholm, I.; Cahill, M.; Byrne, F. and Devonshire, A.L. (1996):** Progress with documenting and combating insecticide resistance in *Bemisia*. In: "Taxonomy Biology, Damage, Control and Management, (Gerling D, Mayer R. Ed.)", Intercept, Ltd., Andover, UK, 577-603.
- Dogimont, C. and Boissot, N. (2016):** Insect resistance in melon and its modification by molecular breeding. In: Ezura H., Ariizumi T., Garcia-Mas J., Rose J. (eds) functional genomics and biotechnology in solanaceae and Cucurbitaceae crops. Biotechnology in Agriculture and Forestry, vol. 70. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- Emden, H. (2002):** Mechanisms of resistance: Antibiosis, Antixenosis, tolerance, nutrition. In: Pimentel D (ed). Encyclopedia of Pest Management. Marcel Dekker, Inc.
- FAO (2006): Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations** , Agricultural production, primary crops [http://www.fao.org.].
- Inbar, M. and Gerling, D. (2008):** Plant-mediated interactions between whiteflies, herbivores, and natural enemies. Annual

- Review of Entomology, 53: 431-448.
- Jones, D. (2003):** Plant viruses transmitted by whiteflies. European Journal of Plant Protection Pathology, 109:197-221.
- Metwally, S.A.G.; Shoukery, I .F. ; Younes, M.W.F. and AbdAllah, Y.N.M. (2013):** The susceptibility of certain cantaloupe cultivars to different three pests infestation in Qalyobia Governorate, Egypt. Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research, 91(1):151-167.
- Mitchell, C.; Brennan, R.M.; Graham, J. and Karley, A.J. (2016):** Plant defense against herbivorous pests: exploiting resistance and tolerance traits for sustainable crop protection. Frontiers in Plant Science, 7: 1-8.
- Neiva, I.P.; Júnior, V. C. A.; Maluf, W.R. and Oliveira, C.M. (2013):** Role of allelochemicals and trichome density in the resistance of tomato to whitefly. Ciência e Agrotecnologia, 37 (7) : 61-67.
- Oliveira, M.R.V.; Henneberry, T.J. and Anderson, P. (2001):.** History, current status, and collaborative research projects for *Bemisia tabaci*. Crop Protection, 20 (9) :709-723.
- Perring, T.M.; Cooper, A.D.; Rodriguez, R. J.; Farrar, C.A. and Bellows Jr, T.S. (1993):** Identification of a whitefly species by genomic and behavioral studies. Science, 259:74-77.
- Polston, J. E. and Anderson, P.K. (1999):** Surgimiento y distribución de geminivirus transmitidos por mosca blanca en tomate en el hemisferio occidental. Manejo Integrado de Plagas, 53:24-42.
- SAS Institute (1988):** SAS / capital state user's guide, 6.03 ed. SAS Institute, Cary, N.C.
- Silva, A.G.; Junior, A.L.B.; Farias, P.R.S; Souza, B.H.S. and Rodrigues, N.E.L. (2019):** Common bean resistance expression to whitefly in winter and rainy seasons in Brazil. Scientia Agricola, 76 (5) .
- Stansly, P.A. and Natwick, E. (2010):** Integrated systems for managing *Bemisia tabaci* in protected and open field agriculture. In book: *Bemisia* : Bionomics and Management of a Global Pest, 467-497.
- Sulistyo, A. and Inayati, A. (2016):** Mechanisms of antixenosis, antibiosis, and tolerance of fourteen soybean genotypes in response to whiteflies (*Bemisia tabaci*). Biodiversitas, 17: 447-453.
- Togni ,P.H.B.; Venzon, M.; Lagôa,A.C.G.; Sujii,E.R.(2019):** Brazilian legislation leaning towards fast registration of biological control agents to benefit organic. Agriculture Neotropical Entomology, 48(2):1-11.
- Toscano, N.; Henneberry, T. and Castl, S. (1994):** Population dynamics and pest status of silver leaf whitefly in the U.S.A. Arab J. Pl. Prot., 12(2): 137-142.
- Vieira, S.S.; Bueno, A.F.; Boff, M.I.; Bueno, R.C. and Hoffman-Campo, C.B. (2011):** Resistance of soybean genotypes to *Bemisia tabaci* (Genn.) biotype B (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae). Neotropical Entomology, 40 (1): 117-122.
- War, A.R. ; Paulraj, M.G.; Ahmad, T.; Buhroo, A.A.; Hussain, B.;**

Ignacimuthu, S. and Sharma, H. C. (2012): Mechanisms of plant defense against insect herbivores. *Plant Signaling and Behavior*, 7 (10): 1306-1320.

Watt, B. K. and Merrill, A. L. (1963): Composition of foods. U.S. Department of Agriculture. *Agricultural Handbook* 8:190.

Egyptian Journal of Plant
Protection Research Institute

www.ejppri.eg.net

Interaction effect of cantaloupe cultivars and sowing date on *Bemisia tabaci*
(Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) infestation and yield parameters

Abd Allah, Y. N. M. ¹; Metwally, S. A. G. ¹; Ibrahim, S.A. ¹; Refaei, B.M. ²
and El Sawaf, B.M. ²

¹Plant Protection Research Institute, Agriculture Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

²Entomology Department, Faculty of Science, Ain Shams University, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 10 / 2/2022

Accepted: 29/ 3 /2022

Keywords

Bemisia tabaci,
Cantaloupe, *Cucumis melo*, sowing dates
and *Bemisia tabaci*

Abstract:

Field trials were conducted to study the interaction effect of three cantaloupe sowing dates (Mar. 16; Apr. and Apr.15) and four cantaloupe cultivars (Arava, Majus, Darvina and Royal 481) on *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) over 2015, 2016 and 2017 summer plantation seasons. The obtained results revealed that *B. tabaci* eggs and nymphs were significantly affected by the tested variables (sowing dates and cantaloupe cultivars). In other words, Darvina and Royal 481 were the most oviposited cultivars in the three tested sowing dates, 10.2 and 11.7, 6.3 and 6.7 and 7.56 and 8.9 eggs /leaf, over 2015, 2016, and 2017 seasons, respectively, versus Arava and Majus ,5.6 and 4.5 3.5 and 2.8 and 3.91 and 3.02 eggs/leaf, respectively. Moreover, Darvina and Royal 481 harbored high nymphal infestations 16.92 and 16.4, 14.9 and 13.23 and 13.4 and 11.4 nymphs/leaf verses 11.45 and 9.33, 8.5 and 8.03 and 6.2 and 5.64 nymphs/leaf in Arava and Majus, respectively. The third sowing date Apr.16 harbored the lowest numbers of *B. tabaci* eggs and nymphs/leaf (5.43 and 10.7), (2.77 and 7.1), and (2.4 and 5.94) over the three tested seasons, respectively. On the other hand, the second sowing date; Apr.2 harbored the highest numbers of eggs and nymphs except in 2017 it harbored a moderate number of eggs, and *B. tabaci* eggs and nymphs over 2015,2016 and 2017 were 10.81 and 16.72, 7.21 and 15.3 and 6.21 and 11.85 eggs and nymphs /leaf, respectively. The first sowing date (Mar.16) harbored moderate infestation over the three tested years except in 2017 it was the most deposited and 7.72 and 13.15, 4.5 and 11.1, 8.9 and 9.7 eggs and nymphs /leaf, respectively were recorded over the three seasons, respectively. The lowest infested cultivar Majus yielded the highest cantaloupe weight (30.52 Kg/plot) followed by the tolerant cultivar Royal 481 (27.5 Kg/plot). The first sowing date Mar.16 gave the highest mean production of cantaloupe yield of 12.22 Kg/plot. So, the best treatment was cultivation Majus or Royal 481 on the first sowing date Mar.16.

Introduction

Cantaloupe, *Cucumis melo* L. (Family: Cucurbitaceae) is one of the most important vegetable crops in Egypt, as it is cultivated under different environmental conditions, open fields, under plastic tunnels, and in greenhouses for local consumption and exportation. It is adapted to be cultivated to several types of soils either clay or sandy lands. *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) is one of the most devastating pests on cantaloupe greenhouses and open fields, adult and nymph attacks cause direct damage by continuous sucking of plant xylem (Bleicher *et al.*, 2000) and also indirect damage, such as silverleaf (Lourenção *et al.*, 2011), sooty mold development and virus transmission (Nagata *et al.*, 2005), that reduce plant productivity.

A model of whitefly integrated pest management (IPM) has been proposed that conveniently organizes all *B. tabaci* control tactics into a multi-level, multi-component pyramid and defines major keys as "sampling" and "avoidance" (Ellsworth and Martinez-Carrillo, 2001). The planting seasons and plant varieties play an important role in the levels of the population density of pests. So, the planting date can be an effective pest management tactic because it results in asynchrony between the pests and crops (Albuquerque, 1993).

The current investigation targeted testing different cantaloupe cultivars cultivated on different dates to choose the best cultivar and date with low infestation and high production. This control strategy could be an alternative to chemical control.

Materials and methods

An area of about 1,400 m² represented the experimental area. Each plot (Replicate) measured 11.9 m² represented by three rows, cantaloupe seeds were sown directly in successive

single rows on the southern edges of summer plantations. Rows are designed as 7 plants per row spaced 0.30 m apart. All the recommended agronomic practices for cantaloupe cultivation including irrigation, hoeing land, pruning, recommended fertilization, and harvesting adopted keeping the whole experimental plot area free from employing any insecticidal, fungicidal, and herbicidal plant protection measures during the whole period of study in summer (Starting on Mar. until Jul.). The natural infestation of whiteflies was evaluated in the experiments. Field experiments were conducted over three successive growing seasons (i.e., 2015, 2016, and 2017) on three different sowing dates; Mar.16, Apr.2, and 16. In order to evaluate the impact of sowing date on *B. tabaci* infestation and the resultant yield as well.

1. Experimental design and cultivation method:

The four tested cultivars; Arava, Majus, Darvina, and Royal 481 were planted on the three tested fortnight dates over the three years of study. The experimental area is represented by 4 cultivars x 3 plots x 3 sowing dates. All plots were set up under a complete randomized block design (CRBD). Cantaloupe fruits were picked out from each sowing date and weighed separately in order to be estimated and compared with each other.

2. Data analysis:

All the obtained data during the trials over the three growing seasons were subjected to analysis by using SAS Institute (1988) program. Duncan's multiple range test was used to obtain the mean separation and arrange cultivars according to their degree of infestation by *B. tabaci* eggs and nymphs at the level of 5 % of probability. The data of sowing dates of cantaloupe were analyzed in two ways analysis of variance and means were

separated by Duncan Multiple Range Test.

Results and discussion

The seasonal mean counts of eggs and nymphs infesting the four cantaloupe cultivars sown in the recommended sowing date Mar.16 and the post recommended dates; Apr.2 and Apr.16 were tabulated in Tables (1-9). The obtained results revealed that the population density of *B. tabaci* and the resultant yield were largely affected by both sowing date and cantaloupe cultivars.

1. Oviposition preference of *Bemisia tabaci* in relation to cantaloupe sowing date and cultivars over three seasons:

Data shown in Table (1) indicated the seasonal mean number of *B. tabaci* eggs over 2015. Majus

Table (1): *Bemisia tabaci* means the number of eggs/leaves on the four cultivars over three summer plantation sowing dates (2015).

Cultivar	Sowing date			Seasonal Mean
	Mar. 16	Apr.2	Apr. 16	
Arava	5.6	7.3	3.8	5.6 c
Majus	4.9	5.9	2.7	4.5 c
Darvina	10.02	13.3	7.33	10.2b
Royal 481	10.36	16.73	7.9	11.7a
Seasonal mean	7.72 b	10.81 a	5.43 c	
F. value	9.2*			25.9**
LSD	1.03			1.2

Means in columns or rows followed by the same letter are insignificantly different at $P < 0.05$.

In the year 2016, data presented in Table (2) showed a similar trend. The lowest infested cultivar was Majus (2.8 eggs/leaf) followed by Arava (3.5 eggs/leaf). Whereas, Darvina and Royal 481 were the most suffered (6.3 and 6.7eggs/leaf, respectively) ($P < 0.05$). In other words, the sowing date;

Table (2): *Bemisia tabaci* means the number of eggs/leaves on the four cultivars over three summer plantation sowing dates (2016).

Cultivar	Sowing date			Seasonal Mean
	Mar. 16	Apr. 2	Apr. 16	
Arava	3.02	5.6	1.78	3.5 b
Majus	2.01	4.7	1.7	2.8 c
Darvina	6.15	9.05	3.8	6.3 a
Royal 481	6.8	9.5	3.8	6.7 a
Seasonal mean	4.5 b	7.21 a	2.77 c	
F. value	26.8**			35.4**
LSD	0.5			0.6

Means in columns or rows followed by the same letter are insignificantly different at $P < 0.05$.

In the third season of 2017, Darvina and Royal 481 cultivars

cultivar recorded the lowest mean numbers (4.5 eggs/leaf) and Arava cultivar (5.6 eggs/leaf) over the three tested sowing dates. However, Royal 481 suffered from the highest number of eggs in the three sowing dates 11.7 eggs/leaf, followed by Darvina at 10.2 eggs/leaf [LSD= 1.2] $P < 0.01$. Concerning the sowing date, it was clear from the calculated data that cantaloupe cultivars were planted on the third date; Apr. 16 had the lowest numbers (5.43 eggs/leaf). However, the second sowing date (Apr. 2) expressed the highest number of eggs (10.81 eggs/leaf). Moreover, the first sowing date (Mar. 16) showed a moderate eggs number (7.72 eggs/leaf) [LSD= 1.03] at $P < 0.05$.

Apr. 2 had the highest eggs compared to the other tested dates. Whereas, Mar. 16 showed a moderate number of *B. tabaci* eggs with a seasonal mean of 4.5 eggs/leaf. However, on Apr. 16 harbored the lowest egg numbers (2.77 eggs/leaf).

manifested high eggs (7.56 and 8.9 eggs/leaf, respectively). On the

contrary, low eggs number were shown on Arava and Majus (3.91 and 3.02 eggs/leaf, respectively). All the tested cultivars had high oviposition preference when sown on Mar.16 (8.9

eggs/leaf). However, the number of moderate eggs was recorded on Apr. 2 (6.21 eggs/leaf). The lowest was shown on Apr. 16 (2.4 eggs/leaf) (Table 3).

Table (3): *Bemisia tabaci* means the number of eggs/leaves on different cultivars over three summer plantation sowing dates (2017).

Cultivar	Sowing date			Seasonal Mean
	Mar. 16	Apr. 2	Apr. 16	
Arava	5.2	4.69	1.87	3.91b
Majus	3.91	3.98	1.16	3.02 b
Darvina	12.4	7.42	2.81	7.56 a
Royal 481	14.1	8.74	3.9	8.9 a
Seasonal mean	8.9 a	6.21 b	2.4 c	
F.value	9.8*			12.8**
LSD	1.2			1.4

Means in columns or rows followed by the same letter are insignificantly different at $P<0.05$

Concerning the average of eggs /leaf over the three studied years altogether on the four tested cultivars across the three tested sowing dates, significant differences were clearly observed. The results for cultivars in Table (4) showed that the low numbers of *B. tabaci* eggs were recorded in Majus followed by Arava (3.44 and 4.32 eggs/leaf, respectively). However, Darvina and Royal 481 had high eggs number (8.03 and 8.54 eggs/leaf, respectively) LSD=1.13 ($P<0.05$).

There were highly significant differences between the three tested sowing dates, Apr. 2 recorded the highest numbers of eggs followed by Mar.16 with moderate eggs number at LSD= 0.98 (7.04 eggs/leaf). Delaying the sowing date to Apr.16 led to a low egg count with an average of 3.13 eggs/leaf over three seasons. From the above mentioned results, it can be concluded that the best treatment to escape adults egg laying was on Apr. 16 followed by Mar.16.

Table (4): Average of *Bemisia tabaci* eggs/ leaves on the four cultivars over 2015, 2016, and 2017 three summer plantation sowing dates.

Cultivar	Sowing date			Seasonal mean
	Mar. 16	Apr. 2	Apr. 16	
Arava	4.61	5.86	2.48	4.32 b
Majus	3.61	4.86	1.85	3.44 b
Darvina	9.52	9.92	4.65	8.03 a
Royal 481	10.42	11.66	3.53	8.54 a
Seasonal mean	7.04 b	8.1a	3.13 c	15.56**
F. value	9.46*			
LSD	0.98			1.13

Means in columns or rows followed by the same letter are insignificantly different at $P<0.05$

2. Nymphal infestation of *Bemisia tabaci* in relation to cantaloupe sowing date and cultivars over three seasons:

Regard the tabulated data in Table (5) represented the infestation rates with nymphs /leaf over 2015 in three sowing dates was low on the Majus cultivar (9.33 nymphs/leaf). However, a

moderate infestation was recorded on the leaves of Arava (11.45 nymphs/leaf). The heaviest infestation was on Darvina and Royal 481cultivars (16.92 and 16.4 nymphs /leaf, respectively). The obtained results revealed that planting cultivars on Apr. 2 led to heavy infestation (16.72 nymphs/leaf) followed by Mar. 16

(13.15 nymphs /leaf). However, delaying the planting of cantaloupe to Apr. 16 led to lowest nymphs

infestation/leaf with seasonal mean population of (10.7 nymphs/leaf) [LSD=1.1] $P<0.05$.

Table (5): *Bemisia tabaci* means the number of nymphs/leaves on the four cultivars over three summer plantation sowing dates (2015).

Cultivar	Sowing date			Seasonal Mean
	Mar.16	Apr. 2	Apr.16	
Arava	9.76	14.83	9.77	11.45b
Majus	9.27	10.84	7.8725	9.33c
Darvina	17.36	20.42	12.98	16.92a
Royal 481	16.21	20.81	12.19	16.4a
Seasonal mean	13.15 b	16.72 a	10.7 c	
F. value	10.6**			27.2**
LSD	1.1			1.24

Means in columns or rows followed by the same letter are insignificantly different at $P<0.05$

In the second season (2016), the nymphs infestation on Majus and Arava was low (8.5 and 8.03 nymphs/leaf) compared to Darvina and Royal 481 cultivars (14.9 and 13.23 nymphs/leaf, respectively). The obtained results in Table (6) were the same compared to the previous season.

The mean seasonal population was slight by delaying the sowing date to Apr. 16 where it was 7.1 nymphs/leaf [LSD= 2.03]. On the contrary, the high nymphal infestation was recorded on Apr. 2 (15.3 nymphs/leaf). The intermediate infestation rate was on Mar. 16 (11.1 nymphs/leaf) [LSD=1.8].

Table (6): *Bemisia tabaci* means the number of nymphs/leaves on the four cultivars over three summer plantation sowing dates (2016).

Cultivar	Sowing date			Seasonal Mean
	Mar. 16	Apr. 2	Apr. 16	
Arava	6.8	12.3	6.34	8.5b
Majus	6.34	11.8	5.9	8.03b
Darvina	18.32	17.49	8.89	14.9a
Royal 481	13.11	19.48	7.1	13.23a
Seasonal mean	11.1 b	15.3 a	7.1 c	
F. value	7.33*			8.6*
LSD	1.8			2.03

Means in columns or rows followed by the same letter are insignificantly different at $P<0.05$

As shown in Table (7) the means of population density of the *B. tabaci* nymphs in the third season (2017) of the four tested cultivars were highly significant different between the tested cultivars [LSD=1.4]. The low infestation was recorded on Arava and Majus (6.2 and 5.64 nymphs/leaf, respectively). On the other hand, Darvina cultivar harbored the highest nymphal infestation (13.4 nymphs/leaf), followed by Royal 481 cultivar (11.4 nymphs/leaf). Regarding the effect of three tested sowing dates

on nymphs infestation, the obtained results confirmed the previous studied years. A slight infestation was recorded on Apr. 16 with a seasonal mean population of 5.94 nymphs/leaf. Whereas, the cultivation of cantaloupe on Apr.2 led to a high infestation rate of *B. tabaci* as 11.85 nymphs/leaf compared to the first and the third dates. The recommended date; Mar.16 showed the moderate nymphal infestation of 9.7 nymphs/leaf.

Table (7): *Bemisia tabaci* means the number of nymphs/leaves on the four cultivars over three summer plantation sowing dates (2017).

Cultivar	Sowing date			Seasonal Mean
	Mar. 16	Apr. 2	Apr. 16	
Arava	6.42	12.4	3.91	6.2 c
Majus	5.9	8.11	2.9	5.64 c
Darvina	16.1	15.74	8.5	13.4 a
Royal 481	11.02	15.31	8.42	11.4 b
Seasonal mean	9.7 b	11.85 a	5.94 c	
F. value	7.57*			22.27**
LSD	1.215			1.4

Means in columns or rows followed by the same letter are insignificantly different at $P < 0.05$

Data in Table (8) showed the average of *B. tabaci* nymphs infesting cantaloupe cultivars and on three sowing dates over the three studied seasons. There was a highly significant difference between the tested cultivars i.e., the low infested cultivars with nymphs were Majus (7.67 nymphs/leaf) followed by Arava (9.2 nymphs/leaf). The high infestation rate during the three sowing dates was recorded on Darvina (15.1 nymphs/leaf) followed by Royal 481 (13.74 nymphs /leaf)

[LSD= 1.4] $P < 0.01$. Concerning the sowing date, there was a highly significant difference between the three tested sowing dates ($P < 0.01$), i.e., the mean population density of *B. tabaci* nymphs decreased as cultivars sown on Apr.16 (7.9 nymphs/leaf). The cultivation of cantaloupe on Apr. 2 led to the highest infestation rates of nymphs (14.97 nymphs/leaf). However, the moderate infestation rate was recorded on Mar. 16 (11.4 nymphs/leaf) [LSD=1.2].

Table (8): Average of *Bemisia tabaci* nymphs/leaf on different cultivars over 2015, 2016, and 2017 three summer plantation sowing dates.

Cultivar	Sowing date			Seasonal mean
	Mar. 16	Apr. 2	Apr. 16	
Arava	7.66	13.2	6.67	9.2 c
Majus	7.17	10.25	5.6	7.67 d
Darvina	17.26	17.9	10.1	15.1 a
Royal 481	13.45	18.53	9.24	13.74 b
Seasonal mean	11.4 b	14.97 a	7.9 c	
F. value	11.8**			20.1**
LSD	1.2			1.4

Means in columns or rows followed by the same letter are insignificantly different at $P < 0.05$.

3. Interaction between cantaloupe cultivars and sowing date on the resultant yield:

Results in Table (9) showed the means of cantaloupe weight produced during the three sowing dates; Mar.16, Apr. 2, and Apr.16 in the summer plantation season of 2015. The lowest infested cultivar Majus yielded the highest cantaloupe weight (6.02 kg/plot) followed by Royal 481 cultivar which produced a weight of 3.885

Kg/plot. Arava and Darvina had the lower production yield of 1.74 and 2.6 Kg/plot, respectively. However, there wasn't a significant difference among the tested cultivars .Results in the subsequent Table (9) cleared that, the weight of cantaloupe considerably varied among the tested sowing dates. In this sense, cantaloupe seeds are sown on the closest sowing date Mar. 16 which had a moderate infestation led to the highest mean production of

cantaloupe yield 12.22 Kg/plot. On the contrary, sowing seeds on the latest sowing date; Apr. 16 yielded 6.05

kg/plot. However, Apr. 2 had the lightest cantaloupe weight with a mean yield of 4.25 Kg/plot.

Table (9): Mean of yield production (Kg.) per plot of cantaloupe cultivars over three summer plantation sowing dates (2015).

Cultivar	Seasonal mean of weight (Kg.) in sowing date/ plot				Total weight (Kg) from 3 plots
	Mar. 16	Apr. 2	Apr. 16	Seasonal Mean	
Arava	6.55	2.6	5.5	4.9	44.055
Majus	15.7	8.8	6.02	10.2	91.55
Darvina	11.9	1.74	3.8	17.44	46.71
Royal 481	14.73	3.855	8.9	5.8	88.81
Seasonal mean	12.22 a	4.25 c	6.05 b	9.6	271.125
F. value	7.94*			5.008	-
LSD	1.7			-	-

Means in columns or rows followed by the same letter are insignificantly different at $P < 0.05$

The obtained results clearly indicated that different sowing dates (Mar.16, Apr. 2 and Apr. 16) affected *B. tabaci* egg laying and nymphal infestation on the four tested cultivars. The second sowing date (Apr. 2) received higher numbers of deposited eggs and nymphal infestation than the other tested dates followed by the recommended sowing date (Mar. 16). However, the latest Apr.16 received the lowest egg numbers and nymphal infestation. Darvina followed by Royal 481 received heavy infestation on all three tested sowing dates. However, Arava and Majus received lower infestation levels of the whitefly on the same dates. Concerning cantaloupe weight, the highest weight of fruits was obtained from the first sowing date (Mar. 16) followed by the latest one. However, the second date gave the lightest weight probably due to the effect of heavy infestation. The results agreed with the results of Mohamed (2011) for the squash yield fruits over planting dates in relation to infestation with *B. tabaci*. Moreover, Abd El-Gawad (2008) revealed that there were significant differences between the different planting dates on the

infestation by *B. tabaci*. Our results were versus those obtained by Mohamed (2012) who found that the early planting of cucumber (Mar.15) harbored low *B. tabaci* infestation. Also, a similar investigation Shaalan (2014) in Egypt in fall plantation indicated that the early sowing date escape *B. tabaci* infestation. However, Saeed and Razaq (2014) indicated that there wasn't a significant difference in *B. tabaci* population among three different canola sowing dates. Helalia *et al.* (2011), stated that the earliest planting date produced a significantly high weight of the yield. Studying the effect of cantaloupe cultivars and the three tested sowing dates revealed that the best treatment was cultivation Majus or Royal 481 on Mar.16.

References

- Abd El-Gawad, A. S. (2008):** Study of integrated pest management on some pests of common bean plant. PhD. Thesis, Fac. of Sci. (Girls) of Al-Azhar University.
- Albuquerque, G.S. (1993):** Planting time as a tactic to manage the small rice stink bug, *Oebalus poecilus* (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae) in Rio Grande do

- Sul. Brazil Crop Protection, 12: 627-630.
- Bleicher, E.; Melo Qms and Sobral Ara (2000):** Uso de inseticidas seletivos no controle de mosca-branca no meloeiro. Horticultura Brasileira, 18: 359-360.
- Ellsworth, P.C. and Martinez-Carrillo, J. L. (2001):** IPM for *Bemisia tabaci*: A case study from North America, 20 (9): 853-869.
- Helalia, A. A. R.; Ali, F. A. F.; Hegab, M. F. A. and Kamal, K. A. (2011):** Effect of sowing dates of three cowpea cultivars on their infestation rate with cowpea pod borer *Etiella zinckenella*. Arab Universities J. Agric. Sci., 19(1):247-25.
- Lourenção, A.L.; Alves, A.C.; Melo, A.M.T. and Valle, G.E. (2011):** Development of leaf silvering in squash cultivars infested by silverleaf whitefly. Horticultura Brasileira, 29:112-116.
- Mohamed, M.A. (2011):** Effect of planting dates on infestations with certain pests and yield parameters of squash plants. Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research, 89 (4):1353-1362.
- Mohamed, M.A. (2012):** Impact of planting dates, spaces and varieties on infestation of cucumber plants with whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* (Genn.). The Journal of Basic and Applied Zoology, 65:17-20
- Nagata,T.; Alves, D.M.T.; Ionue-Nagata,A.K.; Tian,T.Y.; Kitajima,E.W. ; Cardoso, J.E. and Avila, A.C. (2005):** A novel melon fexivirus transmitted by whitefly. Archives of Virology, 150: 379-387.
- Saeed, N.A. and Razaq, M. (2014):** Effect of sowing dates within a season on incidence and abundance of insect pests of canola crops. Pakistan Journal of Zoology, 46 (5): 1193-1203.
- SAS Institute (1988):** SAS / capital state user's guide, 6.03 ed. SAS Institute, Cary, N.C.
- Shaalán, H. S. (2014):** Effect of planting dates on infestation with certain pests and yield of cucumber plants during fall plantation in Giza Governorate. Egyptian Academic Journal of Biological Sciences, 9(2): 23–31.

**Diflubenzuron and lufenuron exposed to magnetic flux
for *Earias insulana* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) suppression**

Mervat, A. Kandil; Omnia, Sh. G. Sheba and Hussein, A.M.

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 13 /2/2022

Accepted: 27/ 3 /2022

Keywords

Earias insulana,
magnetic flux,
diflubenzuron,
lufenuron, toxicity,
and biological aspects.

Abstract:

Two compounds of diflubenzuron and lufenuron were exposed to magnetic flux (180 millitesla) for potentiating purposes to study the toxicity and some biological aspects of the spiny bollworm *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) treated as newly hatched larvae. Half lethal concentrations were 10.6 and 7.39 ppm for *E. insulana* newly hatched larvae treated with diflubenzuron and lufenuron exposed to magnetic flux compared with the same compounds without exposure to the magnetic flux that had LC₅₀ 21.36 and 12.62 ppm. *E. insulana* treated as newly hatched larvae had larval mortalities of 61 and 62% for diflubenzuron and lufenuron without exposure to magnetic compared with 72 and 67% larval mortality for the same compounds exposed to magnetic flux; whereas, the untreated value was 5%. The larval duration was also affected by the elongation in the treatments exposed to magnetic flux compared to those without exposure. In addition, pupal duration and mortalities were affected by compounds used with magnetic flux to become 11.3 and 10.7 days and 45.4 and 53.9% pupal mortality for diflubenzuron and lufenuron exposed to magnetic flux compared with non-exposing compounds that were 9.6 and 9 days and 30 and 41.1% pupal mortality. The adult stage was also affected by reducing its emergency and the malformation was increasing as affected by the treatments exposing to magnetic flux compared with the same compounds without exposure.

Introduction

The spiny bollworm (SBW) *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) is the key pest of the cotton and a wide range of crops in various parts of Egypt. The larvae feed on fruiting parts of the cotton plant, especially the terminal buds (Khan *et al.*, 2007). It is exposed to many insecticides during controlling some pests from these compounds; chitin synthesis inhibitor (CSI) or Insect growth inhibitor (IGR) groups.

The chitin synthesis inhibitor (CSI) as diflubenzuron or Insect growth regulator (IGR) as lufenuron are widely used in the cotton crop until now, because it was a potent compound against the arthropod, especially, different stage larvae of Lepidoptera. Most CSI or IGR are primarily used for the larval stage that develops until molting but fails to molt due to inhibiting the new cuticle synthesis (Kandil *et al.*, 2013). Diflubenzuron or Lufenuron were used to control some lepidopterous (*E. insulana*,

Pectinophora gossepeilla (Saund.) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae), and *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) larvae, also recorded high increased mortality and caused the elongation of larval and pupal duration stages of *P. gossepeilla*, or *E. insulana* (Kandil *et al.*, 2013).

The magnetic flux was considered one of the environmental factors that had a high effect on some biological systems; also, some trials are continually in the laboratory to knowledge the effects of MFs on some biological aspects of various insects. Pandir *et al.* (2013) reported the effects of MFs on egg hatching that was delayed and the hatching rate when exposing the *Ephestia kuehniella* Zeller (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) adults to levels of MFs. Said *et al.* (2017) studied the interaction of some magnetic flux with some biological aspects of *P. gossepeilla*. In addition, Kandil *et al.* (2018a) demonstrated that magnetic Ferro- solution had a high effect on behavior and reduced the fecundity and fertility of *P. gossypiella*. But, up to now, no trials used compound magnetization for controlling the insects in the open field. Moreover, Kandil *et al.* (2018b) mentioned that a magnetic field of 28.6 millitesla (mlt) was affected adult *E. insulana* more than 2.21 mlt on the most toxicity, biological, life table, and biochemical parameters. Meanwhile, Yan, *et al.* (2021) investigated the developmental and behavioral effects of rearing *Mythimna separata* (Walker) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) in a near-zero magnetic field (<500 nT) compared to the local geomagnetic field (approximately 50 μ T).

So, the current work aims to study the effect of magnetic flux on diflubenzuron and lufenuron potentiation for toxicity and some biological aspects of *E. insulana* treated as newly hatched larvae.

Materials and methods

1. Insect:

Spiny bollworm (SBW) *E. insulana* first instar larvae laboratory strain used in this work was obtained from the laboratory of Bollworms Research Department, Plant Protection Research Institute, that reared on an artificial diet described by Amer (2015).

2. Compounds:

2.1. Diflubenzuron (Benzoy phenyl urea); Dimilin 48%; application rate is 200 ml / 200 L.

2.2. Lufenuron: (Match 5% EC); application rate is 160 ml/feddan.

3. Adjusting and creating the magnetic flux:

Different concentrations of the tested compounds were prepared as follows:

3.1. Diflubenzuron: 120, 60, 30, 15, 7.5, 3.75 and 1.875 ppm.

3.2. Lufenuron: 40, 20, 10, 5, 2.5 and 1.25 ppm.

Each compound is allowed to be slowly passed through a narrow plastic tube (5ml diameter) between the main two magnetic poles of the (Static Magnetism Device) with 180 millitesla magnetic flux. The device was designed and measured in the Faculty of Engineering; Menofia University as described in Figures (1-3). The compounds exposed to magnetic flux were prepared at the same concentrations mentioned.

Figure (1): Apparatus consists of 2 rows inside each row 8 magnetic pieces.

Figure (2): Apparatus of Mille Tesla meter.

Figure (3): Compounds exposed to magnetic flux.

4. Bioassay:

Toxicity of tested compounds; diflubenzuron and lufenuron (non-exposing or exposing to magnetic flux) suppress 1st instar larvae of *E. insulana* were tested. The concentrations were sprayed on the surface of an artificial diet in Petri dishes. Three replicates; each replicate 30 newly hatched larvae of *E. insulana* were allowed to feed (3 days) on the treated diet. The untreated (Water only) was done. All treatment was kept under constant conditions of

26 ± 1°C and 65±5 % RH. After 3 days, the dead larvae were counted to represent the acute toxicity of the two tested compounds. Analysis was conducted to estimate LC₂₅, LC₅₀, LC₉₀, and slope values by Probit (Proban) analysis software according to Finney (1971). In addition, the efficiency of different compounds was measured according to Sun's equation (Sun, 1950) by comparing the tested compounds with the most effective ones using the toxicity index (TI).

$$\text{Toxicity index} = \frac{\text{LC}_{25} \text{ or LC}_{50} \text{ or LC}_{90} \text{ of the most toxic compound}}{\text{LC}_{25} \text{ or LC}_{50} \text{ or LC}_{90} \text{ of the tested compound}} \times 100$$

5. Biological aspects:

The newly hatched larvae of *E. insulana* were treated by LC₅₀'s of the two tested compounds (Exposing to magnetic flux and non-exposing) to study some biological aspects. In three replicates, 50 individuals were used for each replicate. The survival larvae for

each treatment were transferred individually (after three days from treatment) by hairbrush to the diet tubes (2 × 7.5 cm) each containing about 3 gm of artificial diet. Another group used as untreated. The tubes were capped with cotton and kept under the previous conditions in an incubator and

investigated daily until pupation. Some biological aspects such as larval or pupal duration and mortalities %; also, adult malformations, and emergency percentages were done.

6. Statistical Analysis:

All biological aspects of *E. insulana* data values recorded were corrected by Abbott's formula (1925) and statistically analyzed, using Costat Statistical Software (1990) and then Duncan's Multiple Range Test

Table (1): Susceptibility of *Earias insulana* newly hatched larvae towards two compounds exposed to magnetic flux.

Compounds	LC ₂₅ (ppm)	LC ₅₀ (ppm)	LC ₉₀ (ppm)	Slope ±SE	Toxicity index		
					LC ₂₅	LC ₅₀	LC ₉₀
Diflubenzuron	6.79	21.39	189.01	1.334 ±0.113	32.4	34.5	38.7
Diflubenzuron +180 mlt	3.51	10.6	86.55	1.405 ±0.121	62.8	69.7	84.6
Lufenuron	4.068	12.62	108.82	1.286 ±0.114	54.2	58.6	67.3
Lufenuron + 180 mlt	2.203	7.39	73.22	1.372 ±0.11	100	100	100

Based on LC₅₀ values the two compounds exposed to magnetic flux were more effective against larvae of *E. insulana* than without exposure. The LC₅₀ values were 10.6 and 7.39 ppm for diflubenzuron and lufenuron exposed to magnetic flux compared with non-exposing (Nearly equal to two times) which were 21.39 and 12.62 ppm.

2. Biological aspects:

2.1. Larval stage:

Results showed that exposure of both compounds to the magnetic flux at a level of 180 mlt caused increased mortality and malformation in the larval stage than the same compounds without exposure to magnetic flux and untreated (Table 2). Data presented in Table (2) showed that larval

Table (2): Effect of two compounds exposed to magnetic flux on *Earias insulana* larval stage.

Compounds	Duration (days)	Comparing with untreated	mortality %	Comparing with untreated	Malformed %	Comparing with untreated
Diflubenzuron	18.3 ^b	+3.4	61 ^b	+56	11 ^b	+9
Diflubenzuron +180 mlt	21.3 ^d	+6.4	72 ^d	+67	19 ^e	+17
Lufenuron	17.6 ^b	+2.7	62 ^b	+57	13 ^c	+11
Lufenuron + 180 mlt	19.9 ^c	+5	67 ^c	+62	16 ^d	+14
Untreated	14.9 ^a	0	5 ^a	0	2 ^a	0
LSD _{0.05}	1.533		3.140		1.054	

(Duncan, 1955) at 5 % probability level to compare the differences among means.

Results and discussion

1. Bioassay:

Effect of diflubenzuron and lufenuron that exposing to magnetic flux (180 mlt) or non-exposing on the susceptibility of *E. insulana* newly hatched larvae after 3- days from treatment was presented in Table (1).

durations were increased to 18.3 and 17.6 days for *E. insulana* treated with LC₅₀ values of diflubenzuron and lufenuron, respectively; whereas, the same compounds had elongation to 21.3 and 19.9 days, respectively when exposed to magnetic flux (180 mlt), compared with 14.9 days of *E. insulana* untreated larvae. Results were in agreement with Kandil et al. (2018b) who tested two levels of magnetic field (MF); 28.6 and 2.21 mlt on *E. insulana* larval duration. Also, the obtained data are in agreement with authors that tested different IGRs against *P. gossypiella* (Kandil et al. 2013 and Said et al., 2017).

The larval percent mortality of *E. insulana* was 61 and 62% when treated with diflubenzuron and lufenuron. On the other hand, when the two compounds were exposed to magnetic flux (180 mlt), the larval mortality percent increased to 72 and 67%, respectively, compared with 5% mortality in normal *E. insulana*. Meanwhile, percentages of malformed larvae were estimated by 11 and 13% when treated with diflubenzuron and lufenuron. While, it's was increased to 19 and 16% malformed larvae, when the same compounds exposing to magnetic flux, compared with 2% normal malformation. These results agree with Pandir *et al.* (2013) that showed the effects of MFs on the survival of *E. kuehniella*. The highest level of MF (10 mt) had completed

mortality for *E. kuehniella*. Also, Matar *et al.* (2018) found that magnetic power (10 and 24 mt) had a highly significant effect on mortality and malformed larval and pupal stages of *E. insulana*.

2.2. Pupal stage:

Data presented in Table (3) obvious that *E. insulana* pupal duration treated as newly hatched larvae were 9.6 and 9 days when treated as newly hatched larvae with diflubenzuron and lufenuron and it was elongated to 11.3 and 10.7 days for *E. insulana* treated with diflubenzuron and lufenuron exposing to magnetic flux, compared with 7.6 days in untreated. Kandil *et al.* (2018b) studied the adult stage field strain of *E. insulana* when exposed to the magnetic field (28.6 mt); the magnetic field caused an increase in pupal stages.

Table (3): Effect of two compounds exposed to magnetic flux on *Earias insulana* pupal stage.

Compounds	Duration (days)	Comparing with untreated	mortality %	Comparing with untreated
Diflubenzuron	9.6 ^b	+2	30 ^b	+27
Diflubenzuron +180 mlt	11.3 ^d	+3.7	45.4 ^d	+42.4
Lufenuron	9 ^b	+1.4	41.1 ^c	+38.1
Lufenuron + 180 mlt	10.7 ^c	+3.1	53.9 ^e	+50.9
Untreated	7.6 ^a	0	3 ^a	0
LSD _{0.05}	1.354		2.57	

The exposure compounds to magnetic power (180 mlt) affected *E. insulana* pupal mortality percent treated as newly hatched larvae. The effects were obviously 45.4 and 53.9% as treated by diflubenzuron and lufenuron exposed to magnetic flux. While, it decreased to 30 and 41.1% mortality when treated with diflubenzuron and lufenuron without exposure to magnetic flux, compared with 3% mortality untreated.

2.3. Adult stage:

At the same trend, the adults treated as newly hatched larvae by the two compounds exposing to magnetic

flux showed a reduction in the percentage of adult emergence by 51 and 48% with malformed 9 and 6% and 4 and 7% for adult female and male with diflubenzuron and lufenuron exposing to magnetic flux comparing with 67 and 69% adults' emergence with malformation of 6&3% and 7&2% for adult female and male treated as newly hatched larvae with diflubenzuron and lufenuron without exposing to magnetic flux. While normal adult emergency was 89% with 1.0 female and 2.0% male malformed in untreated (Table 4). Chun *et al.* (2014)

stated that adults of *Euproctis pseudoconspersa* (Strand) (Lepidoptera: Lymantriidae) were

highly affected when they were exposed to the electromagnetic field.

Table (4): Effect of certain compounds exposed to magnetic flux on *Earias insulana* adult stage.

Compounds	Emergency %	Comparing with control	Malformed %		Comparing with control	
			♂	♀	♂	♀
Diflubenzuron	67 ^c	-22	7 ^c	6 ^c	+5	+5
Diflubenzuron +180 mlt	51 ^b	-38	4 ^b	9 ^d	+2	+8
Lufenuron	69 ^c	-20	2 ^a	3 ^b	0	+2
Lufenuron + 180 mlt	48 ^a	-41	7 ^c	6 ^c	+5	+5
Control	89 ^d	0	2 ^a	1 ^a	0	0
LSD _{0.05}	4.133		0.58	1.47		

Current data indicated that there was a positive effect of tested magnetic power (180 mlt) on the two compounds used (Diflubenzuron and lufenuron) that were exposed for 15 minutes; it increased the potency of the compounds and increased the toxicity that lead to an increase the mortality with malformed and a high prolongation the larval & pupal stages and a high reduction in adults emergency. Current results agree with many studies that showed that MF had a high affected on survivor, longevity, viability and fertility of *E. kuehniella* (Pandir *et al.*, 2013). In addition, Kandil *et al.* (2018b) exposed *E. insulana* adult stage to magnetic fields (28.6 & 2.21 mlt) lead to an increase in pre-oviposition, post-oviposition period, female longevity; while reducing was happened in oviposition period, male longevity, egg laying rate, fertility, and fecundity. Also, life table parameters were affected with two magnetic fields used by decreasing female progeny/ female (Mx), survival rate (Lx), net reproductive rate (Ro), intrinsic rate of natural increase (r_m), finite rate of increase (e^{rm}) and sex ratio; whereas, increasing was happened in generation

time (T) and doubling time (DT) compared to untreated value.

On the other hand, all biochemical determination for *E. insulana* as affected by two magnetic fields used had reduced total protein, free amino acids, total lipid, total carbohydrate, alanine aminotransferase (ALT/ GPT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST/ GOT) and fenoloxidase. Moreover, Amer *et al.* (2019) tested the effects of magnetic flux (20 and 180 mlt) for *E. insulana* treated as an egg. The magnetic flux of 180 mlt, followed by 20 mlt had many deleterious actions on biological parameters such as decreasing hatchability, larval and pupal weights, longevity, sex ratio, and no. of egg/ female; on the other hand, it caused larval and pupal mortalities increasing. In addition, life table parameters of *E. insulana* were affected; female progeny/ female (Mx), survival rate (Lx), net reproductive rate (Ro), intrinsic rate of natural increase (r_m), finite rate of increase (e^{rm}) were decreasing in both treatments.

Meanwhile, generation time (T) and doubling time (DT) were increased as affected by magnetic flux treatments as a 1-day old egg compared with

untreated *E. insulana* egg. Meanwhile, Yan *et al.* (2021) investigated the developmental and behavioral effects of rearing *M. separata* in a near-zero magnetic field (<500 nT) compared to the local geomagnetic field (approximately 50 μ T). The near-zero magnetic field produced by a Helmholtz coil system significantly lengthened larval and pupal development durations increased male longevity, and reduced pupal weight, female reproduction, and the relative expression level of the vitellogenin (Vg) gene in newly emerged females.

Moreover, the near-zero magnetic field had a considerable negative effect on the mating ratio of *M. separata* adults. In addition, the moths in the near-zero magnetic field displayed less flight activity late in the night than those in the Earth's normal geomagnetic field, indicating that the flight rhythm of *M. separata* may be affected by the near-zero magnetic field. Reduction in magnetic field intensity may have negative effects on the development and flight of oriental armyworm, with consequent additional effects on its migration.

References

- Abbott, W. S. (1925):** A method of computing the effectiveness of an insecticide. J. of Econ. Entomol., 18: 265-267.
- Amer, A.E.A. (2015):** Economic artificial diets for rearing spiny bollworm, *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). J. Plant Prot. and Path. Mansoura Univ., 6 (3):527-534.
- Amer, R.A.; Kandil, M.A. and El-Shenawy, R.M. (2019):** Comparison between gamma rays and magnetic flux effects on biological and life table assays of *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) eggs. Egypt. Acad. J. Biolog. Sci., 12(3): 121-131.
- Chun, j.S.i; Hongen, J.; Xiu, C. X.; Jin, B. Y. and Feng, L.V. (2014):** Effect of electromagnetic exposure at different frequencies on *Euproctis pseudoconspersa's* growth and development at different stages. Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research, 6(4):1072-1076.
- Costat Statistical Software (1990):** Microcomputer program analysis version 4.20, cohort Software, Berkeley, CA.
- Duncan, D.B. (1955):** Multiple ranges and multiple F test. Biometrics, 11:1-42.
- Finney, D.J. (1971):** Probit – analysis, 3rd Ed., Cambridge University Press, London.
- Kandil, M. A.A.; El-Shanawy, R.M. and Amer, R.A. (2018b):** Impact of magnetic fields and temperatures on biological, life table, morphological and biochemical parameters in *Earias insulana* (Boisd.). Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 96 (3): 967-985.
- Kandil, M.A.A.; Matar, A. M.; Hussain, A. M. and Said, S. M. and Nenaey, H.M. (2018a):** Effect of magnetic ferro-solution on behavioral, fecundity and fertility of *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Lepidoptera: Gel.). Egypt. Acad. J. Biolog. Sci., 12 (1): 79 -87.
- Kandil, M.A.A.; Salem, M.S. and Adly, A.M. (2013):** Biological and biochemical changes in pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* after treatment with Hexaflumuron and Chlorfluazuron. Annals of Agric. Sci. Moshtohor, 51 (4): 427- 432.
- Khan, R.R.; Ahmed, S.; Saleem, M. W. and Nadeem, M. (2007):**

- Field evaluation of different insecticides against spotted bollworms *Earias* spp. at district Sahiwal. Pak. Entomol., 29(2): 129-134.
- Matar, A. M.; Hussein, A. M.; El-Sayed, A. A. and Kandil, M.A.A. (2018):** Effect of magnetic power and radiant compound on some biological and biochemical aspects of *Earias insulana* (Boisduval) (Lep.: Noctuidae). Egypt. Acad. J. Biolog. Sci., 11(6): 85- 92.
- Pandir, D.; Ercan, F.S. and Sahingoz, R. (2013):** Assessment of the influence of magnetic fields on aspects of the biology of the adult Mediterranean flour moth *Ephestia kuehniella* Zeller, 1879 (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae). Türk. Entomol. Derg., 37 (4): 423-431.
- Said, M.S.; Kandil, A.A.M. and Matter, A.A. (2017):** Interaction of some magnetic flux with some biological aspects of *Pectinophra gossypiella* (Sund.). Bull, ent. Soc. Egypt, Econ., Ser., 43: 27-30.
- Sun, Y. P. (1950):** Toxicity index – An improved method of comparing the relative toxicity of insecticides. J. Econ. Entomol., 43: 45-53.
- Yan, M.; Zhang, L.; Cheng, Y.; Thomas, W.; Pan, W. and Jiang, X. (2021):** Effect of a near-zero magnetic field on development and flight of oriental armyworm (*Mythimna separata*). Journal of Integrative Agriculture, 20(5): 1336–1345.

Egyptian Journal of Plant
Protection Research Institute

www.ejppri.eg.net

Effect of methomyl on certain land snails under field conditions

Ismail, G.H.; Abou-Hashem, A. A. M. and Fatma, K. Khider

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 13 /1/2022

Accepted: 26/ 3 /2022

Keywords

Methomyl, land snails,
control, field
conditions, and Egypt.

Abstract:

Methomyl compound was applied as virulent baits with different four concentrations (0.5,1.0, 2.0, and 3.0%), and four treatments under each concentration were carried out as fellows (Fresh baits and baits treat after one, three, and seven days). Results illustrated that methomyl baits were effective in the percent of reduction of land snails *Monacha cartusiana* (O. F. Müller) (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae), *Succinea putris* (L.) (Gastropoda: Succineidae) and *Eobania vermiculata* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Helicidae) when it was used after preparing directly on an orchard tree and ornamental plants, Howsoever this effect was increased when baits were stored for one day, but the high effect was recorded when baits stored for three days, especially at high concentration 3%, reduction percentages were (84.7,73.2 and 59.8) and (88.3, 74.8 and 56.3%) for three species of snails in orchard tree and ornamental plants, respectively. Although the effect was decreased when baits had been stored for a week under field conditions. As well as the impression of lanate was increased as the concentration was increased in all treatments. Also, it is clear from the results that *M. cartusiana* was the most sensibility for these baits compounds under field conditions.

Introduction

The increased pest status has been associated with the cultivation of new crops, intensification of the agricultural production system, and then spread through human trade and the trend of species adapted to these modified environments. Furthermore, in some crops, the significance of gastropods is only now becoming apparent with the decline in the importance of other pest groups, such as insects, for which effective control strategies have been developed (Barker, 2002). Land

snails are considered the most injurious pest in Egypt (Heiba *et al.*, 2002).

Likewise, *Monacha cartusiana* (Müller), Mollusca, Gastropoda, Pulmonata, Stylomatophora, Helicoidae, Monacheae were widely distributed in the Egyptian Governorates. They are found in vegetable and fields, fruit crops, orchards, ornamental and medical plants (Abou Senna *et al.*, 2016 and Rady, 2019). In Egypt, land mollusks have been increased and distributed rapidly in most Governorates. They caused considerable damage,

especially in most areas where they found suitable conditions for survival and dispersion (Kassab and Daoud, 1964 and El-Okda, 1979, 1980, 1981 and 1984).

The present study is planned to investigate the effect of time elapsed between the preparation of methomyl poison baits and their use on certain land snails which are the main pest of orchard trees and ornamental plants under field conditions.

Materials and methods

1. Pesticide Used: Methomyl:

Methomyl (Copter 90% SP) is a Carbamate compound (S-methyl N (Methyl carbamoyloxy) thioacetamide) with a structure formula (C₅H₁₀N₂O₂S). Methomyl is purchased from the chemical company of Egypt chem international Agricultural chemical (Egypt, Cairo). The study was done in February 2021.

2. Mode of action:

Methomyl compound kills the animals by effectiveness on the nervous system.

3. Effect of the pesticide methomyl on land snails under field conditions:

This trial was appliance on orchard trees and ornamental plants with a heavy infestation of snails at Bahada Locality, EL-Qantar ELKhaerei, district, Qalubiya Governorate to study the activity of the carbamate pesticide methomyl. The toxicant was applied as poisonous baits at concentrations of 0.5, 1, 2, and 3%. Baits were prepared by using bran as carrier material with 5% molasses. Under each concentration, baits have been used directly after preparing and after one, three, and seven days of storage. Baits were prepared and stored under laboratory conditions as previously then transferred to the field. With each plant orchard, 10 trees (or

plants) were selected for every treatment.

Baits were put under each tree on plastic sheets (50 x 50cm) before sunset and left until sunrise of the next day. The treated baits were changed every day. The collected snails over these baits were watched to define the different species of land snails and count individuals from different stages (Adult and juveniles) of each species. On the other hand, the dead and alive animals were counted. Ten trees of each test plant were chosen as check control by using un poison baits. This experiment was continued for seven days. Before and after application snails were counted on the trees or plants, on the soil, and on herbs under the trees for three days left without collecting them. The percent reduction in the population density of each snail species was calculated by the formula given by Henderson and Tilton (1955).

% Reduction = $[1 - (t_2 \times r_1 / t_1 \times r_2)] \times 100$.

Where:

r_1 = number of alive snails before treatment in untreated plots

r_2 = number of alive snails after treatment in untreated plots

t_1 = number of alive snails before treatment in treated plots

t_2 = number of alive snails after treatment in treated plots

Results and discussion

The effect of methomyl compound which was applied as baits at four concentrations and different four experiment periods to control the land snails *Monacha cartusiana* (O. F. Müller)

(Gastropoda: Hygromiidae), *Succinea putris* (L.) Gastropoda: Succineidae) and *Eobania vermiculata*

(Müller) (Gastropoda: Helicidae) in orchard trees and ornamental plants at Qalubiya Governorate. Data in Tables (1 and 2) demonstrated the effect of methomyl baits on percentages of population reduction of land snails in

orchard trees and ornamental plants. According to average percentages of population reduction of land snails in orchard trees and ornamental plants.

It had been clear that baits of methomyl gave a high reduction percentage of all tested land snails when applied directly after preparing or after one day of application at different four concentrations 0.5, 1, 2, and 3%. Average percentages of population reduction were 50.8, 57.9, 64.5, and 74.9%, 39.2, 54, 55.2, and 57.4%, and 25.4, 39.3, 43.1, and 50.5% for *M. cartusiana*, *S. putris*, and *E. vermiculata*, respectively in orchard tree.

On the other hand, these percentages after one day of storing were 56.0, 64.1, 70.3, and 80.2% and 43.5, 57.3, 63.2, 65.8 and 63% and 34.1, 44.9, 50.4, and 55.3% respectively. However, the efficiency of this compound increased when baits had been stored for three days after preparing than another experimental period. The reduction percentages were (62.5, 67.1, 75.8 and 84.7%, 46.6, 63.2 and 73.2%, and 35.1, 45.2, 54 and 59.8 % for population reduction in orchard trees for all different land snails, respectively.

Also, the population reduction percentages of the same different tested land snails by methomyl baits after Seven days of preparing decreased with the four tested concentrations as the period was increased to seven days after preparing under field conditions. Means of the population reduction percentages were 39, 45.6, 48.2 and 49.2%, 23.6, 31.7, 35.7 and 38.8%, and 14.4, 21.3, 28.0 and 30.2% for *M. cartusiana*, *S. putris*, and *E. vermiculata*, respectively in the orchard trees.

While the results in Table (2) showed the effect of methomyl baits on percentages of population reduction of land

snails ornamental plants. According to average percentages of population reduction of land snails in ornamental plants. It had been clear that baits of methomyl gave a high reduction percentage of all tested land snails when applied directly after preparing or after one day of application at different four concentrations of 0.5, 1, 2, and 3%. Average percentages of population reduction were 48.7, 57.4, 68.9 and 76.9, 41.6, 48, 56.9 and 62.3, 30.8, 35.3, 41.6, and 52.4 % for *M. cartusiana*, *S. putris*, and *E. vermiculata*, respectively.

The efficiency of this compound increased when baits had been stored for three days after preparing than another experimental period. The reduction percentages were (62.6, 72.4, 79.3 and 88.3, 55.4, 64.8, 66.2%, and 74.8%, and 42.5, 44.5, 51.9, and 56.3 % for population reduction in the ornamental plants for all different land snails, respectively. Also, the population reduction percentages of the same different tested land snails by methomyl baits after a week of preparing decreased with the four tested concentrations as the period was increased to seven days after preparing under field conditions. Means of the population reduction percentages were 33.3, 40.7, 43.8 and 46.7%, 23.4, 27.3, 34.7 and 35.2%, and 12.4, 21.8, 25 and 27.5% for *M. cartusiana*, *S. putris*, and *E. vermiculata*, respectively, in the ornamental plants.

Generally, from the limited data in the different mentioned Tables (1 and 2), it was clear that there was a contradiction of act upon by methomyl between the different land snails under any executed treatment of baits with any concentration. Results showed that the individuals of land snails *M. cartusiana* were the highest perceived by this compound followed by *S.*

putris, while *E.vermiculata* snail was more resistant to methomyl than other species under field conditions. And the juvenile stage was the most sensibility

for methomyl than the adult stage for all tested land snails under all different experimental periods with any concentration of poisonous baits.

Table (1): Effect of time elapsed between preparation of poison baits and their offering to snails on their efficacy against certain land snails on an orchard tree.

		% Reduction								
		<i>Monacha cartusiana</i>			<i>Succinea putris</i>			<i>Eobania vermiculata</i>		
		Juvenile	Adult	General Mean	Juvenile	Adult	General Mean	Juvenile	Adult	General mean
Contractions	Treatment									
%										
0.5	Directly	55.6	45.9	50.8	40.1	38.2	39.2	28.9	21.8	25.4
	One day	61.2	50.8	56	46	41	43.5	35.7	32.5	34.1
	Three days	64.1	60.9	62.5	53.1	40.1	46.6	39.8	30.3	35.1
	Seven days	41.9	36.1	39	29.3	17.9	23.6	16.8	11.9	14.4
1.0	Directly	65.2	50.6	57.9	60.2	47.7	54	43.9	34.7	39.3
	One day	69.9	58.3	64.1	63.2	51.4	57.3	50.3	39.5	44.9
	Three days	71.2	63	67.1	68.3	58	63.2	50	40.4	45.2
	Seven days	49.3	41.9	45.6	36.1	27.3	31.7	21.2	21.4	21.3
2.0	Directly	70.8	58.1	64.5	61.9	48.4	55.2	45.9	40,3	43.1
	One day	76.9	63.7	70.3	67.8	58.6	63.2	51.4	49.3	50.4
	Three days	80.4	71.2	75.8	70.4	61.1	65.8	62.1	45.8	54
	Seven days	52.6	43.7	48.2	39.5	31.8	35.7	32.1	23.9	28
3.0	Directly	77.6	72.1	74.9	64.4	50.4	57.4	52	48.9	50.5
	One day	84	76.4	80.2	71.3	54.6	63	59.2	51.4	55.3
	Three days	87.2	82.2	84.7	77.2	69.2	73.2	66.9	52.7	59.8
	Seven days	54.5	43.9	49.2	41.5	36.1	38.8	32.1	28.3	30.2

Table (2): Effect of time elapsed between preparation of poison baits and their offering to snails on their efficacy against certain land snails on ornamental plants.

		% Reduction								
		<i>Monacha cartusiana</i>			<i>Succinea putris</i>			<i>Eobania vermiculata</i>		
		Juvenile	adult	General mean	Juvenile	adult	General mean	Juvenile	adult	General mean
Concentration	Treatment									
0.5	Directly	53.1	44.3	48.7	44.1	39.0	41.6	32.3	29.3	30.8
	One day	66.3	49.5	57.9	53.1	42.1	47.6	40.7	33.3	37.0
	Three days	69.8	55.4	62.6	57	53.8	55.4	44.2	40.8	42.5
	Seven days	40.2	26.4	33.3	25.1	21.7	23.4	14.0	10.8	12.4
1.0	Directly	63.3	51.5	57.4	52.0	44	48.0	37.3	33.3	35.3
	One day	79	63	71	69	55.8	62.4	44	36.6	40.3
	Three days	82.5	62.3	72.4	73.1	56.5	64.8	45.6	43.4	44.5
	Seven days	45.8	35.5	40.7	31.3	23.2	27.3	25,1	18.5	21.8
2%	Directly	75.7	62.0	68.9	60.8	53.0	56.9	44.7	38.4	41.6
	One day	78.8	72.4	75.6	70.4	56.2	63.3	49.6	42.2	45.9
	Three days	82.4	76.1	79.3	72	60.4	66.2	59.6	44.2	51.9
	Seven days	50.1	37.5	43.8	38.9	30.4	34.7	29.4	20.6	25
3%	Directly	81.5	72.2	76.9	64.2	60.4	62.3	58,5	46.3	52.4
	One day	86.3	82.4	84.4	73.3	62.2	67.8	64.1	50.6	57.4
	Three days	93.2	83.4	88.3	76.5	73.1	74.8	60.1	52.5	56.3
	Seven days	52.3	41.1	46.7	40.2	30.2	35.2	31.5	23.5	27.5

Discussing the foregoing results, it seems clear that methomyl was very effective on land snails under field conditions when it was applied as toxicant baits. The highest effect of this compound was found on *M. cartusiana* Followed by *S. putris* and *E. vermiculata* snails. As well as data emphasized that, as the concentration of methomyl increased, percent reduction was obviously increased for all tested snails under all experimental periods.

These results agree with El-Okda (1984) tested barn baits containing 2% methomyl after preparing under plant growth of berseem, wheat, and vegetables against the land snails. He showed that baits caused 12-35% mortality percentage of the useful glass shell snail, *Oxychilus* sp. As well as, Radwan and El-Wakil (1991) reported that methomyl compound was more effective on *E. vermiculata* snail than carbosulfan and thiodicarb under laboratory conditions.

Youssef (2006) found that methomyl compound gave the highest percentage of mortality for *M. abstracta*, *E. ermiculata*, and *Theba pisana* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Helicidae) after 72 hrs. of treatment and that because of the good fermentation of components of the baits. And after seven days the effect of the baits decreases due to the breakdown of their components.

References

Abou Senna, F.M.; Almaraghy, A.H.A.; Ismail, Sh. A.A. and Mohamad, A. (2016): Survey and population dynamic of terrestrial gastropods infesting certain crops at Sharkia Governorate. Int. J. Adv. Res. 4: 641–649. Doi: 10.21474/IJAR01/2128.

Barker, G. M. (2002): Molluscs as crop pests. CABI Publishing, CAB International, Walling Ford, U. K., pp.468.

El-Okda, M. K. (1984). Land Mollusca infestation and chemical control in EL-Ismaelia Governorate. Agric. Res. Rev., 62(1):87-92.

El-Okda, M. K. (1979): Laboratory studies on the molluscicidal toxicity of methomyl and aldicarb against some land snails. Agric. Res. Rev., 57 (1):199-207.

El-Okda, M. K. (1980): Land snails of economic importance on vegetable crops at Alexandria and neighboring regions. Agric. Res. Rev. Egypt, 58: 79 – 85.

El-Okda, M. K. (1981): Response of two lands Mollusca to certain insecticide Bull. Ent. Soc. Egypt Econ. Ser., 12:53-57.

Heiba, F. N.; Al-Sharkawy, I. M. and AL Batal, A. A. (2002): Effects of the insecticide, lannate, on the land snails, *Eopania vermiculata* and *Monacha contiana*, under laboratory conditions. J. Biol. Sci. <https://doi.org/10.3923/jbs.2002.8.13>.

Henderson, G.F. and Tilton, E. W. (1955): Test with acaricides against the brown wheat mite. J. Econ. Entomol., 48: 157- 161.

Kassab, A. and Daoud, H. (1964): Notes on the biology of land snails of economic importance in the U.A.R. J. Agric. Res. Rev. Min. of Agric U.A.R., 42: 77 – 98.

Radwan, M.A. and El-Wakil, H. B. (1991): Impact of certain carbamate and synthetic pyrethroid insecticide on the

- non-target terrestrial snail
Eobania vermiculata . Alex.
Sci. Exch., 12 (2): 129-139.
- Rady, G.H. (2019):** Survey and
population density of land snails
under different conditions at
Qalubia and
Sharkia governorates.
Ann. Agric.
Sci. Moshtohor, 57(3): 755–
760.
- Youssef, H. M. (2006):** Molluscicidal and
biochemical activity of some
crude plant extracts against
three types of land snails.
J. Agric. Sci. Mansoura, Univ.,
31(10): 6735-6742.

Morphological forms of varroa mites (Acari and Varroidae) in Egypt and Lebanon by means of scanning electron microscope

Amany, Saad M. Abou-Lila¹; Taksira, D.M.¹; Hebat Allah, S. Elsayh¹
and Sawires, S.G.²

¹Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

² Department of Natural Products, National Center for Radiation Research and Technology, Atomic Energy Authority, Cairo, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 16 / 2/2022

Accepted: 31/ 3 /2022

Keywords

Varroa destructor,
Apis mellifera,
scanning electron
microscope,
morphology, Egypt
and Lebanon.

Abstract:

In the present study, adult females were collected from infested *Apis mellifera* Linnaeus (Hymenoptera: Apidae) in Lebanon and Egypt which are represented in three different regions: Giza, Behera, and Beni Suef were examined by scanning electron microscope (SEM). The *Varroa destructor* Anderson and Trueman (Acari and Varroidae) has a remarkably different morphology between the two sexes. *V. destructor* was analyzed and studied with SEM response was the chewing off of modified appendages from the mite destroying the terminal segment used for attachment. Both the ventral and dorsal sides of the mite were scanned. Only varroa females cause the depriving parasitic action on bees. The adult female is reddish-brown with an elliptical shape and it is on average 1.1 mm long and 1.5 mm wide. It has four pairs of legs that enable the mite to move very quickly inside the hive.

Introduction

The varroa life cycle is tightly linked to that of a honeybee. Varroa mites *Varroa destructor* Anderson and Trueman (Mesostigmata and Varroidae) are a significant threat to bees. A varroa infestation weakens the immunity of honey bees and spreads disease. Varroa can only reproduce in a honey bee colony. Mites attach to the body of a bee and weaken it by sucking haemolymph (The bee equivalent of blood). This spreads viruses, including deformed wing virus sacbrood virus, and acute paralysis virus. *Varroa destructor* is an external parasitic mite that attacks honey bees [*Apis cerana* Fabricius and *Apis mellifera* Linnaeus (Hymenoptera: Apidae)].

Varroa mite life cycle has two stages. During the phoretic stage (5-11 days), mites ride on adult workers or drones, at the same time feeding on blood (hemolymph) from bees, usually from the inter-segmental membrane on the abdomen. Mites change hosts (hop from one bee to another) often and this contributes to the transmission of various viruses. *Varroa destructor* (Anderson and Trueman), is amongst the world's most serious and dangerous pests of European honey bees, *A. mellifera*. However, Anderson and Trueman (2000) stated that varroa mite (*V. destructor*) was most responsible for damage in bee colonies whereas, *Varroa jacobsoni* Oudemans (Acari and Varroidae) resulted less harmful to honeybees (James and Nalen, 2014).

It is believed that *A.cerana* is rarely affected and has a maximum level of natural defense against varroa mites. When *A. mellifera* colonies were introduced, Asian people begin to accept how dangerous these mites could be. As evidence suggested that these mites may take 50 to 100 years when Varroa's host shifts to another host and did the genus Varroa includes in excess of 18 genetically different strains of mites (Cobey, 2001). It is considered that *V. destructor* and *V. jacobsoni* are closely related and both parasitize the Asian honey bee (*A. cerana*) (Zhang, 2000 and Delaplane, 2001). Hence in 1904 Oudemans described that *V. jacobsoni*, is not the same species that also attacks *A. mellifera*. Anderson and Trueman (2000) corrected previous confusion and mislabeled the literature prior to 2000, recognizing *V. destructor* as a separate species. Accurate estimates of the effect of varroa on the apiculture industry are hard to find, but it is safe to colonies of honeybees worldwide, resulting in an economic loss of billions of dollars.

Varroa has caused lower honey production, which ultimately lowers the profit margin in beekeeping. Varroa also affected the feral (Wild) population of bees in many areas. Since feral colonies when become unmanageable for varroa and left unprotected. This ultimately results in the loss of feral colonies quickly as varroa continued to spread (Webster and Delaplane, 2001).

The aim of the present work was to study the morphology variation in *V. destructor* by the morphological characteristics of mites from Egypt and Lebanon using a scanning electron microscope during the summer and winter generations.

Materials and methods

Mites collected in the field should be preserved immediately in 70-95% ethyl alcohol this ensures the specimens are not damaged and, even if they are kept this way at room temperature, are good for morphological analyses for at least a few months, but often much longer. Should be stored in a cool environment, such as a fridge at 4°C (Human *et al.*, 2013). The specimens were quickly dried and then mounted on specimen stubs with gold conducting paints. Samples were gold coated in a layer of approximately 300 Å using a fine gold coating apparatus, an ion sputtering device (JEOL- JFC-1100 E). Preparations were examined in the JOEL-JSM-5400 scanning electron microscope (SEM) with an accelerating voltage of 30 kV.

Results and discussion

Data illustrated in Figures (1-4) showed the difference in adult females *V. destructor* were collected from infected *A. mellifera* in Lebanon and Egypt. In Egypt, three regions were selected.

Figure (1): Scanning electron microscopy images of a dorsal view of an adult female *Varroa destructor* mite different type of between Lebanon (A) and Egypt represented in three different regions: Giza (D), Behera (C) and Beni Suef (B).

Figure (2): Scanning electron micrographs of ventral shields of *Varroa destructor*. (A) ventral shields, (B) sterna shield enlarged, (C) genital shield, (D) endopodal shield, Arrows indicate specific areas of the shields. SP=sternal plate, GP=genital plate, P=endopodal plate, MP=metapodal plate, NP=anal plate, St=sternal setae, Est=endopodal setae, an1-3=anal setae.

Figure (3): Scanning electron micrographs of legs of *Varroa destructor*. Legs were categorized by length as Leg I, Leg II, Leg III, and Leg IV. (A) Leg-I is 624.4µm long and rounded. The condylophore is 78.94µm long. (B) Leg-II is 584.3µm long and dorso-ventrally flat with a short condylophore. (C) Leg-III is 812.8µm long, completely flattened, with short tarsi and the condylophore is 100.68µm long. (D) Leg-IV is 970.3µm long, completely flattened, and the condylophore is 86.07µm long.

Figure (4): Scanning electron micrographs of different kinds of body setae of *Varroa destructor*. (A) Dorsal setae in different dorsal body parts, (B) Higher magnification images of mid-dorsal setae, (C) Higher magnification image of posterior setae, (D) Lateral setae, arrows indicate types of setae.

Table (1): difference in adult females *Varroa destructor* were collected from infected *Apis mellifera* in Lebanon and Egypt. In Egypt, three regions were selected.

Size and shape	Lebanon (A)	Beni Suef (B)	Behera (C)	Giza (D)
Body Lengths μm	1.88 \pm μm	1.8 \pm μm	1.8 \pm μm	1.82 \pm μm
Body Width μm	1.33 \pm μm	1.2 \pm μm	1.46 \pm μm	1.29 \pm μm
Morphological Character	Oblate	Semi oblate	Oblate spheroid	Semi oblate

Data illustrated in Figures (1-4) and Table (1) showed the difference in adult females *V. destructor* were collected from infested *A. mellifera* in Lebanon and Egypt which are represented in 3 regions (Gov.) for morphological forms the following:

-Figure (1) SEM images of dorsal view of an adult female *Varroa destructor* mite different types between Lebanon (A) and Egypt represented in three different regions: Beni Suef (B), Behera (C), and Giza (D).

-Figure (2) SEM of ventral shields of *Varroa destructor* mite (A) ventral shields, (B) sterna shield enlarged, (C) genital shield, and (D) endopodal shield. Arrows indicate specific areas of the shields and differences between plats and some morphological characteristics among regions.

-Figure (3) SEM of legs of *Varroa destructor* legs were categorized by length as leg 1, 2, 3, and leg 4.

A-leg-1 is 624.4 μm long and rounded. The condylophore is 78.94 μm long.

B-leg-2 is 584.3 μm long and dorso-ventrally flat with a short condylophore. C-leg-3 is 812.8 μm long, completely flattened, with short tarsi and the condylophore is 100.68 μm long.

D-leg-4 is 970.3 μm long, completely flattened and the condylophore is 86.07 μm long.

-Figure (4) SEM of different kinds of body setae of *Varroa destructor*.

(A) Dorsal setae in different dorsal body parts.

(B) Higher magnification images of mid-dorsal setae.

(C) Higher magnification images of posterior setae.

(D) Lateral setae, arrows indicate types of setae.

Therefore, treatment thresholds have been developed for specific geographic climatic conditions adapted for specific honey bee breads (Locke, 2016). SEM micro graphs showed (Figure 1) dorsally serrated setae dorsally and entire simple setae ventrally. The most possible explanation is that the dorsal setae are probably used to interlock with the body hairs of bees during the phoretic period. The ventrally entire spinecent setae may help *Varroa destructor* to walk on brood cells and on bee's bodies. All these setae are reflexed posteriorly. Nuzzaci *et al.* (1992) described the presence of some specialized sensilla on mouth parts, suspected by ultrastructural evidence to be gustatory chemical sensilla and mecano sensilla.

These are probably related to the feeding behavior of *Varroa* and not so much involved in orientation. Büchler,(2015) observed that *Varroa* tolerance in honey bee occurrence characters and breeding. The morphological plasticity suggests that K-type *Varroa destructor* also uses the marginal setae to grab the integument of the larvae during the feeding periods inside the sealed cell, and also uses to grab the adult bees during the hibernation times inside the tergits of winter bees, and the phoretic period. Davis and Camin (1976) have

demonstrated the primary role of marginal setae in *Dermanyssus prognepphilus* Ewing (Acari: Dermanyssidae) mites, ectoparasites of birds are for attachment.

Generally: comment on that, find that the *Varroa destructor* in Egypt (Behera, Giza and Beni Suef) and Lebanon in size and some morphological differences between them and (fig1) SEM images of a dorsal view of an adult female *V. destructor* mite different type of between Lebanon (A) and Egypt represented in three different regions: Beni Suef (B), Behera (C) and Giza (D). Kuenen and Calderone (1998) stated that positive anemotaxis by *Varroa* mites: responses to bee odour plumes and single clean-air puffs. It is a study in agreement with the results of this research.

Shimanuki and Knox, (2000) showed that diagnosis of honey bee diseases of both brood and adult and using some chemicals for controlling diseases.

It is concluded that *V. destructor* is still the common species in both Egypt and Lebanon, despite the morphological differences.

References

- Anderson, D. L. and Trueman, J.W.H. (2000):** *Varroa jacobsoni* (Acari: Varroidae) is more than one species. *Experimental and Applied Acarology*, 24:165-189.
- Büchler, R. (2015):** *Varroa* tolerance in honey bees-occurrence, characters and breeding. *Bee World*, 75: 54–70.
- Cobey, S. (2001):** The *Varroa* species complex: Identifying *Varroa destructor* and new strategies of control. *American Bee Journal*, 141(3):194-196.
- Davis, J.C. and Camin, J.H. (1976):** Setae of the anterior tarsi of the martin mite, *Dermanyssus prognepphilus* (Acari: Dermanyssidae). *J. Kans. Entomol. Soc.*, 49:441–449.
- Delaplane, K.S. (2001):** *Varroa destructor*: revolution in the Making. *Bee World*, 82(4):157-159.
- Human, H.; Brodschneider, R.; Dietemann, V.; Dively, G. et al. (2013):** Miscellaneous standard methods for *Apis mellifera* research. *Journal of Apicultural Research*, 52 (4): 1-53. DOI: 10.3896/IBRA.1.52.4.10.
- James, D.E. and Nalen, C.M.Z. (2014):** *Varroa* Mite, *Varroa destructor* Anderson and Trueman (Arachnida: Acari:Varroidae). Extension Assistant; Department of Entomology and Nematology, UF/IFAS Extension, Gainesville. FL 32611.
- Kuenen, L. P. S. and Calderone, N. W. (1998):** Positive anemotaxis by varroa mite: responses to bee odour plumes and single clean-air puffs. *Physiol. Entomol.*, 23:255Y264.
- Locke, B. (2016):** Natural varroa mite-surviving *Apis mellifera* honeybee populations. *Apidologie*, 47(3): 467-482.
- Nuzzaci, G.; de Lillo, E. and Porcelli, F. (1992):** Functional morphology of mouthpart sensilla in females of *Varroa jacobsoni* Oudemans (Acari: Varroidae). *Entomologica Bari*, 27: 41-67.
- Oudemans, A. C. (1904):** *Acarologische Aanteekeningen XII*. *Entomologische Berichten Uitgegeven Door de Nederlandse Entomologische Vereeniging*, 1: 18.
- Shimanuki, H. and Knox, D.A. (2000):** Diagnosis of Honey bee

- Diseases. Agriculture
Handbook No. AH690, pp.61.
- Webster, T. C. and Delaplane, K.S. (2001):** Mites of the Honey bee. Dadant and Sons, Inc., Hamilton, Illinois. pp. 280.
- Zhang, Z.Q. (2000):** Notes on *Varroa destructor* (Acari: Varrionidae) parasitic on honey bees in New Zealand. Systematic and Appl. Acarol. Special Publications, 5 (S).

Instruction to authors

Original articles are full length papers describing original research. The paper should not exceed 15 pages of double-spaced typed text (including abstract, tables, figures and references). One double-spaced typed page contains approximately 300-350 words. Reviews are normally by invitation from the Editor-in-Chief. However, authors are encouraged to submit a tentative title and a table of contents of a proposed review for consideration. These reviews should not exceed 20 pages of double-spaced typed text (Including abstract, tables, figures and references). Scientific notes and short communications to the Editor usually on matters of general concern to plant protection, are welcome but should not exceed 4 typed pages. The decision to publish submitted scientific notes and short communications with the Editor-in-Chief.

Manuscripts should be written in clear, concise, and grammatically correct English. Submission of a manuscript implies: that the work described has not been published before; that it is not under consideration for publication anywhere else. Authors should submit their manuscripts online. To the Email: shaabanabdrabou59@yahoo.com

Manuscript preparation

Title: The title should reflect the most important aspects of the article, in a preferably concise form of not more than 150 characters and spaces. By-line The authors' names should be followed by affiliations and addresses.

Abstracts are required for all the manuscripts. They should be typed in one paragraph and limited to max.150- 200 words. The abstract should not contain any undefined abbreviations or unspecified references.

Keywords: Most important words of paper. Should be from 4 to 6 words.

Text: Main text should contain (1) an Introduction (2) a Material and Methods (3) a Results (4) a Discussion (5) a Conclusion (6) a References

Text formatting: Use a normal, plain font (e.g., 14 Point Times Roman) for text.

Abbreviations should be defined at first mention and used consistently thereafter. Authors should adhere to the rules governing scientific nomenclature to the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature. All biotica (crops, plants, insects, birds, mammals, etc.) should be identified by their scientific names including authors (and Order: Family) when the English term is first used in the main text, with the exception of common domestic plants and animals. Scientific names should be as follows: In the Title only give the Latin name but No authority or (Order: Family); in the Abstract all Latin names should be accompanied with the correct authority and with (Order: Family); in addition, at the first mention in the body of the text - and only then - these data should be given; authority, the order, family, should also go in the Key Words list.

Footnotes

Footnotes on the title page are not given reference symbols. Footnotes to the text are numbered consecutively; those to tables should be indicated by superscript lower-case letters (or asterisks for significance values and other statistical data).

References

The list of References should only include works that are cited in the text and that have been published or accepted for publication. Personal communications and unpublished works should only be mentioned in the text.

Cite references in the text by name and year in parentheses. Some examples:

- Negotiation research spans many disciplines (Abd-Rabou, 1996).
- This result was later contradicted (Simmons and Abd-Rabou, 2009).
- This effect has been widely studied (Abd-Rabou, 1998; Simmons *et al.*, 2002; Evans and Abd-Rabou, 2005 and Abd-Rabou *et al.*, 2005).

List style

Reference list entries should be alphabetized by the last names of the first author of each work.

Journal article

Abd-Rabou, S. (1998): The efficacy of indigenous parasitoids in the biological control of *Siphoninus phillyreae* (Homoptera: Aleyrodidae) on pomegranate in Egypt. Pan-Pacific Entomologists, 74 (3): 169-173.

Evans and Abd-Rabou (2005): Two new species and additional records of Egyptian Aphelinidae. Zootaxa, 833:1-7.

Simmons, A. and Abd-Rabou, S. (2006): Whitefly populations in vegetables crops with different fertilizers. 52nd Annual meeting of the South Carolina Entomological Society, Mc Cormick, Sc., October 19-20.

Abd-Rabou, S. and Simmons, A. M. (2012): *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) whitefly as a pest in Egypt. Advances In Agricultural Research In Egypt, 10 (1): 1-82.

Figures Line-drawing should be clear and of high quality. Cite all figures in numerical order in the manuscript.

Tables The title should be self-explanatory and include enough information so that each table is intelligible without reference to the text or other tables. The title should summarize the information presented in the table without repeating the subheadings. Subheadings should be brief, nonstandard ones can be explained in footnotes. Cite tables in numerical order in the manuscript. Information presented in a table should agree with that in the text.